

EXPLORING THE APPLICATION OF MATCH ANALYSIS IN HIGH-
PERFORMANCE FOOTBALL (SOCCER) ENVIRONMENTS

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Abstract

Rationale: This thesis aims to enhance understanding of applied match analysis in high-performance football by focusing on the under-researched perspectives of its main stakeholders: analysts, players, and coaches. Using a nested theoretical framework of culture, motivational climate, and coach-athlete relationships, this research investigates the complexity of match analysis. It focuses on the early career experiences of neophyte analysts and the context-specific demands in women's football, including calls for gender-responsive coaching. The goal is to provide novel insights to inform future application and examination of match analysis.

Methods: The thesis adopted a qualitative research design guided by constructivism and interpretivism to explore three purposefully chosen case studies: neophyte analysts in male youth football (Chapter 4), players in a female international youth football squad (Chapter 5), and a professional coach's experiences in women's football (Chapter 6). Data collection methods included interviews, participant observations, and archival data, with reflexive thematic analysis used to identify patterns and themes. Quality assurance was ensured through credibility, dependability, confirmability, and transferability.

Findings: Chapter 4 reveals a typical model of novice analysts' experiences in professional male youth football. Initially, they build relationships with the coach, then focus on analysis systems, feedback efficacy, and the impact of their analysis. Chapter 5

shows that female international youth football players find match analysis beneficial for game understanding, decision-making, and confidence. Players emphasised the importance of need-supportive team feedback meetings and an empowering coaching environment. Chapter 6 highlights the necessity of an athlete-centred coaching philosophy in applying match analysis, fostering trust, open feedback, and player voice. It underscores the importance of context, demonstrating how gender, age, coaching environment, and available technology influence the coach's match analysis.

Synthesis: The thesis reveals that collaborative match analysis, incorporating analysts, players, and coaches, can enhance performance by promoting active participation and ownership. A nested theoretical perspective, considering culture, motivational climate, and coach-athlete relationships, provides a comprehensive framework for understanding match analysis. Furthermore, context-specific factors are critical in developing the effectiveness of match analysis.

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1 Introduction

This chapter defines the role and scope of match analysis within high-performance football, highlighting the involvement of performance analysts (analysts), players, and coaches. It introduces the theoretical framework of culture, motivational climate, and the coach-athlete relationship, which underpins the thesis. Subsequently, a significant research problem is then identified – the complexity of match analysis needs to be better understood through the perspective of its key stakeholders. The thesis aims are then outlined, focusing on the early career experiences of neophyte analysts and the context-specific demands in women's football. Finally, the organisation of the thesis is presented.

1.1 Background

Performance analysis employs technology to systematically monitor and analyse sports performance, making it indispensable for coaches (Carling and Datson, 2022). Coaches often struggle with accurately observing and recalling performance due to issues with attention, memory, and bias (Franks and Miller, 1986; Franks and Miller, 1991; Laird and Waters, 2008; Nicholls and Worsfold, 2016; Maslovat and Franks, 2020). Accurate coach feedback is crucial for player learning, development, and performance (Butterworth and Woodward, 2023), making observational inaccuracy problematic. Subsequently, performance analysis bridges these observational gaps by generating detailed and accurate performance data (Carling, Lawlor and Wells, 2018), which augments the feedback process (O'Donoghue and Mayes, 2013; Pearson *et al.*, 2023). For example, it

provides data such as passing accuracy rates, shot conversion percentages, and heatmaps of positional play. Additionally, video footage highlights key match events and tactical patterns, revealing team dynamics and individual contributions (Carling, 2019). Consequently, coaches who use performance analysis are better informed about performances (Carling, 2019), potentially gaining competitive advantages (Kioussis, 2018). Therefore, from bio-scientific perspectives, which predominate in sport science and coaching (Konoval, Denison and Mills, 2019; Nichol *et al.*, 2019; Barker, Nyberg and Larsson, 2022), performance analysis is essential. Thus, performance analysis techniques are pervasive in high-performance team sports, normalised through the deployment of multidisciplinary sport science support teams (Waters *et al.*, 2019; Otte *et al.*, 2020b).

One performance analysis method used extensively within high-performance team sports, and especially football, is (notational) match analysis (Prim and van Rooyen, 2013; Horne, 2014; Carling, Lawlor and Wells, 2018; Lomax, 2018). It involves systematic observation, video recording, and objective analysis of technical and tactical performance (Wright *et al.*, 2013). This process is based on key performance indicators (KPIs), which are specific, measurable metrics believed to be essential to team success (Wright, Carling and Collins, 2014). These KPIs guide the generation of categorised video highlights and reliable match statistics, ensuring that match analysis focuses on critical aspects of team performance (Hughes and Bartlett, 2020). For example, KPIs could include successful passes or defensive recoveries in key areas of the pitch, reflecting critical elements of a

team's tactical performance. In high-performance football, match analysis is common in both senior and youth settings. A survey of 46 elite UK-based team sport coaches found that 84% received match analysis output after most or every game (Wright, Atkins and Jones, 2012). Similarly, 84% of 123 professional male youth football academies, across 42 different countries, reported using match analysis regularly (European Club Association, 2019), up from 75% in a previous survey (European Club Association, 2012). Furthermore, studies in other high-performance sport settings, particularly team sports, also report extensive use of match analysis, underscoring its importance in sport coaching for preparation and performance improvement (Painczyk, Hendricks and Kraak, 2017; Kraak, Magwa and Terblanche, 2018; Martin *et al.*, 2018; Nicholls *et al.*, 2018; Andersen, Francis and Bateman, 2022; Callinan *et al.*, 2023).

The proliferation of match analysis in football is supported by its inclusion in the UEFA coach licensing programme (e.g., English Football Association, 2019), and performance analysis courses by football governing bodies (e.g., Scottish Football Association, 2023). Football policy enforces its adoption through accreditation criteria for professional male youth academies in Scotland (Scottish Football Association, 2017), England (English Premier League, 2011; Raya-Castellano and Uriondo, 2015), and other countries like France (Gregson *et al.*, 2022). Thus, its use in high-performance football merits attention. Computerised match analysis has been regularly utilised since the 1990s (Martinez-Arastey, 2019), with advancements in video technology increasing its use and transforming coaching practices (Butterworth, 2023b; Pearson *et al.*, 2023). Relatedly,

academic interest has persisted for over 25 years (e.g., Hughes and Franks, 1997; Carling, Williams and Reilly, 2005; McGarry, 2013; Memmert, 2022), focusing on new systems, testing validity and reliability, and reporting on data sets and their predictive abilities (e.g., Lorains, Ball and MacMahon, 2013; Liu *et al.*, 2016; Lord *et al.*, 2022; Moreira Praça *et al.*, 2023). These studies have enhanced understanding of sports performance and analytical possibilities. Systematic reviews of context-specific match analysis methods and data are widely available (e.g., Sarmiento *et al.*, 2014a; Sarmiento *et al.*, 2018; Lord *et al.*, 2020). However, positivist research often remains detached from practical applications, overlooking the nuanced realities of sporting environments (Sprake and Palmer, 2022; Campbell *et al.*, 2023).

The literature mainly reinforces the traditional paradigm, with match analysis viewed as a technocratic activity (Williams and Manley, 2016). Historically, coaches were encouraged to prioritise objective numerical data, dismiss subjective observations as unreliable and inaccurate, and allow quantitative data to direct practice (Nelson and Groom, 2012). However, evolving perspectives now recognise the multifaceted nature of match analysis, where both objective data and subjective insights play critical roles (Windt *et al.*, 2021; Davidson *et al.*, 2024). This earlier view portrays coaches as technicians of knowledge (Cushion, Armour and Jones, 2003; Cushion, Stodter and Clarke, 2022), operating in an uncomplicated coaching environment (North, 2017), and providing straightforward feedback (Wright, Carling and Collins, 2014). However, match analysis is more complex, and this simplistic view fails to capture its multifaceted role in enhancing performance.

Coaching practice involves intricate professional judgement and decision-making (Collins, Carson and Collins, 2016; Collins, Collins and Carson, 2016) because coaching is context-specific (Lyle, 2018; Cruickshank, 2019), ambiguous (Raabe, Readdy and Zakrajsek, 2017; Collins *et al.*, 2022; Nichol *et al.*, 2023), and complex and social (Gilbourne, 2012; Cushion and Stodter, 2023). For example, coaches make critical decisions on shaping the practice environment and providing feedback, significantly impacting player learning and development (Larkin, Barkell and O'Connor, 2022; Taylor, Collins and Cruickshank, 2022). As such, simplistic, technocratic views of match analysis fail to account for the importance of subjective expertise (e.g., Colomer *et al.*, 2022). Thus, researchers must acknowledge that match analysis involves subjective interpretation (Wright, Carling and Collins, 2014). Positivist research often fails to represent practical realities (Mackenzie and Cushion, 2013), underscoring the need for nuanced studies. As coaching environments and the cognitive process of the coach require close investigation to be fully understood (Stodter, Abraham and Hodgson, 2024), there have been calls for naturalistic enquiry into the application of match analysis (Mackenzie and Cushion, 2013; Carling *et al.*, 2014).

1.2 Research Problem

Despite widespread use, there is limited research on real-life match analysis contexts (Mackenzie and Cushion, 2013; Carling *et al.*, 2014). However, a small but growing number of studies contribute to understanding its complex application, with surveys of coaches and analysts showing typical patterns of use (Wright, Atkins and Jones, 2012;

Wright *et al.*, 2013; Nicholls *et al.*, 2018; Nicholls *et al.*, 2019; Andersen, Francis and Bateman, 2022). Subjective video feedback is more valued than statistical information, with coach experience guiding the focus of match analysis rather than KPIs from research. These findings challenge the traditional view of match analysis as purely objective and technocratic, highlighting a growing recognition of subjective expert knowledge (Nelson and Groom, 2012; Williams and Manley, 2016). This evolving understanding has also enabled the integration of both qualitative and quantitative analysis, bridging the gap between objective data and contextualised performance insights (McLean *et al.*, 2019; Windt *et al.*, 2021; Colomer *et al.*, 2022; Schweickle, Swann and Vella, 2023; Davidson *et al.*, 2024). Additionally, the use of match analysis varies, including pre-match opposition analysis, post-match analysis, and motivational video, with feedback varying in length, structure, and delivery. This supports the evaluation of match analysis as a complex pedagogical enterprise (Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018; Pearson *et al.*, 2023).

Researchers have investigated the experiences and perspectives of its three main stakeholders: analysts, players, and coaches. Analysts produce video and statistical outputs that are used to support coaching and feedback processes (Hughes and Bartlett, 2020; Francis, Kyte and Bateman, 2024). Players are the focus and end-users of match analysis feedback (Bampouras, Cronin and Miller, 2012). Coaches direct match analysis (Carling *et al.*, 2014), use it to inform their practice (Nicholls *et al.*, 2018), and orchestrate the provision of feedback (Wright *et al.*, 2013). Each stakeholder offers a unique

perspective, which warrants further investigation, as do their interactions, which have been largely neglected. Moreover, there is agreement that match analysis is advantageous (e.g., Wright, Atkins and Jones, 2012; Wright *et al.*, 2013; Wright *et al.*, 2016), with it linked to enhanced player self-reflection, on-field decision-making, match preparation, motivation, and individual and team performance (Reeves and Roberts, 2013; Wright *et al.*, 2016; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018; Fernandez-Echeverria *et al.*, 2019; Gleeson and Kelly, 2021). For coaches, match analysis informs their planning and decision-making (Jenkins, Morgan and O'Donoghue, 2007; Wright *et al.*, 2013) including their tactics and problem-solving (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2011; Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2012; Nelson and Groom, 2012; Brümmer, 2019).

However, its complex application means not all accounts of match analysis are positive. Some players have criticised relentless surveillance, overbearing coaches, poor quality match review, and conflict in analysis interpretations (Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014; Williams and Manley, 2016; Taylor *et al.*, 2017; Manley and Williams, 2022). These also expressed fear and anxiety about public criticism, avoiding contentious discussions with coaches, and disengaging from critical reviews. For example, six out of 11 elite male youth football players noted that match analysis could generate harmful thoughts and negatively affect performance (Middlemas and Harwood, 2018). These findings suggest the need for contextually rich investigation and consideration of stakeholder experiences and decision-making. Match analysis research also needs appropriate theoretical framing.

Studies have provided details of applied processes and stakeholder experiences (e.g., Bampouras, Cronin and Miller, 2012; Reeves and Roberts, 2013; Francis and Jones, 2014). However, they often lack a theoretical framework, limiting their contribution to understanding match analysis. These studies could be enhanced with theoretical and contextual interpretation. Some use specific lenses, like the politics of application (Booroff, Nelson and Potrac, 2016) and surveillance in performance monitoring (Williams and Manley, 2016; Taylor *et al.*, 2017; Manley and Williams, 2022), but these are constrained by their singular focus. Jones and Turner (2006) argue for a holistic approach to address the complex social dynamics of coaching. Therefore, understanding match analysis may be best achieved through multiple interacting theoretical constructs (Lyle, 2018). Accordingly, negative player experiences could relate to controlling coaching cultures (Denison, Mills and Konoval, 2017), disempowering coaching (Duda *et al.*, 2018), and dysfunctional coach-athlete relationships (Jowett and Shanmugam, 2016). Thus, match analysis should be investigated holistically through the nested concepts of culture (Cruickshank and Collins, 2012), motivational climate (Duda *et al.*, 2018), and the coach-athlete relationship (Jowett, 2017).

Due to the context-specific nature of coaching (Lyle, 2018; Cruickshank, 2019), it is essential to recognise the environments and perspectives examined and those overlooked in the literature. Some studies have described analysts' practice (Wright *et al.*, 2013; Martin *et al.*, 2021; Francis, Kyte and Bateman, 2024), but failed to include their voices. Others have explored analyst experiences and perceptions of role, including the

micropolitics and coach-analyst relationships involved (Butterworth and Turner, 2014; Huggan, Nelson and Potrac, 2015; Bateman and Jones, 2019; Martin *et al.*, 2023; Nelson *et al.*, 2023). Although this research acknowledges analysts' role in generating and disseminating match analysis output, it overlooks their perspectives on the pedagogical aspects of these processes. This omission is significant, considering that many analysts not only contribute to feedback but can lead its provision (Wright *et al.*, 2013; Carling, 2019; Nicholls *et al.*, 2019). Notably, the analysts studied in this literature are mostly experienced, with novice analysts largely neglected. While the analysts studied in this literature are often represented as experienced, it is important to acknowledge that some may still be relatively inexperienced, operating at a *competent* rather than *expert* level (Schempp, McCullick and Sannen Mason, 2006; Grant and Dorgo, 2014). This distinction highlights the variability in experience, underscoring the absence of well-established development pathways and frameworks within performance analysis (Martin *et al.*, 2021; Martin *et al.*, 2023), as practitioners often progress through informal or unstructured routes rather than a formalised training system.

As no specific definition exists to describe inexperienced performance analysts, this thesis adopts a definition of *novice* or *neophyte* practice drawn from sport coaching and strength and conditioning literature (Schempp, McCullick and Sannen Mason, 2006; Grant and Dorgo, 2014). Novice analysts are those with limited practical experience, who rely on rules and procedures, with limited ability to adapt to complex or unpredictable situations and often require supervision. Progression to *competence* involves connecting

past experiences with new challenges, developing contingency plans, prioritising key tasks, and working independently. In other professions, significant attention has been given to neophyte practitioners, which has been beneficial. In sport psychology, early accounts of practice offer useful insights for early career practitioners and their supervisors, influencing reflection and development (Collins, Evans-Jones and O'Connor, 2013; Owton, Bond and Tod, 2014). Sharing context-specific challenges faced by neophyte sport coaches may help inform the education and support provided to others (Gomes *et al.*, 2018; Wood *et al.*, 2023). Therefore, exploring the experiences of novice analysts presents another critical avenue of investigation.

Historically, many of the available performance analysis roles have been in men's football compared to women's football. This disparity is due to the traditional imbalance in support and funding between them, despite recent strides towards the professionalisation of the women's game in the UK (Sleeman and Ronkainen, 2020; Fielding-Lloyd and Woodhouse, 2023). In amateur settings, more akin to women's football, clubs often cannot afford analysts, leaving coaches to conduct match analysis themselves (Painczyk, Hendricks and Kraak, 2017; Martin *et al.*, 2018; Sousa *et al.*, 2021). Resultantly, neophyte analysts often start in men's football, typically in youth academies or lower leagues where opportunities are more prevalent. Consequently, the few positions available in women's football are often occupied by practitioners who have first gained experience in men's football. Further investigation is needed to understand this conventional route into match analysis which produces analysts for both men's and women's football.

Compared to the limited voice of analysts, researchers have considered players' experiences with match analysis. This evolving literature has mainly addressed male players within club environments (e.g., Groom and Cushion, 2005; Francis and Jones, 2014; Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014; Williams and Manley, 2016; Wright *et al.*, 2016; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018). The intricacies of international sport settings, where match analysis is extensively used (Nicholls *et al.*, 2019), add to the research landscape. These environments involve varying preparation times, team dynamics, and familiarity with opponents, which brings into question the transferability of findings from club football. The experiences of female players have also received limited attention (Jenkins, Morgan and O'Donoghue, 2007; Taylor *et al.*, 2017; Fernandez-Echeverria *et al.*, 2019), particularly in women's football (Gleeson and Kelly, 2021). This gap is concerning given the stark differences in infrastructure, support, and professional status between men's and women's football (Sleeman and Ronkainen, 2020; Fielding-Lloyd and Woodhouse, 2023). Consequently, the growing call for gender-responsive coaching (Norman, 2016; de Haan and Norman, 2019) highlights the need for coaches and analysts to consider the specific needs of female players. Expanding research into women's football is imperative to ensure match analysis supports the unique challenges and opportunities within these contexts. Addressing this research void is crucial for advancing gender equity in sports science and coaching, as well as enhancing the strategic development of women's football.

Research on coaches' applications of match analysis often misrepresents the process as simple (Wright, Atkins and Jones, 2012; Painczyk, Hendricks and Kraak, 2017; Kraak, Magwa and Terblanche, 2018; Martin *et al.*, 2018; Nicholls *et al.*, 2018). In reality, it is complex and warrants thorough investigation (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2011). Coaches primarily review match analysis output from analysts to inform coaching plans and feedback (Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018; Brümmer, 2019). Given the importance of this feedback in enhancing players' game understanding, decision-making, confidence, and performance (Reeves and Roberts, 2013; Francis and Jones, 2014; Wright *et al.*, 2016; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018), research has largely focused on feedback provision. Feedback meetings are typically coach-led, last approximately 20 minutes, and are delivered to the entire team (Wright *et al.*, 2013; Sousa *et al.*, 2021). Coaches strive to provide balanced feedback to maintain players' confidence and motivation (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2011; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018; Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2020; Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2021). Despite recognising the benefits of interactive feedback sessions, many coaches remain predominantly coach-centred in their application of match analysis (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2012), highlighting the complexity involved.

Some studies suggest that knowledge gaps may explain a coach's controlling delivery of match analysis feedback (Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2020; Kinnerk *et al.*, 2023). These gaps include a lack of pedagogical understanding to effectively shape practice and insufficient self-awareness, resulting in a disconnect between intentions and practice. Consequently,

there is a need to investigate match analysis practices through the lens of coaching philosophy (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2011), especially given its impact on coaches' perceptions and professional behaviours (Gould *et al.*, 2017; Collins, 2021). Existing literature has underscored the importance of coaching background, often describing qualifications and years of experience (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2011; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018). However, it has not sufficiently addressed coaches' beliefs and experiences regarding match analysis, warranting further investigation. Additionally, the application of match analysis is context-specific, with coaches adapting their practice based on factors such as players' age, experience, and psychological status (Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2021; Kinnerk *et al.*, 2023). Most research has focused on male sports, highlighting the need to explore perspectives in female sports, due to contextual differences including the perceived need for gender-responsive coaching (Norman, 2016; de Haan and Norman, 2019). Furthermore, designing and delivering high-quality match analysis feedback requires critical thinking and expertise, which takes time to develop. Consequently, exploring the experiences of a professional women's football coach with extensive match analysis expertise may illuminate developmental influences and changes in the coaching landscape over time that impact match analysis, advancing our understanding of practice.

Building on the need to address these research gaps, this thesis is shaped by my personal journey as a performance analyst. My early experiences in men's football underscored the challenges of implementing match analysis in environments where it had not been

established, particularly the complexities of coach-led feedback and limited integration with training. Transitioning into women's football highlighted the distinct demands and opportunities within these settings. These experiences highlighted the importance of exploring the roles of neophyte analysts and the specific challenges of women's football, ultimately informing the aims of this thesis. This transition from men's to women's football contexts addresses critical gaps in the literature while reflecting the realities of analyst practice. The initial focus on men's football acknowledges its prevalence as a starting point for early-career analysts, who benefit from greater opportunities for entry-level roles in these settings. This mirrors my own professional journey, which naturally evolved from men's to women's football and informed the scope and direction of this research. By incorporating both contexts, this thesis examines the application of match analysis across these distinct environments and highlights the specific demands and challenges of women's football.

1.3 Research Objectives

This thesis aims to enhance understanding of applied practice by exploring under-researched match analysis contexts from a holistic perspective. Each main stakeholder's viewpoint is closely considered. Achieving this required naturalistic enquiry and involved considering each new setting from the nested perspectives of culture, motivational climate, and the coach-athlete relationship. These theoretical frameworks informed the selection of a case study approach as the research design and guided the planning of data collection, including the focus of observations and interview guides. They also

shaped the interpretation of data, ensuring a contextually rich and holistic exploration of match analysis. This approach allows for a deeper understanding of match analysis within its applied setting, bridging the gaps in the current literature. Subsequently, a critical aspect is incorporating the experiences of neophyte practitioners and addressing the unique dynamics within women's football. The three thesis objectives are:

- To explore the experiences of neophyte match analysis interns in professional male youth football.
- To investigate players' experiences with match analysis in an international female youth football squad.
- To interpret a professional coach's career experiences with match analysis in women's football.

1.4 Thesis Organisation

After this introduction, **Chapter 2** reviews the literature on applied match analysis from the perspectives of analysts, players, and coaches. It discusses limitations, unused theoretical concepts, and explains where and how match analysis can be better understood. **Chapter 3** outlines and justifies the general methods, including study design, participant selection, data collection, and analysis. **Chapters 4-6** present original research studies addressing the thesis aims:

- **Chapter 4** explores neophyte match analysis interns' experiences in professional male youth football using a multiple case study approach. Six interns across three

professional football clubs were investigated through interviews conducted after their first season, supported by archival data providing background context.

- **Chapter 5** investigates players' experiences with match analysis in an international female youth football squad through a longitudinal ethnographic case study spanning two years. Field notes informed the development of nine in-depth interviews with players to capture their perspectives.
- **Chapter 6** interprets a professional coach's career experiences with match analysis in women's football through a single case study. A UEFA pro-license coach with over 10 years of experience participated in six semi-structured interviews and shared archival match analysis outputs.

These studies use a nested perspective of culture, motivational climate, and the coach-athlete relationship to make sense of the findings. **Chapter 7** concludes the thesis, discussing implications, recommendations, limitations, and future research areas.

2 Literature Review

In this chapter, the existing match analysis literature will be summarised and critiqued from the perspective of each of its primary stakeholders, namely analysts, players, and coaches. This review will then consider the contextual and theoretical limitations of the current literature base. After this, an argument for a new theoretical framework for applied match analysis research will be made. The chapter concludes by further explaining the purpose of this thesis.

2.1 The Role of the Analyst

Analysts are vital in high-performance team sports (Carling, Lawlor and Wells, 2018), producing the match analysis outputs that enhance coaching and feedback (Bampouras, Cronin and Miller, 2012; Hughes and Bartlett, 2020). By leveraging contemporary hardware and software (Butterworth, 2023c), analysts serve as technicians who provide the technical output necessary for developing tactical understanding, playing a critical role in facilitating knowledge development (Martin *et al.*, 2021; Martin *et al.*, 2023). Specifically, these outputs help players and coaches to develop their declarative knowledge (what to do and why), procedural knowledge (how to do it), and conditional knowledge (when to do it), enabling better decision-making (Nash and Collins, 2006; McRobert and Williams, 2019). For instance, analysts can use video footage to highlight an opponent's pressing structure during goalkeeper distribution, helping players understand what to expect (declarative knowledge). Video feedback sessions can also

demonstrate effective options for distributing the ball safely under pressure, such as how to create passing angles (procedural knowledge), and when to play through the press versus bypassing it with a direct pass to an advanced target player (conditional knowledge).

The match analysis conducted by analysts typically involves reviewing performance in competition (Wright *et al.*, 2013; Nicholls *et al.*, 2019), including pre-match analysis of an upcoming opponent or post-match analysis of team performance (Stanway and Boardman, 2020). Live in-game analysis is becoming more common despite being less frequently used (Carling, 2019; Andersen, Francis and Bateman, 2022). Though limited in depth, these accounts offer valuable insights into analysts' roles. Pre-match analysis predominates in senior football due to the limited time between matches, varied opposition, and restricted player development compared to youth football (Wright *et al.*, 2013; Stanway and Boardman, 2020). Additionally, precarious coach employment and the emphasis on winning contribute to the short-term focus of match-to-match analysis (Huggan, Nelson and Potrac, 2015; Carling, 2019). In youth academy football, pre-match opposition analysis is questionable (Wright *et al.*, 2013; Stanway and Boardman, 2020) due to unavailable match footage and unpredictable opposition strategy and performance. Moreover, the priority to develop players for the first team in academy football requires focusing on post-match analysis (Booroff, Nelson and Potrac, 2016; Ribeiro *et al.*, 2019). Consequently, academy analysis takes a longer-term view, offering players a blueprint of high-level play (Carling, 2019) aligned with the club's game model

(O'Sullivan *et al.*, 2023). These examples demonstrate the nuance involved in applying match analysis.

Traditionally, match analysis is seen as objective and technocratic (Nelson and Groom, 2012; Williams and Manley, 2016), reflecting evidence-based approaches in high-performance sport science (Duncan and Strudwick, 2016). While generating match analysis output is largely objective (Stanway and Boardman, 2020), interpreting and disseminating it is highly subjective, with video being critical (Jones, Rands and Butterworth, 2020; Andersen, Francis and Bateman, 2022; Pearson *et al.*, 2023). For example, analysing attacking play involves subjective judgements on width, penetration, support, and creativity (Carling and Datson, 2022), whereas defensive analysis includes qualitative evaluations of marking, positioning, space reduction, and counter-pressing (Carling, Lawlor and Wells, 2018). Consequently, analysts use video more regularly than statistical data (Wright *et al.*, 2013; Nicholls *et al.*, 2019). Further evidence of subjectivity is that coaches often alter the performance data collected from match-to-match, making ad-hoc requests for additional data (Wright, Atkins and Jones, 2012; Carling, 2019). Given the complexity of providing match analysis feedback and the central role of analysts in this process (Martin *et al.*, 2023), this warrants close attention.

Analysts operate as support staff, with the head coaches holding the power in these hierarchical relationships (Huggan, Nelson and Potrac, 2015). Under significant pressure to succeed (Carling, 2019), high-performance coaches often exert control (Denison, Mills

and Konoval, 2017), which extends to match analysis. This can result in the focus of match analysis being driven by coach preferences and team video-feedback sessions being coach-led (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2012; Wright *et al.*, 2013; Macquet, Ferrand and Stanton, 2015; Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018; Nicholls *et al.*, 2019; Mehta *et al.*, 2023). Coaching expertise affects the delivery of meaningful and persuasive video feedback (Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014), potentially limiting analyst involvement. For example, Wright *et al.* (2013) reported that only 13% of analysts led feedback sessions, and 19% held a 'UEFA B' coaching license. However, the delivery of statistical information to players appears more evenly distributed between analyst and coach (Nicholls *et al.*, 2019), possibly due to analysts better understanding statistics. However, more recent reports indicate that analysts are influencing match analysis and increasingly delivering feedback to players (Carling, 2019; Martin *et al.*, 2023; Mehta *et al.*, 2023). In one study, 90% of analysts supported coaches to develop a style of play or change individual performances (Andersen, Francis and Bateman, 2022). This evolution may be due to sport-specific knowledge and coaching experience now being considered key attributes for contemporary analysts (Martin *et al.*, 2021; Callinan *et al.*, 2023; Francis, Kyte and Bateman, 2024).

Coaches and analysts agree on the importance of positive relationships for the design and delivery of match analysis (Wright, Atkins and Jones, 2012; Wright *et al.*, 2013; Bateman and Jones, 2019; Andersen, Francis and Bateman, 2022; Callinan *et al.*, 2023; Nelson *et al.*, 2023). Whereas, analysts recognise that gaining coach trust is crucial for

greater responsibility, collaboration, and inclusion in decision-making (Nelson *et al.*, 2023), allowing them to negotiate their role (Martin *et al.*, 2021) and add value (Martin *et al.*, 2023). Analysts should build trust by demonstrating knowledge, expertise, interpersonal skills, and attributes like approachability and integrity (Francis *et al.*, 2015; Nelson *et al.*, 2023). For example, Callinan *et al.* (2023) found that having strong relationship-management, communication skills, and creativity, helped analysts positively influence coaches and players, enhancing support and accountability through match analysis. Moreover, Bateman and Jones (2019), found that maintaining coach-analyst dyads required openness and honesty, which parallels earlier work on the coach-athlete relationship (Rhind and Jowett, 2010). Furthermore, unmet coach expectations were said to result in conflict in coach-analyst dyads, similar to coach-athlete dynamics (Davis *et al.*, 2018; Davis, Jowett and Tafvelin, 2019). Therefore, effective match analysis requires purposeful coach-analyst cooperation, facilitated by trust in the analyst.

Cultural expectations and coach education influence the development of contemporary analysts. Analysts now commonly require coaching qualifications, university degrees, alongside expertise in match analysis (Butterworth, 2023a; Francis, Kyte and Bateman, 2024). Therefore, vocational and degree courses focused on match analysis (Butterworth, 2023a) may better prepare analysts for practice. Wright *et al.* (2013) reported that 84% of analysts had or were undertaking a university degree in sport science or coaching, which often includes education on pedagogical principles. Additionally, coaches are transitioning into analyst roles (Andersen, Francis and Bateman, 2022). These findings

suggest that contemporary analysts are not mere technicians, but practitioners with significant coaching knowledge that can positively influence match analysis.

Although analyst-focused research is in its infancy, recent conceptualisations of applied practice have been validated in consultation with experienced practitioners and academics (Martin *et al.*, 2021; Martin *et al.*, 2023). This research confirms that analysts are not mere technicians; they collaborate with coaches to co-create knowledge and design learning opportunities. This research outlines that contextual awareness and building relationships are important alongside professional knowledge and skills, highlighting the complexity of practice. This research has also generalised the match analysis process from the analyst's perspective, including their role in feedback provision, but fails to demonstrate the pedagogy involved. This is despite surveys outlining that analysts have clear preferences on the format, frequency, timing and length of feedback sessions, which do not address the underpinning pedagogy either (Wright *et al.*, 2013; Nicholls *et al.*, 2019). This understanding is important as it may contribute to analysts' ability to shape match analysis through meaningful collaboration with coaches (Callinan *et al.*, 2023). Therefore, given their educational background and influential role, investigating analysts' pedagogical perspectives is critical, especially since this area is currently under-reported and poorly understood.

While models and frameworks represent practice in sport coaching environments, they under-represent the complexity involved (Cushion, Armour and Jones, 2006; Nelson,

Potrac and Groom, 2014; Taylor *et al.*, 2017). This limits their usefulness for guiding practitioner development as they fail to provide the nuanced understanding of contextually rich accounts of practice. Subsequently, as sport coaches value experiential and peer learning, using it to inform their practice (Stodter and Cushion, 2017; Van Woezik *et al.*, 2022). Naturalistic accounts of expert coaching have revealed context-specific knowledge, skills and development pathways (e.g., Cooper and Allen, 2018; Taylor, Ashford and Jefferson, 2023; Mallett *et al.*, 2024). This work is important as it can inform and enhance the quality of practice (Fifer *et al.*, 2008; Cushion and Stodter, 2023). Therefore, in-depth naturalistic accounts of applied match analysis should be encouraged (Mackenzie and Cushion, 2013; Carling *et al.*, 2014).

However, given that coaching environments are context-specific (Lyle, 2018; Cruickshank, 2019) and ambiguous (Raabe, Readdy and Zakrajsek, 2017; Collins *et al.*, 2022; Nichol *et al.*, 2023), expert accounts may not adequately support neophyte practitioners due to the gulf between their practices. For instance, novice sport coaches lack a fully articulated coaching philosophy, leading them to mimic perceived good practice, while experienced coaches possess a well-defined philosophy letting them adapt to emerging situations (Nash and Sproule, 2011). Such differences highlight the value of novice accounts. In sport psychology, early practice accounts can provide valuable insights for novices and their supervisors, influencing practitioner reflections and development (Collins, Evans-Jones and O'Connor, 2013; Owton, Bond and Tod, 2014). Moreover, sharing the context-specific challenges faced by neophyte sport coaches may

inform the education and support provided to others (Gomes *et al.*, 2018; Wood *et al.*, 2023). Given the proliferation of football match analysis (Wright *et al.*, 2016), examining novices should be a priority to support the growing number of new practitioners in football.

In the match analysis literature, scarce attention has been given to neophyte practitioners. Huggan, Nelson and Potrac (2015) explored micropolitical challenges faced by a novice analyst in professional football. The analyst understood the head coach's legitimate power (Rylander, 2016), and their own vulnerability as an analyst (McKenna *et al.*, 2018; Gibson and Butterworth, 2023). Impressing key decision-makers, building trust, and negotiating their role with head coaches (5 in 18 months) was necessary. As in other studies, this required appreciating the coaches' varying experience with and attitudes toward match analysis (Bateman and Jones, 2019; Andersen, Francis and Bateman, 2022). Given their vulnerability, the analyst allied with assistant coaches and support staff to mutually affirm their competence. Meanwhile, fostering relationships with the club chairperson and players helped impact the club's performance culture. Subsequently, this study highlights the importance of social elements in analysts' roles and provides insights into the strategic thinking and micropolitical literacy required (Gibson and Butterworth, 2023). Consequently, further investigation into novice analysts' experiences from relational and pedagogical perspectives is needed.

Funding and support significantly influence the application of match analysis (Butterworth, 2023c). Elite professional football clubs often have multiple full-time analysts across

senior teams, academies, and recruitment departments (Stanway and Boardman, 2020; Francis, Kyte and Bateman, 2024). Smaller clubs employ only one or two analysts for the entire organisation, often using student interns to compensate (Martin *et al.*, 2023). Amateur settings generally lack analysts, forcing coaches to adopt dual roles to integrate match analysis (Painczyk, Hendricks and Kraak, 2017; Martin *et al.*, 2018). However, the rise of automated tracking camera systems (Butterworth, 2023c) and cost-effective analysis solutions (Butterworth, 2023b) have increased accessibility for amateur clubs. Despite progress in professionalising women's football in the UK, a significant resourcing gap to men's football persists (Sleeman and Ronkainen, 2020; Fielding-Lloyd and Woodhouse, 2023), creating a digital divide (Barker-Ruchti *et al.*, 2021). This results in a considerable gap in match analysis support for women's football. Consequently, most novice analysts start in men's football, particularly in youth academies or lower leagues, where there are more opportunities. The limited opportunities in women's football are often filled by analysts who have started in men's football. Subsequently, this early career path warrants further investigation as it produces analysts for both men's and women's football due to the similarities and transferability across analysis roles (Martin *et al.*, 2021; Butterworth, 2023e; Francis, Kyte and Bateman, 2024).

2.2 Player Experiences

Match analysis feedback is provided to players to enhance their individual and collective performances (Butterworth, 2023e), making them key stakeholders in the process (Bampouras, Cronin and Miller, 2012; Gleeson and Kelly, 2021). However, despite the

importance of player perceptions in understanding and informing the application of match analysis (Groom and Cushion, 2005; Butterworth, 2023e), they are often overlooked. This oversight likely stems from a belief that players should be detached from the process, with them only receiving coach-selected feedback (Bampouras, Cronin and Miller, 2012; Butterworth and Woodward, 2023). This reflects the coach-centred culture prevalent in high-performance sports (Cushion, Ford and Williams, 2012; Denison, Mills and Konoval, 2017). As a result, existing research has primarily focused on players' reactions to match analysis feedback, examining their responses to coach-delivered insights and its perceived impact on their performance, rather than exploring their potential active involvement in the match analysis process (Francis and Jones, 2014; Wright *et al.*, 2016; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018). By limiting players' engagement, this traditional approach may hinder the development of their analytical skills and diminish opportunities for collaborative learning, which could enhance both their game understanding and decision-making capabilities.

Effective match analysis feedback supports the development of players' game understanding by fostering declarative (what to and why to), procedural (how to), and conditional (when to) knowledge (McRobert and Williams, 2019). This understanding enables the creation of *action plan profiles* (i.e., rule-governed strategies for specific scenarios) and *current event profiles* (i.e., contextual tactical adaptations during matches), which can enhance player decision-making (Evans, Whipp and Lay, 2012; Cotterill and Discombe, 2016). For example, a central defender might develop an action

plan profile for deciding whether to track a striker making a diagonal run or hold their position to maintain the defensive line. Through *reflection on-action* (i.e., happens after the activity and is deliberate, analytical, and evaluative), the defender could review instances where tracking the striker left space for an opposing midfielder to exploit or where holding the line allowed the striker to receive the ball in time and space to create a dangerous opportunity (Stephenson, Cronin and Whitehead, 2020). This process sharpens *reflection in-action* (i.e., happens during the activity and is immediate, intuitive, and responsive), enabling the defender to dynamically assess in real time whether the striker's movement poses an immediate threat or is intended to create space for another attacker, thereby making the optimal decision based on the evolving match context (Stephenson, Cronin and Whitehead, 2020). These cognitive adaptations, particularly the interplay of action plan profiles and current event profiles, are enhanced through interactive video-feedback sessions, supporting the capacity of players to dynamically assess and respond during matches (McRobert and Williams, 2019).

Video-feedback sessions, typically conducted in team meetings lasting around 20 minutes (Wright *et al.*, 2013; Carling, 2019; Sousa *et al.*, 2021), aim to support these cognitive adaptations. These sessions focus on key segments from pre-match or post-match analysis (Brümmer, 2018; Jones, Rands and Butterworth, 2020). Coaches typically control meeting organisation, determine the topics of conversation, and dominate discussions, which are often results-focused (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2012; Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018; Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2020). In contrast, some

coaches adopt alternative approaches by promoting interaction, encouraging questioning, and being process-focused, which can positively influence player's experiences (Wright *et al.*, 2016; Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2021). Occasionally, coaches ask players to lead match analysis feedback to share control and offer an alternative voice (Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018; Butterworth, 2023b). This interaction has been suggested to enhance player engagement and learning (Nelson *et al.*, 2014; Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018; Gleeson and Kelly, 2021). Sub-unit and individual feedback sessions also facilitate better player engagement (Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018), which may explain why individual video-feedback improves self-efficacy, psychological affect, tactical knowledge, and performance (Moreno *et al.*, 2016; Middlemas and Harwood, 2020). However, these are used infrequently due to time pressures (Wright *et al.*, 2013; Carling, 2019). Meanwhile, cloud-based platforms allow players independent access to match analysis data (Butterworth, 2023b), facilitating player-led analysis and reflection on personalised video clips (Vinson *et al.*, 2017; Carling, 2019). However, match analysis can contribute to negative self-evaluation and psychological affect (Middlemas, 2017). Therefore, coaches need to support constructive engagement with video, starting with balanced performance reviews.

Several authors recognise the value of players' perceptions of match analysis. Interview-based studies have revealed that players perceive match analysis to have positively impacted their development and performances (Reeves and Roberts, 2013; Francis and Jones, 2014; Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014). Match analysis is also linked to

improvements in players' game understanding and in-game decision-making through meaningful self-evaluation (Reeves and Roberts, 2013; Wright *et al.*, 2016; Gleeson and Kelly, 2021). For example, professional youth football players noted improvements in their understanding and decision-making, which included marking in defence and passing in attack (Groom and Cushion, 2005). Elite youth footballers also benefited from in-game recollections of video feedback, supporting their decision-making (Middlemas and Harwood, 2018). Coaches play a crucial role in this process by facilitating discussions in feedback meetings that aid self-reflection (Francis and Jones, 2014; Wright *et al.*, 2016; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018; Gleeson and Kelly, 2021). Interactive video feedback improves the complexity, sophistication, structure, and long-term recall of players' tactical knowledge, significantly enhancing cognitive expertise (García-González *et al.*, 2013; Gil-Arias *et al.*, 2015; Moreno *et al.*, 2016). This enhancement may explain why players value match analysis and seek greater involvement (Bampouras, Cronin and Miller, 2012; Wright *et al.*, 2016).

Researchers have linked the delivery of match analysis feedback to player confidence, motivation, and readiness to perform. For instance, Middlemas and Harwood (2018) suggest keeping the mood light and positive to elicit higher enjoyment and confidence in youth football players, especially for mistake-conscious individuals. While balanced pre-match reviews help avoid fearing or underestimating opponents (Carling, 2019). Additionally, elite players value negative post-match feedback for structuring tactical learning and positive feedback for motivation (Fernandez-Echeverria *et al.*, 2019).

Therefore, creating a supportive environment and avoiding psychologically damaging feedback, such as public criticism, is essential (Reeves and Roberts, 2013; Gleeson and Kelly, 2021). Moreover, coach delivery impacts the clarity of team meetings, influencing players' understanding and confidence in the feedback received (Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018). Subsequently, coach guidance can support players' tactical learning (Wright *et al.*, 2016) if feedback sessions are well-constructed, including the questions asked (Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014; Gleeson and Kelly, 2021). Furthermore, Wright *et al.* (2016) highlight players' preference for a 24-48 hour delay before post-match review meetings to allow for reflection and emotional subsidence (McArdle *et al.*, 2010). Positive outcomes may be dependent on the established coaching culture and motivational climate, although this link is under-researched (Collins, Carson and Cruickshank, 2015; Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018). Consequently, more research is needed to establish whether an empowering coaching culture offers the same benefits to match analysis as it appears to in elite sport coaching more broadly (Pineda-Espejel *et al.*, 2021).

A supportive coaching environment intertwines with the coach-athlete relationship, making it integral to match analysis (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2012; Francis and Jones, 2014; Booroff, Nelson and Potrac, 2016). Trust and respect are pivotal for player engagement and acceptance of feedback (Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014; Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018). Furthermore, coaching culture, shaped by communication, empathy, and ethical conduct (Kim, Kim and Won, 2018), significantly impacts the trust players place in their coach (Alder, 2018). This trust is essential in high-performance sport

(Bandura and Kavussanu, 2018; Kao, Hsieh and Lee, 2017). Consequently, a coach fostering a culture of trust is more likely to earn player acceptance of match analysis and integrate it effectively into the coaching process. For instance, a veteran ice-hockey player shared his experiences of interacting with various coaches during match analysis feedback sessions (Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014). The player's trust and respect towards the head coach were contingent on perceptions of the coach's competence, effort, and commitment. Furthermore, the player's acceptance of match analysis feedback depended on the coach's preparedness, the quality of their analytical insights, communication, and their utilisation of an inclusive approach. Conversely, coaches can deliver poor tactical analysis (Carling, 2019), leading to players challenging or rejecting feedback, especially from inexperienced coaches (Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014; Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018). Therefore, the role of coach-athlete relationships requires greater consideration in the application of match analysis.

In contrast to the positive player experiences, negative accounts appear to relate to disempowering coaching cultures, behaviours, and poor coach-analyst relationships. One study reported a professional head rugby coach's use of analysis did not match their players' expectations. This involved delivering copious negative feedback, both publicly and punitively, and surveilling players' use of a cloud-based data platform (Williams and Manley, 2016; Manley and Williams, 2022). Such practices align with ego-orientation, restricting of player autonomy, and disempowering coaching (Hassan and Morgan, 2015; Duda *et al.*, 2018). Similarly, Taylor *et al.* (2017) explored the experiences of an

international field hockey goalkeeper who faced significant discomfort, anxiety, and embarrassment due to their coach's use of video. This included recording goalkeeper training when the head coach was working with outfield players, one-to-one review meetings to address unsatisfactory performance, and evaluating individual errors in group meetings. The player experienced heightened self-awareness and responsibility, which mediated her behaviour, but was unable to raise these concerns due to the prevailing culture of surveillance and control. Similar feelings were reported among elite football players who felt anxious and embarrassed about seeing their mistakes in team feedback sessions (Middlemas and Harwood, 2018; Gleeson and Kelly, 2021). Some of these players experienced negative thoughts during and after video-feedback sessions, affecting their focus in these sessions and their subsequent performance. These disempowering experiences restrict the players' voice throughout the process (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2012).

Several of these negative experiences and the subsequent player responses (Williams and Manley, 2016; Manley and Williams, 2022) relate to the emotional abuse experienced and coping mechanisms adopted by players in high-performance sports (Kavanagh, Brown and Jones, 2017). Players viewed these approaches negatively, but did not voice their concerns because they understood the legitimate power held by the coach (Rylander, 2016). Even when asked to speak their minds in feedback sessions, players typically remained silent for fear of disagreeing with the coach's statistics and the potential repercussions, such as being deselected from the team. Despite the match analysis data

likely being high-quality, the disempowering application limited the positive outcomes. Subsequently, a disempowering coaching culture that focuses on surveillance and control, can inhibit player development by acting as a barrier to player engagement with match analysis (Williams and Manley, 2016; McCosker *et al.*, 2022). Therefore, coaches and analysts can take significant lessons from players' positive and negative experiences with match analysis.

Another important consideration is the context-specific nature of coaching (Lyle, 2018; Cruickshank, 2019), and how this relates to the existing match analysis literature. Current accounts predominantly reflect the experiences of male team-sport players within high-performance club environments (e.g., Francis and Jones, 2014; Wright *et al.*, 2016). Although insights from international youth football coaches have been documented, there remains a notable gap in understanding the viewpoints of international players, with only one study to date (Taylor *et al.*, 2017). Consequently, it is imperative to focus on international environments, where match analysis is routinely employed (Nicholls *et al.*, 2019). This focus is particularly relevant due to significant differences between club and international settings. These include the duration coaches, players, and analysts spend together (Lindgren and Barker-Ruchti, 2017), and the level of familiarity with upcoming opponents. These variations can significantly influence the application of match analysis.

Female players deserve equal attention in the match analysis literature, yet few studies have explored their perspectives. Jenkins, Morgan and O'Donoghue (2007) discovered

that female netball players responded positively to pre-match motivational videos created from their match analysis. They reported enhanced performance comprehension, individual and team confidence, and motivation, similar to male players (Middlemas and Harwood, 2018). Taylor *et al.* (2017) revealed that a female international hockey player's negative experiences under a controlling coach mirrored those of male rugby players facing similar conditions (Williams and Manley, 2016; Manley and Williams, 2022). This reinforces that the creation of such cultures and environments is not gender-specific; as power abuse reflects a broader issue of control and authority. Moreover, these studies suggest common principles in the application of match analysis. However, Loo, Francis and Bateman (2020) noted that female players focused more on developmental (negative) feedback, aligning with observations in elite female volleyball (Fernandez-Echeverria *et al.*, 2019), while male players may prioritise positive feedback (Groom and Cushion, 2005). This is possibly due to gender differences in goal orientation with women reported as being more task-oriented (Kavussanu and Roberts, 2001; Murcia, Gimeno and Coll, 2008; Hanrahan and Cerin, 2009; Koh and Wang, 2015) and intrinsically motivated (Kingston, Horrocks and Hanton, 2006; Wendling *et al.*, 2018). Similar gender differences have been reported in other educational and recreational sport settings (Anderson and Dixon, 2009; Bakirtzoglou and Ioannou, 2011; Alić, 2017), though cultural and contextual factors also appear to influence these patterns (Hadjiyankova and Iancheva, 2021; Stolk, Gross and Zastavker, 2021; Schüler, Wolff and Duda, 2023), suggesting that educators can play a pivotal role in influencing this in practice.

These findings suggest that male and female players may interact differently with match analysis, supporting calls for gender-responsive coaching (Norman, 2016; de Haan and Norman, 2019). Gender-responsive coaching focuses on the relational and motivational aspects of coaching. For high-performance female players, this may mean prioritising enjoyment, discussing decisions, fostering personal relationships, and adopting a democratic coaching style (Norman and French, 2013; Norman, 2015). Female athletes often want to explore the rationale behind coaching decisions and be involved in the decision-making process, which makes them feel supported when these needs are met (Longshore and Sachs, 2015; de Haan and Norman, 2019). Providing female players with adequate information fosters trust in the coach-athlete relationship (de Haan and Norman, 2019). According to female athletes, open communication and trust are critical in shaping coach-athlete relationships (McDonald, Tsukada and Chung, 2016). Conversely, communication issues can damage their coach-athlete relationships (Kristiansen *et al.*, 2012). Given that social support is an important source of confidence, being gender-responsive can also involve awareness of low self-evaluation, self-confidence, and susceptibility to confidence decrements among high-performance female athletes (Hays *et al.*, 2009; Rintaugu, Mwangi and Toriola, 2018; O'Connor *et al.*, 2020; Trbojević and Petrović, 2021).

However, significant differences exist in facilities, sport science, coaching support, and professional status between male and female football (Sleeman and Ronkainen, 2020; Fielding-Lloyd and Woodhouse, 2023). Therefore, any perceived differences may be due

to the varied socio-cultural experiences of male and female players (Roberts and Quesnel, 2023). Consequently, Gosai, Jowett and Rhind (2022) warn against gender stereotyping of female athletes and advocate for coaching tailored to players' unique characteristics. Thus, future research into players' experiences with match analysis should be discussed in relation to the culture under investigation, including contextual factors like gender.

2.3 The Perspective of the Coach

Coaches are gatekeepers to match analysis (Bampouras, Cronin and Miller, 2012; Butterworth, 2023e), deciding what analysis is undertaken and how it influences their plans (Jenkins, Morgan and O'Donoghue, 2007; Wright *et al.*, 2013). Therefore, coaches' use of match analysis has been investigated. While these studies are insightful, they often misrepresent match analysis as straightforward (Wright, Atkins and Jones, 2012; Painczyk, Hendricks and Kraak, 2017; Kraak, Magwa and Terblanche, 2018; Martin *et al.*, 2018; Nicholls *et al.*, 2018). In reality, coaches use their experience and relationships to shape match analysis (Andersen, Francis and Bateman, 2022; Callinan *et al.*, 2023), given the complexity they face in applying it (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2011). Consequently, coaches must make critical decisions about utilising match analysis to positively impact player development (Larkin, Barkell and O'Connor, 2022; Taylor, Collins and Cruickshank, 2022). Coaches should draw upon declarative, procedural and conditional knowledge to scaffold players' tactical learning (Ashford, Abraham and Poolton, 2021b; Moran, Taylor and Macnamara, 2024). By breaking down complex

tactical concepts into manageable components, coaches help players recognise patterns, anticipate scenarios, and make effective decisions under match conditions. This process not only shapes players' game understanding and decision-making but also underscores the critical role of match analysis in player development (Reeves and Roberts, 2013; Francis and Jones, 2014; Wright *et al.*, 2016; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018). Thus, research into how coaches experience and utilise match analysis is essential.

In high-performance football, match analysis is fundamental for enhancing team performance and strategy (Brümmer, 2019; Andersen, Francis and Bateman, 2022). Coaches and players agree that effective match analysis can enhance confidence, learning, and motivation (Macquet, Ferrand and Stanton, 2015; Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018). It also improves coaches' performance review, and the quality of feedback provided to players, better preparing them for matches (Andersen, Francis and Bateman, 2022; Callinan *et al.*, 2023). Thus, match analysis is a tool that augments reflective coaching practice (Brümmer, 2019), helping coaches to identify areas for development, refine training, make strategic decisions, and monitor progress (Carling, 2019; Butterworth and Woodward, 2023). Video is central to this process, providing an aerial view of performance that should differ from touchline and in-game perspectives (Brümmer, 2018; Sousa *et al.*, 2021). It reveals information not apparent during matches, such as passing options and team organisation, highlighting its educational value. Therefore, video enables coaches to critically reflect on performance

and the efficacy of their tactics (Macquet, Ferrand and Stanton, 2015), and enhance their understanding of team coordination (Brümmer, 2019).

To achieve these positive benefits, analysts first generate match analysis output. Post-match review focuses on the previous match, whereas pre-match analysis involves observing multiple games to identify key patterns in the opposition's play (Sarmiento *et al.*, 2013; Sousa *et al.*, 2021). Analysts select games contextually similar to the upcoming match (Sousa *et al.*, 2021), including those where the opponent played teams of similar quality or style. Coaches then review this output, focusing on key moments of play including offensive and defensive strategy, transitions, and set plays (Hewitt, Greenham and Norton, 2016; Sousa *et al.*, 2021). Video is preferred over statistics to evaluate strengths and weaknesses (Andersen, Francis and Bateman, 2022), perhaps due to the misconception that team sports such as football are too fluid for statistical analysis (Kioussis, 2018). This iterative process allows coaches to observe how situations evolve, recognise tactical patterns, and identify additional details to inform their coaching plans (Butterworth, Turner and Johnstone, 2012; Almeida *et al.*, 2019; Brümmer, 2019). After this, coaches discuss their assessments with key staff and construct feedback presentations (Brümmer, 2019). Video is carefully selected and edited to enhance player understanding, deliver clear and concise messages, and retain player attention in feedback meetings (Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2020; Sousa *et al.*, 2021). This process relies on coaches' pedagogical knowledge (e.g., coaching science principles, instructional methods, and team morale) (Moran, Taylor and Macnamara, 2024). By combining tactical

insight with pedagogical expertise, coaches can transform match analysis into a meaningful learning experience that fosters players' engagement, deepens understanding, and enhances performance.

The insights gained from video analysis form the foundation for feedback meetings, which are typically classroom-based and last around 20 minutes (Wright *et al.*, 2013; Sousa *et al.*, 2021). Head coaches usually lead these sessions (Carling, 2019; Andersen, Francis and Bateman, 2022), offering a balance of positive and negative feedback, while considering player confidence and motivation (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2011; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018; Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2020; Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2021). Coaches understand that player engagement is important, which aligns with high-performance players favouring autonomy-supportive coaching (Rothwell *et al.*, 2017; Goffena and Horn, 2020). Subsequently, some use *divergent questioning* (i.e., broad, open-ended questions that encourage the exploration of various perspectives, and allow for multiple responses, which fosters deeper thinking (O'Connor *et al.*, 2022)), silence, and player-led discussions to encourage interaction and deeper thinking (Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018; Brümmer, 2019; Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2021; Kinnerk *et al.*, 2023).

Conversely, other coaches use minimal questioning, or answer their own questions, limiting player engagement (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2012; Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2020; Kinnerk *et al.*, 2023). Coaches also target players for public criticism to develop

mental toughness (Macquet, Ferrand and Stanton, 2015; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018; Brümmer, 2019). While players' views of and responses to such feedback may depend on their individual psychological qualities (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2011), it can also be criticised as disempowering (Smith *et al.*, 2017). This is due to the established link between task orientation and mental toughness (Jackman, Swann and Crust, 2016), meaning coaches risk having negative effects if this strategy is overused or applied indiscriminately. Therefore, given the coach's ability to engage players significantly impacts learning (Light and Harvey, 2017; Bowles and O'Dwyer, 2019; McCleery *et al.*, 2022), careful planning of match analysis is important to maximise player learning.

Coaches then design training sessions to implement the strategies discussed in match analysis feedback sessions (Sarmiento *et al.*, 2014a; Sarmiento, Bradley and Travassos, 2015; Macquet, Ferrand and Stanton, 2015; Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018; Sousa *et al.*, 2021). Ongoing engagement with match analysis, particularly when paired with scenario-based training, is considered crucial for enhancing players' anticipation skills (McRobert and Williams, 2019; Ashford, Abraham and Poolton, 2021c). It enables them to predict opponents' intentions and respond effectively under pressure. Scenario-based training, informed by match analysis outputs, places players in realistic situations where they can refine game plans and rehearse tactical decisions (Ramos *et al.*, 2021; Ashford *et al.*, 2022). This feedback-training cycle is perceived to reinforce tactical knowledge and sharpens players' reflection in-action and on-action (Ashford, Abraham and Poolton, 2021a), fostering adaptability and confidence in high-pressure match scenarios (Ashford

et al., 2022). To support this process, coaches remind players of key messages during training to aid recall (Brümmer, 2019), and hold informal tactical discussions to contribute to a learning culture (Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018). This practice and discussion embed tactical concepts into players' anticipatory knowledge, enhancing team coordination (Brümmer, 2018). Thus, the coach's ability to plan and deliver quality training is linked to the efficacy of match analysis. Subsequently, the match analysis-to-training link needs to be better understood.

Given the complexity of this process, several constraints impact the effectiveness of match analysis. Time constraints often lead to inconsistent and ad-hoc application, especially in individual feedback meetings (Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018; Sousa *et al.*, 2021), which is problematic given the importance of routine in learning (McCleery *et al.*, 2022). Consequently, these inconsistencies may limit the efficacy of sub-unit and individual analysis, which are crucial for addressing player-specific needs and enhancing role-specific understanding (Vinson *et al.*, 2017; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018). Furthermore, coaches can now provide regular individual feedback and make video footage available on cloud-based platforms (Butterworth, 2023c). While this offers convenience, players may feel pressured to engage in additional analysis depending on the performance culture and power dynamics involved (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2011; Brümmer, 2018). Additionally, other technology presents opportunities and challenges. Tools like laser pointers and telestration help draw attention to key points during feedback review (Brümmer, 2019). However, coaches must be proficient with

technology to ensure effective communication and engagement, or they risk players losing attention and confidence in their messages (Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018).

Other contextual factors such as situational and psychological dynamics also shape match analysis (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2011; Macquet, Ferrand and Stanton, 2015; Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018). Coaches consider player experience and knowledge, as these can influence their interpretation of game situations (Macquet, Ferrand and Stanton, 2015) and their confidence in group discussions. Psychological status may also influence feedback, with coaches prioritising positive feedback to build or restore confidence (Brümmer, 2018; Kinnerk *et al.*, 2023). Furthermore, player age may impact concentration and cognitive ability, requiring more coach instruction to scaffold understanding before engaging in discussions (Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2021; Kinnerk *et al.*, 2023). These examples highlight why coaching applications of match analysis should meet players' needs, as failing to do so risks negative effects (Williams and Manley, 2016; Taylor *et al.*, 2017; Manley and Williams, 2022). Coaches also use match analysis micropolitically in line with performance targets to develop players for the first team, offering extra support to the most talented players (Booroff, Nelson and Potrac, 2016).

Given the complexity of applying match analysis as a coach, context-specific examinations that reveal their knowledge informed decision-making would be beneficial (Côté and Gilbert, 2009; Martindale and Collins, 2010; Stodter, Abraham and Hodgson, 2024). This is because coaching philosophy significantly influences practice, including

match analysis (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2011; Gould *et al.*, 2017; Collins, 2021). Relatedly, some researchers have begun to uncover decisions behind the application of match analysis. For example, coaches who value player engagement and trust try to adopt athlete-centred approaches when providing match analysis feedback (Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018; Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2020; Kinnerk *et al.*, 2023). However, knowledge gaps, such as a lack of understanding of pedagogical principles and low self-awareness, can lead to controlling approaches. These coaches may see learning as passive (Harvey *et al.*, 2013; Partington and Cushion, 2013), due to the influence of traditional coaching cultures (Denison, Mills and Konoval, 2017). This explains why coach-centred applications of match analysis predominate (e.g., Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2012). However, coach education interventions can enhance coaches' understanding of feedback practices (Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2021). Therefore, further research is needed to understand how coaches' beliefs and experiences, along with the coaching context, shape the application of match analysis.

Most research into coaching applications of match analysis has focused on male team sports. This emphasis neglects the cultural differences between men's and women's football (Sleeman and Ronkainen, 2020; Fielding-Lloyd and Woodhouse, 2023) and calls for gender-responsive coaching (Norman, 2016; de Haan and Norman, 2019). However, some research does exist on the perceptions of high-performance coaches working with female athletes. High-performance coaches perceive female athletes to have relatively low and unstable self-confidence compared to male athletes (de Haan and Knoppers,

2020; Danielsen *et al.*, 2023). Coaches often encourage female athletes to try their best and focus on developmental goals, perceiving them as less competitive (Felton and Jowett, 2013; Lindgren and Barker-Ruchti, 2017; de Haan and Sotiriadou, 2019). Additionally, coaches appreciate that female athletes tend to ask more questions to understand their coach's decisions. Meanwhile, some international women's football coaches have transitioned from autocratic to democratic coaching styles to focus on player development, well-being, and conversation (Lindgren and Barker-Ruchti, 2017). This is similar to other limited accounts of need-supportive high-performance coaching (Annerstedt and Lindgren, 2014; Barker-Ruchti, Barker and Annerstedt, 2014). Therefore, understanding how coaches construct match analysis in women's football requires further investigation. Pedagogical expertise, which takes time to develop (Nash and Collins, 2006; Cushion and Stodter, 2023), is required to optimise coaching practice (Cope *et al.*, 2016). Therefore, exploring a coach with significant experience in applying match analysis in women's football would be beneficial (Nash and Collins, 2006; Cushion and Stodter, 2023).

2.4 Theoretical Framework

Match analysis is a nuanced pedagogical enterprise (Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018), and should be studied through a lens that embraces its complexity (Mackenzie and Cushion, 2013). The research addresses match analysis processes and stakeholder experiences (e.g., Bampouras, Cronin and Miller, 2012; Reeves and Roberts, 2013; Francis and Jones, 2014), but mainly offers superficial

interpretations, limiting its contribution to understanding practice. Other studies have applied specific theoretical lenses such as micropolitics (Booroff, Nelson and Potrac, 2016), surveillance (Williams and Manley, 2016; Taylor *et al.*, 2017) and coach-athlete relationships (Bateman and Jones, 2019). These enrich our understanding of practice but are limited by their singular focus. As holistic research in coaching is suggested (Jones and Turner, 2006), both it and match analysis could be better understood through multiple interacting theoretical constructs (Lyle, 2018). Collins and Cruickshank (2015) identified that cultural, motivational, and interpersonal perspectives are central to a coach's nested thinking, making it viable for exploring match analysis. Negative player experiences could be linked to controlled coaching cultures (Denison, Mills and Konoval, 2017), disempowering coaching (Duda *et al.*, 2018), and dysfunctional coach-athlete relationships (Jowett and Shanmugam, 2016). Thus, match analysis would benefit from being investigated through the nested perspective of culture (Cruickshank, 2019), motivational climate (Duda *et al.*, 2018), and the coach-athlete relationship (Jowett, 2017).

To summarise these interconnections and provide a visual roadmap for the detailed discussion that follows, a proposed framework for understanding athlete-centred match analysis is presented (see, *Figure 2.1*). This framework synthesises elements of team culture, motivational climate, and coach-athlete relationships, drawing on established theoretical constructs (e.g., micropolitics, empowering coaching, and coach-athlete relationship). While these constructs have been explored individually in prior research,

this framework combines them to offer a holistic perspective that aims to address the complexities of match analysis. The proposed framework serves as a conceptual guide for the analysis and discussion that follow.

Figure 2.1: An Integrated Theoretical Framework for Athlete-Centred Match Analysis

2.4.1 Coaching Culture

The culture within high-performance sports shapes team dynamics and performances (Fletcher and Arnold, 2011). Team culture, characterised by shared opinions, attitudes, principles, and customs (Cruickshank and Collins, 2012), is foundational in achieving collective goals. High-performing cultures develop explicit purposes, identity, procedural systems, and hierarchical structures to sustain efforts aligned with team objectives (Cruickshank, 2019). Performance pressure in elite sport (Carling, 2019) instigates significant politics in sport coaching (Mallett, Rynne and Billett, 2016), and match analysis

contexts (Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014; Huggan, Nelson and Potrac, 2015; Booroff, Nelson and Potrac, 2016). Conflict in these high-performance environments intensifies when players and staff vie to uphold or enhance their positions, along with the egos and personal objectives involved (e.g., Thompson, Potrac and Jones, 2015). Hence, navigating and fostering collaboration in these environments is a challenge requiring an understanding of the interplay between team culture, micropolitics and power (Gibson and Groom, 2020).

In elite sport, practitioners must be prepared for both overt and covert micropolitical action (Huggan, Nelson and Potrac, 2015; McCalla and Fitzpatrick, 2016), like disruptions against team goals (Potrac, Jones and Armour, 2002; Purdy, Potrac and Jones, 2008), which complicate the navigation of often-hidden power dynamics (Collins and Cruickshank, 2015; Purdy, 2016). For example, players might strategically display docility to help manage the coach-athlete relationship in a controlling coaching culture (Manley and Williams, 2022; Andrijiw and Jones, 2023). Subsequently, practitioners must decipher the socio-political actions of key stakeholders (Rowley *et al.*, 2020; Allanson, Potrac and Nelson, 2021), recognising their power and agency are fluid, shaped by relationships and situational contexts. These stakeholders possess the ability to shape or constrain practice (Cruickshank, Collins and Minten, 2013; Cruickshank and Collins, 2015b; Collins, Trower and Cruickshank, 2017), which requires practitioners to critically evaluate the interplay of power and influence to develop adaptable, context-sensitive strategies that align with team objectives.

Navigating these challenges requires strategic use of power to promote cooperation. French and Raven's typology (Lyngstad, 2017), relevant in team sports (Rylander, 2016), helps understanding the fluid and context-dependent nature of sources of power. These sources of power are not static; their effectiveness may shift depending on evolving contexts, requiring practitioners to critically evaluate and adapt their strategies. Coaches can leverage person-centred power, including interpersonal liking (referent power), perceptions of competence (expert power), and persuasive arguments (informational power) (Rylander, 2016). These actions, akin to impression management (Thompson, Potrac and Jones, 2015; Jenkins, 2017), can foster acceptance of necessary action (Hall *et al.*, 2021) and are more appropriate for long-term success in coaching (Rylander, 2016; Cruickshank, 2019). In match analysis, analysts, players, and coaches benefit from this approach. Nelson, Potrac and Groom (2014) showed that a player's acceptance of match analysis was influenced by the perceived competence (expert power) of the coach, which might evolve as trust develops or erodes over time. Booroff, Nelson and Potrac (2016) illustrated coaches use match analysis output to rationalise player evaluations (informational power). Huggan, Nelson and Potrac (2015) emphasised cultivating positive relationships (referent power) and showcasing competence (expert power) as an analyst. Recognising the continuum of power dynamics within these interactions highlights the need for practitioners to remain sensitive to changing contexts and relationships, applying match analysis in ways that build trust, credibility, and collaboration.

However, coaches must adapt to challenges (Cruickshank and Collins, 2016), which might necessitate the controlling approaches of coercion, reward, and legitimate power (e.g., Cushion and Jones, 2006). Machiavellian actions and coach control may benefit the group by optimising team functions (Potrac and Jones, 2009b; Santos, Jones and Mesquita, 2013; Cruickshank and Collins, 2015a). For instance, legitimate power from coach authority is linked to player compliance (Rylander, 2015). However, elite team leaders must apply social dominance sensitively and sparingly to limit the negative consequences that occur over time (Cruickshank and Collins, 2015a; Mills and Boardley, 2017). Thus, micropolitics and power can contribute to understanding match analysis within high-performance team sport culture.

In high-performance sport, culture is influenced by practices like using technology, such as match analysis, to track players' performance (Barker-Ruchti *et al.*, 2016; Williams and Manley, 2016). While technology itself is not inherently problematic (Collins, Carson and Cruickshank, 2015; Cronin *et al.*, 2019), using it to seek an unproblematic truth reinforces controlling cultures (Kohe and Purdy, 2019). Therefore, practitioners must carefully consider the ability of technology to both restrict and enable practice, as well as the dynamic interplay between technology and humanistic coaching values, to mitigate potential disengagement. Brümmer (2019) identified that video feedback is viewed as objective truth superior to players' experiences. Coaches holding this view risk devaluing and disregarding players, thereby restricting their behaviour (Manley and Williams, 2022). This perspective aligns with passive, technocratic views of learning as mere data

transmission (Harvey *et al.*, 2013; Partington and Cushion, 2013), reinforcing hierarchical power dynamics (Barker-Ruchti *et al.*, 2021). Although cloud-based technologies offer athletes autonomy through open access to data, they can also pressure players to engage in additional review (Brümmer, 2018). Thus, in a controlling culture, match analysis can disenfranchise players, lead to superficial engagement, and harm coach-athlete relationships (Williams and Manley, 2016; Taylor *et al.*, 2017; Manley and Williams, 2022). This exemplifies the link between culture, motivational climate, and coach-athlete relationships (Barker-Ruchti *et al.*, 2016), and the need for a humanistic coaching approach (Lindgren and Barker-Ruchti, 2017; Barker-Ruchti *et al.*, 2021), extending to match analysis. High-performance sports culture, micropolitics, and power dynamics can change over time with changing contexts. Recognising these shifts helps practitioners develop adaptable strategies suited to the realities of applying match analysis.

2.4.2 Motivational Climate

Motivation shapes behaviour, influencing the initiation, persistence and modification of player actions, and determines the direction and intensity of their efforts (Keegan *et al.*, 2011; Appleton and Duda, 2016). Thus, effective coaching requires a positive motivational climate. However, existing match analysis research has only made superficial links to player motivation (Reeves and Roberts, 2013; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018; Fernandez-Echeverria *et al.*, 2019), thus a deeper investigation considering motivational theory is required. Motivational climate has been conceptualised

through empowering and disempowering coaching (Duda *et al.*, 2018), viewed as points on a continuum rather than fixed behavioural states. In elite sport, empowering coaching, often linked to task-involved climates, has been associated with player success (Gillet *et al.*, 2010; Gillet, Vallerand and Paty, 2013). Elements of both approaches often coexist in practice. Empowering coaches foster a task-involved climate and provide autonomy and social support (Duda, 2013). Task-involved climates are associated with greater player enjoyment, need satisfaction, player engagement, and group functioning in recreational and performance sport (Alvarez *et al.*, 2012; García-Calvo *et al.*, 2014; Curran *et al.*, 2015; Jaakkola, Ntoumanis and Liukkonen, 2016). These climates are dynamic, shifting with player needs, team dynamics, and external pressures. To foster such climates, coaches may rely on frameworks like TARGET, which considers task, authority, recognition, grouping, evaluation, and time (Kingston, Wixey and Morgan, 2020). Autonomy and social support are established through meaningful choice, legitimate voice, and interpersonal connections (Mageau and Vallerand, 2003; Duda and Appleton, 2016). Empowering coaching has been shown to offer many positive effects including intrinsic motivation, player well-being, subjective vitality, self-esteem, and sport performance in various participatory and performance football settings (Reinboth and Duda, 2006; Álvarez *et al.*, 2009; Adie, Duda and Ntoumanis, 2012; Balaguer *et al.*, 2012; González *et al.*, 2016).

Elite players in task-involved climates with autonomy-support tend to develop competence, intrinsic motivation, and self-confidence (Pineda-Espejel *et al.*, 2021),

contributing to enhanced performance. However, the effectiveness of these climates may shift depending on situational pressures, player individuality, and team dynamics. In a World Cup winning team, an empowering climate was central to the coach's strategy (Hodge, Henry and Smith, 2014). The coach collaborated with the players' leadership group, encouraged player initiative, and focused on mastery to enhance performance. Elite players prefer task-focused climates and autonomy-supportive coaching (Pensgaard and Roberts, 2002; Høigaard, Jones and Peters, 2008; Rothwell *et al.*, 2017; Goffena and Horn, 2020), so while not all decisions are democratic, coaches should operate transparently, as players value rational coach decision-making and coach candour (Keegan *et al.*, 2014). Providing players with a rationale for decisions is considered autonomy-supportive (Mageau and Vallerand, 2003). Subsequently, empowering coaching should support the application of match analysis. For example, players express their need for autonomy by requesting more involvement in match feedback (Bampouras, Cronin and Miller, 2012; Wright *et al.*, 2016).

Disempowering coaches use controlling behaviours like intimidation, conditional regard, rewards, and excessive personal control (Bartholomew *et al.*, 2011). These actions hinder need satisfaction, promote extrinsic motivation, and can lead to burnout, negative psychological affect, and reduced well-being, self-worth, and performance in both recreational and performance sport (Bartholomew, Ntoumanis and Thøgersen-Ntoumani, 2009; Bartholomew *et al.*, 2011; Balaguer *et al.*, 2012; González *et al.*, 2016). Ego-involved climates, part of disempowering coaching, can result in negative effect, extrinsic

regulation, and maladaptive strategies including avoidance and withdrawal (Kim, Duda and Gano-Overway, 2011; Harwood *et al.*, 2015; Hassan and Morgan, 2015). Higher stress, anxiety, and lower well-being in elite players are likely with need dissatisfaction and perfectionistic concerns (Lundqvist and Raglin, 2015; Haraldsen *et al.*, 2019; Haraldsen *et al.*, 2020). Coach-centred behaviours linked to disempowerment (Kidman and Lombardo, 2010; Nelson *et al.*, 2014) are prevalent across various football environments (Ford, Yates and Williams, 2010; Partington and Cushion, 2013), which is concerning. Meanwhile, negative experiences such as excessive surveillance and public criticism (Williams and Manley, 2016; Taylor *et al.*, 2017; Manley and Williams, 2022) may be explainable through disempowering coaching. Therefore, the motivational effects of match analysis can be better understood through empowering and disempowering coaching. While empowering approaches offer clear benefits, applying them requires flexibility. Coaches must balance task focus with environmental and relational demands, often blending elements of empowerment and control, to meet the specific demands of their teams.

2.4.3 Coach-Athlete Relationship

Navigating high-performance sport is challenging, making an effective coach-athlete relationship essential (McDonald, Tsukada and Chung, 2016; Tshube and Hanrahan, 2018; López de Subijana *et al.*, 2021). Although often described in binary terms (e.g., positive vs. negative relationships), these constructs may be better understood as existing on a continuum. Robust coach-athlete relationships are linked to greater motivation (Adie

and Jowett, 2010; Isoard-Gauthier *et al.*, 2016), player well-being (Felton and Jowett, 2013; Solstad *et al.*, 2022), engagement (McGee and DeFreese, 2019), team efficacy (Hampson and Jowett, 2014; Cho and Baek, 2020), and player development and performance (Rhind and Jowett, 2010; Jowett and Shanmugam, 2016; Davis *et al.*, 2018). Recognising the impact of these relationships on match analysis underscores its relevance (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2011; Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2012; Francis and Jones, 2014; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018).

The quality of coach-athlete relationships are determined by closeness, commitment, complementarity, and co-orientation (Yang and Jowett, 2017). Positive relationships are foundational to effective coaching (Jowett, 2017). Closeness, based on mutual respect, trust, and interpersonal liking (Jowett, 2017), mediates coach-athlete dyads (Kao, Hsieh and Lee, 2017; Bandura and Kavussanu, 2018), while trust facilitates open communication (Raabe, Readdy and Zakrajsek, 2017). Early in relationships, coaches often control the environment, with trust, understanding, and power-sharing developed over time (Antonini-Philippe *et al.*, 2011). Additionally, autonomy-support is an antecedent to positive relationships (Cho and Baek, 2020; Wekesser *et al.*, 2021), and requires time, effort, and responsive behaviours to develop (Jowett and Poczwardowski, 2007; Antonini-Philippe *et al.*, 2011). This highlights the dynamic and gradual nature of these constructs, which can shift and adapt as relationships mature. As successful match analysis requires trust in both coach-athlete (Nelson *et al.*, 2014) and coach-analyst relationships (Bateman and Jones, 2019), understanding the factors shaping these partnerships is important.

A coach's competence and expertise significantly impacts trust (Kao, Hsieh and Lee, 2017). Furthermore, effective communication, including clear information, constructive feedback, and active listening, fosters positive rapport (Jowett and Shanmugam, 2016). Integrity and ethical conduct are also paramount, as coaches earn trust through honest, transparent, and principled actions (Crossan, Copeland and Barnhart, 2023). While genuine care mediates satisfaction in the relationship (Li, Gao and Hu, 2021), coach adaptability and power-sharing also foster trust (Jowett *et al.*, 2023). Thus, trust is not static but develops incrementally through repeated positive interactions, clear communication, and consistent ethical behaviour. Distance in co-orientation constrains coach-athlete relationships (Lorimer and Jowett, 2013; Jowett, 2017; Smoll and Smith, 2020), and there can be significant distance between their perceptions of the coaching environment (Rocchi and Pelletier, 2018; Gjesdal *et al.*, 2019). Open two-way communication and feedback are critical to developing co-oriented thinking (Meeûs, Serpa and De Cuyper, 2010; Choi, Jeong and Kim, 2020; Li, Gao and Hu, 2021). This co-orientation process is dynamic, requiring ongoing alignment to bridge differing perspectives and achieve shared understanding. This is especially important for team sport coaches, who are considered less empathic than individual sport coaches (Lorimer and Jowett, 2009a), as empathetic accuracy is critical for player satisfaction (Lorimer and Jowett, 2009b). Co-oriented thinking is also important in match analysis, as aligned thinking between analysts, coaches, and players is required (Brümmer, 2019; Butterworth, 2023e). While closeness in the coach-athlete relationship may influence how

the players receive match analysis feedback (Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014; Taylor *et al.*, 2017).

Negative coach-athlete relationships often manifest as interpersonal conflict (Davis *et al.*, 2018). Players failing to meet expectations in high-performance sport may experience emotional abuse, such as humiliation, punishment, and being denied attention and support (Stirling and Kerr, 2008; Stirling and Kerr, 2014). This abuse is more common when players are unsuccessful (Gervis, Rhind and Luzar, 2016), and coaches prioritise winning (ego-orientation) over well-being (Wilinsky and McCabe, 2021). Studies on youth (Battaglia, Kerr and Stirling, 2017) and elite senior players (Stirling and Kerr, 2013; Kerr, Willson and Stirling, 2020), link punitive coach behaviours to impaired training performance, negative affect (e.g., embarrassment, fear, and anxiety), and psychological outcomes (e.g., reduced confidence, motivation, and well-being). These behaviours also contribute to poor coach-athlete relationships (Olympiou, Jowett and Duda, 2008). Despite awareness of ethical practice, such occurrences are prevalent in high-performance coaching (Wilinsky and McCabe, 2021), and often pass unchallenged, indicating tacit acceptance (Stirling and Kerr, 2014). Similar problems in match analysis contexts (Williams and Manley, 2016) highlight the need to examine coach-athlete relationships from this perspective.

Psychological safety exists where players feel heard, valued, and connected, and is linked to high-quality coach-athlete relationships (Jowett *et al.*, 2023). This creates an

environment with enhanced trust and cooperation, where individuals can voice concerns and admit mistakes without fear of negative consequences (Burns, Collins and Nolte, 2024). Safe environments enhance player engagement, learning, well-being, and performance (Reardon *et al.*, 2019; Smittick, Miner and Cunningham, 2019; Fransen, McEwan and Sarkar, 2020; Henriksen *et al.*, 2020; Gosai, Jowett and Nascimento-Júnior, 2023). In contrast, poor leadership and dishonest communication can erode group functioning, leading to stress and suboptimal performance (Rice *et al.*, 2022; Salcinovic *et al.*, 2022). As with trust, psychological safety is dynamic and fluctuates based on leadership behaviours, team dynamics, and individual perceptions. Coaches play a pivotal role in creating this climate in a sports team by encouraging open, cooperative dialogue and reframing failures as learning opportunities (Jowett *et al.*, 2023). Therefore, psychological safety can also be linked to coaching culture, and motivational climate, and will likely impact the application of match analysis, thus it warrants consideration.

2.5 Conclusion

This review provides insight into the pedagogical complexity of applying match analysis, considering the perspectives of the analyst, player and coach. The technical facets of analysts' work are well understood, but social and pedagogical dimensions have received limited attention. Given the many novice practitioners, especially in football, exploring the experiences of neophyte analysis interns in professional youth football is necessary (Chapter 4, McKenna *et al.*, 2018). Players' experiences are shaped by how match analysis feedback is delivered. Thus, considering calls for gender-responsive coaching

(Norman, 2016; de Haan and Norman, 2019) the challenges of international football (Lindgren and Barker-Ruchti, 2017), and that players' accounts focus on male players in club football, there is a need to explore players' experiences with match analysis in international female youth football to understand the related context-specific demands (Chapter 5). Coaches play a pivotal role in directing the match analysis process (Carling *et al.*, 2014). Match analysis is a complex pedagogical enterprise (Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014) requiring expertise and context-specific application. While some coach narratives exist (e.g., Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2011; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018), women's football has been overlooked despite calls for gender-responsive coaching (Norman, 2016; de Haan and Norman, 2019). Additionally, these accounts also fail to capture the impact of the coaching philosophy and experience of practice. Therefore, there is a need to investigate a professional football coach's experiences with match analysis in women's football (Chapter 6). Given its complexity, match analysis can be understood through a nested perspective of culture, motivational climate, and the coach-athlete relationship.

3 Methodology

In this chapter, the overarching study design is explained, followed by the case and participant selection methods used throughout this thesis. Next, the quality assurance framework adopted in the initial design of this research is outlined. The data collection methods employed in the original research chapters are then introduced, including interviews, participant observation, and archival data. Subsequently, an explanation is provided regarding the data analysis applied throughout this research. Additional quality assurance steps undertaken are integrated within this chapter whenever pertinent to the methods under discussion. More detailed study methods are presented in Chapters 4-6 when discussing the original research from this thesis.

3.1 Study Design and Case Selection

In the context of applying match analysis within the complexities of the coaching process, the research across this thesis was guided by the philosophical positions of *constructivism* and *interpretivism* (Gray, 2021). Both philosophies underscore the importance of subjective experiences, meanings, and the social contexts in which phenomena occur. Constructivism suggests that individuals actively construct their own understanding of reality, while interpretivism emphasises the role of interpretation in understanding an individual's experiences. To align with these perspectives, a qualitative *theoretical drive* was adopted (Morse, 2015b). This involved examining and grasping the depth and nuances of individual experiences from the perspective of different

stakeholders within the match analysis process. These perspectives informed the adoption of a qualitative framework and case study approaches, to explore diverse perspectives, meanings, and contextual factors associated with the application of match analysis in high-performance football settings, offering holistic and intricate insights into this dynamic process.

A case study design (Yin, 2018) was selected because it facilitates in-depth, context-specific inquiry, enabling a detailed exploration of real-world phenomena. Three distinct case study approaches (multiple, ethnographic, and single) were adopted to align with the thesis aims, with each case bounded by clear temporal, spatial, and participant boundaries. The case study approach was particularly appropriate given the research aims, which required a nuanced, in-depth understanding of how match analysis operates in practice across distinct settings and participants. Meanwhile, its multi-method nature, a hallmark of case research, involved integrating interviews, observations, and archival data, to ensure a comprehensive understanding of each case (Armour and Griffiths, 2012; Hamilton and Corbett-Whittier, 2013).

In the first phase of this research, a *multiple-case study* design (Crowe *et al.*, 2011) was used to compare the experiences of neophyte analysts in professional male youth football (Chapter 4). Temporal boundaries were defined by a single football season, while spatial boundaries focused on elite-level youth academies within professional football clubs. Participant boundaries included neophyte interns who met specific inclusion criteria, such

as limited experience with match analysis and a sport coaching degree. Given the limited number of analysts in typical football settings, this design enabled identification of shared patterns and context-specific variations (Yin, 2018). By investigating analysts working with similar age groups at similarly sized clubs with 'elite' academies, the research captured commonalities in their challenges, learning trajectories, and interactions with coaches and players. At the same time, it revealed contextual factors, such as resources, processes, and organisational support, that shaped analysts' opportunities to apply match analysis effectively. This comparative design mitigated the limitations of a single-site study by capturing a broader, yet still detailed, account of emerging match analysis practices.

Building on this, an *ethnographic case study* (Cushion, 2014) examined players' experiences with match analysis within an international female youth football squad (Chapter 5). Temporal boundaries were established over a two-year period, ensuring prolonged engagement. Spatial boundaries centred on the international squad environment, while participant boundaries included players who met specific criteria, such as international experience and position diversity. The ethnographic approach, with its longitudinal and immersive qualities, fostered trust and participant openness over time (Sparkes and Smith, 2014). Prolonged immersion enabled a deeper understanding of players' relationships with match analysis. This extended engagement captured contextual nuances, ensuring a richer and more authentic representation of participants' experiences (Hammersley and Atkinson, 2019).

In contrast, a *single case study* design (Willig, 2022) explored a professional coach's career experiences with match analysis in women's football (Chapter 6). Temporal boundaries encompassed the coach's career, while spatial boundaries focused on women's football environments, including club and international settings. Participant boundaries identified a single professional UEFA pro-licensed coach with over a decade of experience, serving as an information-rich case. The single case study was chosen for its intrinsic value (Willig, 2022), providing focused, in-depth insights into the coach's philosophy, subjective experiences, and pedagogical rationale. It illuminated long-term engagement with match analysis, particularly the interplay between the coach's evolving pedagogy and practical challenges in high-performance women's football. By examining the coach's professional journey, spanning varied roles and contexts, the study revealed how these experiences shaped their understanding and application of match analysis. This holistic exploration provided unique insights into match analysis practices not achievable through broader, multi-case designs.

The researcher's industry experience (>10 years) was essential in identifying high-quality cases and facilitating access to participants (Cushion, 2014). Cases were purposefully chosen as established sites of match analysis, ensuring they offered information-rich insights into current practices (Douglas, 2022; Palinkas *et al.*, 2015). In following the approach of Kjær (2019), the researcher engaged with each case for an extended period, cultivating cultural familiarity with the specific match analysis contexts (Creswell and Poth,

2016). Inclusion criteria were systematically applied to identify and recruit participants integral to the match analysis process (Hastie and Hay, 2012). This approach promoted *multivocality* (Tracy, 2010), ensuring the distinctive perspectives of analysts, players, and coach were considered in line with the thesis aims. Additionally, as used in other qualitative research (Wadey *et al.*, 2012; Jorgensen and Mainwaring, 2021), *maximum variation sampling* (Douglas, 2022) was applied at the study level in Chapter 5 by accounting for different playing positions. This careful selection of cases and participants supported a comprehensive examination of match analysis across the specified contexts.

3.2 Quality Assurance

Quality assurance is crucial in qualitative research to uphold its *trustworthiness* (Sparkes and Smith, 2014). Therefore, drawing from established practices in sport coaching and sport science case studies (e.g., Caron, Bloom and Bennie, 2015; Mueller, Ruiz and Chroni, 2018; Kjær, 2019; Behan *et al.*, 2020; Mesquita *et al.*, 2023), the widely used trustworthiness criteria proposed by Lincoln and Guba were adopted (Korstjens and Moser, 2018). However, as Smith and McGannon (2018) suggest, quality assurance criteria can be applied partially and creatively. Therefore, the concepts of *credibility*, *dependability*, *confirmability*, and *transferability* were flexibly applied to align with the qualitative paradigm, ensuring trustworthy accounts of match analysis in high-performance football settings.

This chapter and the methods sections in the subsequent original research chapters provide an *audit trail* of the critical methodological decisions made in constructing this thesis (Burke, 2016). These explanations demonstrate the dependability and confirmability of this research (Loh, 2013; Yilmaz, 2013). Each documented decision in this trail enhances the transparency of the research process, enabling scrutiny and replication. Additionally, the incorporation of *thick description*, a fundamental aspect of rigour in qualitative research (Burke, 2016), plays a pivotal role in enhancing the credibility of this thesis. Through detailed depictions of contextual information, participant interactions, and nuanced situational elements, thick description provides readers with a comprehensive overview of the research process and phenomena studied. Further application of quality assurance procedures and their connection to trustworthiness are discussed in the remaining sections of this chapter when relevant.

3.3 Data Collection Methods

Across this thesis, *interviewing* was the primary data-gathering technique, supplemented by *participant observation* and the review of *archival data*. This multi-method approach aligns with the principles of case study research (Yin, 2018), ensuring *data triangulation* (Burke, 2016) to enhance depth, credibility, and context-specific insights within each bounded case. This combination of techniques, mitigated their individual limitations (Hastie and Hay, 2012), and provided alternative perspectives for each case (Hamilton and Corbett-Whittier, 2013). Before data collection in each study, ethical approval was

granted by the School of Health and Life Sciences at the University of The West of Scotland.

3.3.1 Interviews

Interviewing was the primary data collection method to reveal participants' opinions, ideas, feelings, and attitudes (Sparkes and Smith, 2014), aligning with the aims of this thesis and the adopted research paradigm. One-to-one semi-structured interviews were conducted across all three case studies, providing rich, detailed insights into the experiences of analysts, players, and the coach. This method was central to understanding the nuances of match analysis practices within each bounded case (Yin, 2018), complementing observations and archival data. One-to-one *semi-structured interviews* in all three studies elicited personal insight (Purdy, 2014) and balanced participant freedom with researcher direction (Sparkes and Smith, 2014). These professional conversations (Brinkmann and Kvale, 2018) focused on the *what, how, and why* of participant experiences (Purdy, 2014; Martin *et al.*, 2023).

To ensure quality data collection, the reflexive *interviewing the investigator* method promoted interview guide development (Chenail, 2011). *Piloting* was then conducted to refine each guide and prepare for data collection (Sampson, 2004). Interviews were informal and rapport was established through positive regard (Ennis and Chen, 2012). Initial background questions eased participants into the interview before sensitively addressing complex topics (Braun and Clarke, 2013). Interview guides kept the dialogue

focused (Mears, 2012), and audio recording facilitated attentive listening (Patton, 2015; Lavee and Itzchakov, 2021). Interview guides were developed to explore participants' experiences through the theoretical lenses of culture, motivational climate, and coach-analyst relationships, ensuring alignment with the study's conceptual framework. Participants received an advance copy of the interview guide (an abridged version) to reflect on their experiences beforehand, enhancing data richness. Open-ended questions elicited fuller answers (Sparkes and Smith, 2014), and iterative questioning ensured understanding (Smith and Sparkes, 2016). Probing questions and silence coaxed further detail and clarification (Sparkes and Smith, 2014).

The researcher's prior working relationships and shared communities of practice (Nash and English, 2015) with all participants helped reduce power asymmetries (Brinkmann and Kvale, 2018), and contributed to establishing and maintaining trust and rapport during interviews (Roiha and Ikkänen, 2022). Given this shared history and understanding (Garton and Copland, 2010), the researcher was mindful to avoid the problems associated with the conversational style of *acquaintance interviews* (Braun and Clarke, 2013). Thus, the researcher limited personal disclosure and empathic comments (Garton and Copland, 2010) and explained to participants that their voices should predominate (Chenail, 2011; Berger, 2013). Participants were also asked directly about implicitly shared understandings (Morse, 2015a) to ensure they were recorded (Drake, 2010).

Each interview lasted approximately 60 minutes (Purdy, 2014), with 6-10 interviews conducted per study. This volume was comparable to related studies (Caron, Bloom and Bennie, 2015; Mueller, Ruiz and Chroni, 2018), aligned with sample size advice (Braun *et al.*, 2019), and allowed for *data saturation* (Fusch and Ness, 2015; Saunders *et al.*, 2018). Given the ambiguity surrounding data saturation it was essential to select a specific conceptualisation (Braun and Clarke, 2021b). The approach promoted by Morse (2015a) was used, which goes beyond data redundancy to appreciate that added information is generated during data analysis (Braun *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, data collection ended when a theoretically robust data analysis was developed from data sufficient in scope and replication (Morse, 2015a), which parallels the concept of *meaning saturation* (Hennink, Kaiser and Marconi, 2016).

Reaching data sufficiency with limited participant numbers required each study to have high *information power* (Malterud, Siersma and Guassora, 2016). This was facilitated by selecting samples that were suitably homogenous and information-rich (Braun *et al.*, 2019). In Chapter 4, homogeneity was achieved as all participants were match analysis interns working with similar age groups in 'elite' academies at similarly sized clubs. Their shared educational backgrounds, training, and practical experiences further ensured a consistent understanding of match analysis processes. In Chapter 5, homogeneity was maintained through participants' shared membership of an international youth football squad and their considerable experience with match analysis processes specific to this setting. For Chapter 6, homogeneity was not a relevant consideration as the single case

study focused on an individual coach's extensive and diverse career experiences, providing unique insights into match analysis practice. Beyond ensuring homogeneity and information-rich samples, the quality of the dialogue between the researcher and participants, and the theoretical perspectives considered, enhanced each study's information power (Malterud, Siersma and Guassora, 2016). Data collection and analysis proceeded simultaneously (Peel, 2020), and in support of data saturation, time was left between interviews for data analysis and reflexivity, influencing subsequent interview questions. Furthermore, collecting background case information before interviewing expedited the process and contributed to data saturation (Cushion, 2014).

3.3.2 Participant Observation and Archival Data

This research employed observations and archival data to provide complementary insights across the case studies, aligning with their distinct methodological designs and objectives. In Chapter 5, the researcher used his role as an analyst within an international female youth football squad to produce first-hand impressions of this environment and inform participant interviews (Öhman and Quennerstedt, 2012; Sparkes and Smith, 2014). Aligned with the ethnographic case study approach (Cushion, 2014), prolonged and immersive observations were critical to capturing players' evolving relationships with match analysis. Participant observations focused on developing a nuanced understanding of the match analysis process within this context (Sparkes and Smith, 2014). Observations included training sessions; formal team, sub-unit and individual player meetings; staff meetings; informal conversations; and solo analysis work. Regular

and prolonged participant observation developed a deep understanding of social norms and contextual subtleties (Cushion, 2014). Gaining this perspective was critical given the experiential distance between the researcher and participants in Chapter 5 (female players) compared to Chapter 4 (analysts) and Chapter 6 (a high-performance coach).

Initially, observations were unstructured, with substantive and methodological note-taking (Willig, 2022), recording taken-for-granted culture (Sparkes and Smith, 2014). Later, observations became increasingly selective and note-taking more analytical (Angrosino, 2012; Willig, 2022) as the hidden curriculum was established (Cushion and Jones, 2014). Participant observations were guided by the study's theoretical framework, which sensitised the researcher to key aspects of culture, motivational climate, and coach-athlete interactions. This focus ensured that observations were attuned to relevant contextual and interpersonal dynamics within the case. To combat forgetting, *field notes* were taken during reflective downtime as soon as possible after each observation (Hastie and Hay, 2012). Field notes were only captured after analysis-related events that offered new insight, making sampling purposeful (Öhman and Quennerstedt, 2012). Observations were conducted overtly and included informal discussions and the review of squad documentation (Sparkes and Smith, 2014). However, the extended nature of data collection and the private recording of field notes limited the influence on participant behaviour (Angrosino and Rosenberg, 2011; Öhman and Quennerstedt, 2012).

Given the researcher had worked *in situ* for three years before data collection commenced, their insider status required careful consideration (Bonner and Tolhurst, 2002; Drake, 2010). This aspect was partly mitigated by the researcher's relative detachment from the participants' role as players compared to their own role as an analyst (Willig, 2022). Moreover, the researcher engaged in reflexive thinking (Attia and Edge, 2017) to promote open-mindedness, and actively sought disaffirming observations (Willig, 2022). This approach helped to prevent researcher bias from unduly influencing data collection (Cushion, 2014). The researcher initially reflected upon their beliefs, values, and biases before data collection (Donoso-Morales, Bloom and Caron, 2017). This *reflexivity* allowed the researcher to make sense of their thoughts (Emerson, Fretz and Shaw, 2011), address their *positionality* (Day, 2012), and anticipate their impact on the research process (Hill, 2020). Subsequently, enhanced self-awareness led to improvements in research design and rigour (Darawsheh, 2014; Jamie and Rathbone, 2022), and guided the ethical decision-making across this research (Reid *et al.*, 2018). As a person's position and assumptions are fluid (Berger, 2013), they can affect the entire research process, so reflexive action was extended from research design and data collection to data analysis and the research write-up (Cushion, 2014).

In contrast to Chapter 5's immersive observations, archival data played distinct roles in Chapter 4 and Chapter 6, enhancing contextual understanding and supporting subsequent interviews. Across both chapters, archival data provided fragments of culture (Silverman, 2020), which helped reveal social reality and supported subsequent

interviewing and data analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2013; Yin, 2018). This included video highlights and match statistics from team, sub-unit, and individual analysis, spanning pre-match opposition and post-match analysis, and other related output. Chapter 4 applied this data to develop a broader understanding across multiple clubs, while Chapter 6 relied on targeted data to explore the coach's professional journey and decision-making processes within bounded contexts. In Chapter 4, additional archival material, including coursework completed during university studies (e.g., reflections on practice), revealed the analysts' evolving applications of match analysis. This material enriched interviews by prompting critical reflections on learning trajectories, aligning with the comparative focus of the multiple-case study design (Crowe *et al.*, 2011).

In Chapter 6, archival data similarly supported contextual understanding by providing insights into distinct phases of the coach's professional journey. Examples of match analysis outputs, such as match reports and video highlights, served as memory prompts during interviews. This approach facilitated detailed recollections of the coach's decision-making processes within specific career contexts, aligning with the focused, retrospective nature of the single case study design (Willig, 2022). Across both chapters, archival data offered tangible artefacts that enriched contextual understanding, supported interview narratives, and strengthened the analysis. Its role as a foundation for interviews allowed the researcher to pose more detailed questions about the analysts' and coach's experiences and cultivate a more critical understanding of their evolving appreciation of match analysis. Moreover, the researcher's professional judgement informed the *targeted*

sampling (Silverman, 2020) of archival data that best represented each professional practice account. Data authenticity (McCulloch, 2017) was ensured, as direct copies of match analysis output were examined.

3.4 Data Analysis

Given the philosophical position guiding this research, the selected data analysis method needed to respect the researcher's subjective role in interpreting the data and constructing the narrative (Braun, Clarke and Hayfield, 2022). Therefore, *reflexive thematic analysis* (RTA) was adopted (Byrne, 2022), to identify contextually bound and positioned patterns of meaning (Braun *et al.*, 2019). RTA has been used to provide a nuanced reading of qualitative data in sport science and coaching research (e.g. Bell *et al.*, 2021) and can reveal the messy and sometimes paradoxical nature of real-life contexts (Braun, Clarke and Weate, 2016). Like other methods of thematic analysis, RTA involves rigorous and systematic work but within an interpretive and creative six-phase process (Braun and Clarke, 2021a) that is fluid and recursive (Braun and Clarke, 2019). During analysis, the theoretical perspectives of culture, motivational climate, and coach-analyst relationships sensitised the researcher to patterns of meaning in the data, guiding the interpretation of themes while preserving the inductive nature of reflexive thematic analysis.

Initially, the researcher became immersed in the data through multiple cycles of active listening (Byrne, 2022) and note-taking, with close attention paid to critical features and perceived connections in the data (Braun *et al.*, 2019). Note-taking moved from descriptive to analytical and included reflexive thoughts. While some researchers recommend *transcription* to deepen data analysis (Braun *et al.*, 2019), others promote audio-based data familiarisation and coding (Halcomb and Davidson, 2006; Stonehouse, 2019; Vindrola-Padros and Johnson, 2020; Ligita *et al.*, 2022). After developing a substantial understanding of the data, each interview was systematically *open-coded* (Braun and Clarke, 2013) to maintain a data-driven approach, given the inductive nature of this research (Byrne, 2022). *Audio-coding* of each interview took place using notational analysis software (Longomatch, Version 1.3.1, Spain, 2016, or Nacsport, Scout, Version 8.4.2, Netherlands, 2022), with meaningful segments saved and named for further analysis. The researcher generated *semantic codes* first followed by *latent codes* to consider both explicit and implicit meanings (Braun *et al.*, 2019). Semantic coding involved descriptive analysis, whereas latent coding required the researcher to assume a more imaginative and active role, exploring deeper underlying meanings that explained the descriptive data (Byrne, 2022). As part of the quality assurance process (Nowell *et al.*, 2017), *recoding* of the interviews took place to rework and enhance the initial coding (Castleberry and Nolen, 2018; Braun *et al.*, 2022).

Next, the researcher actively reviewed the coded data for patterns of shared meaning (Braun *et al.*, 2019), which went beyond highlighting superficial *domain summaries* (Braun

and Clarke, 2019). When codes were judged to share a *central organising concept* (Braun, Clarke and Weate, 2016), they were organised into unifying *themes*, with some substantial codes promoted directly to themes (Byrne, 2022). The critical questions raised by Braun and Clarke (2013) were used to inform initial theme creation alongside Patton's dual criteria of *internal homogeneity* within themes and *external heterogeneity* among themes (Byrne, 2022). A provisional *thematic map* (Braun *et al.*, 2019) was then created individually for each study, serving as a valuable visual aid in representing the connections between themes and subthemes. Supported by consultation, this thematic map was critiqued, reimagined, and finalised.

Member checking was used to establish authentic representation of participants' situated experiences and perspectives (Smith and McGannon, 2018), enhancing the credibility of this research (Nowell *et al.*, 2017). Participants were asked to provide feedback on an informal oral report of study findings after the initial thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2013). Findings were communicated in practical terms with appropriate lay language to aid understanding and encourage participant engagement (Martindale and Nash, 2013; Kubayi, Coopoo and Toriola, 2021). Given the interpretive nature of this research, the focus was on confirming that participants' perceptions were authentically represented, rather than performing a validation check of interview transcripts typical of other member checking approaches (Cavallerio, Wadey and Wagstaff, 2020). Overall, participants confirmed their perceptions were fairly represented, and minor clarifications were noted where necessary. This feedback further refined the analysis and reinforced the

trustworthiness of the findings. At this stage, selective transcription (Stonehouse, 2019) of coded audio segments took place in preparation for the study write-up.

With the researcher now content with the essence of each theme, they were given their final names. Establishing how each theme contributed in a distinct but complementary manner helped form compelling narratives (Byrne, 2022). Throughout the wider analysis, and especially in the write-up, the PhD supervisory team acted as a theoretical sounding board. They were not affiliated with the cases under investigation, providing appropriate analytical distance to critically challenge the researcher's interpretations (Brewer and Sparkes, 2011; Geranosova and Ronkainen, 2015). Moreover, multivocality (Tracy, 2010) was offered by these *critical friends* (Sparkes and Smith, 2014) who were sports science, coaching and performance analysis practitioners. They provided individual and thought-provoking feedback on the interpretations of the study (Cowan and Taylor, 2016). This process, parallel to member checking, served to test and challenge the researcher's interpretations, offering alternative perspective and identifying possible bias projections (Berger, 2013; Sparkes and Smith, 2014). This feedback enhanced the thematic structure, improved the analytical process, and facilitated the development of a cohesive narrative.

The resulting themes were then illustrated using vivid extracts that captured their essence (Braun and Clarke, 2006), creating a distinct narrative supported by rich data (Finlay, 2021). Combined results and discussions provided a direct synthesis of the data

presented (Terry *et al.*, 2017) and helped elevate the write-up from illustrative to analytical (Byrne, 2022). In addressing transferability, the researcher provided *naturalistic generalisations* (Sparkes and Smith, 2014) through relatable vicarious experiences (Tracy, 2010) to try to affect reflection and change in the reader's practice (Smith and Caddick, 2012). However, transfer is a highly individual process that is difficult to predict, so *analytical generalisations* were also suggested (Smith, 2018). Theoretical discussion is provided to connect the study findings to broader sports coaching contexts. Through *user generalisability* (Ahumada, Galdames and Clarke, 2016), readers are encouraged to reflect on their own experiences in similar situations to gain new insights, understandings, and meanings.

4 Neophyte Experiences of Football (Soccer) Match Analysis: A Multiple Case Study Approach

This is the first of three chapters presenting original research in this thesis. The work in this chapter has been published (McKenna *et al.*, 2018) with the accepted manuscript provided in [Appendix 1](#). However, this chapter offers an augmented version that incorporates recent findings and situates the output within the framework of this thesis.

4.1 Introduction

Match analysis is well-established within elite team sport settings as a method to augment subjective observations of sport performance (Prim and van Rooyen, 2013; Carling, Lawlor and Wells, 2018). While research on match analysis is extensive (Mackenzie and Cushion, 2013), it mainly focuses on developing match analysis methods (e.g., Lorains, Ball and MacMahon, 2013; Lord *et al.*, 2022) and interpreting its data (e.g., Liu *et al.*, 2016; Moreira Praça *et al.*, 2023). This focus neglects the intricacies inherent in sport coaching (Collins *et al.*, 2022), where individual cognitive processes (Stodter, Abraham and Hodgson, 2024) and a matrix of factors such as roles, interpersonal interaction, and power dynamics intertwine (Thompson, Potrac and Jones, 2015). Given this complexity, researchers are shifting their focus to the integral role of match analysis in high-performance sport coaching and its pedagogy (Nelson and Groom, 2012; Taylor *et al.*, 2017; Fernandez-Echeverria *et al.*, 2019; Gleeson and Kelly, 2021). However, most

research has concentrated on practice descriptions rather than using theoretical frameworks to understand match analysis.

Despite limited research, there are clear indications that match analysis is embedded in cultural, motivational, and interpersonal domains (Booroff, Nelson and Potrac, 2016; Fernandez-Echeverria *et al.*, 2019; Gleeson and Kelly, 2021). A sports team's culture, encompasses traditions, norms, and values (Cruickshank and Collins, 2012), which can profoundly influence match analysis. For instance, over-reliance on performance analysis technology can be negatively perceived by players, especially in coach-centred cultures (Williams and Manley, 2016; Manley and Williams, 2022). Moreover, the micropolitical nature of coaching practice (Thompson, Potrac and Jones, 2015) can impact the application of match analysis (Gibson and Butterworth, 2023). For example, using match analysis to exert power may negatively affect player perceptions, relationships, and club culture (Booroff, Nelson and Potrac, 2016). Practitioners must carefully consider how they use performance data in coaching environments (Collins, Carson and Cruickshank, 2015).

Conversely, humanistic actions like referent, informational, and expert power (Rylander, 2016) may positively influence player engagement with match analysis (Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014; Gleeson and Kelly, 2021). Within this cultural framework, the motivational climate appears pivotal in shaping how players perceive and respond to match analysis. A well-constructed motivational climate can foster positive player

engagement with match analysis feedback. Accordingly, players in team sport settings emphasise the motivational significance of match analysis (Middlemas and Harwood, 2018; Fernandez-Echeverria *et al.*, 2019). In elite rugby, players want more match analysis due to its positive role in match preparations (Francis and Jones, 2014). Similarly, a university netball squad reported heightened motivation when analysis was integrated into pre-match coaching routines (Jenkins, Morgan and O'Donoghue, 2007). Furthermore, the coach-athlete relationship and trust greatly impact player receptiveness to match analysis (Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014). Current discourse predominately focuses on the pedagogical application of match analysis from players' and coaches' perspectives, largely overlooking analysts' experiences and perspectives. This oversight likely stems from valuing analysts as technicians (Martin *et al.*, 2021; Martin *et al.*, 2023) and their restricted role in feedback processes.

Surveys indicate that many analysts have limited involvement in providing match analysis feedback to players, despite their pedagogical insights and desire for more involvement (Wright *et al.*, 2013; Nicholls *et al.*, 2019). Recently, in elite football, some analysts have gained head coaches' trust to deliver feedback to players (Carling, 2019; Andersen, Francis and Bateman, 2022). They have done so by demonstrating the sport-specific knowledge and coaching experience that contemporary analysts require (Martin *et al.*, 2021; Francis, Kyte and Bateman, 2024). Analysts understand that coach trust allows for greater responsibility, enhanced collaboration, and inclusion in decision-making processes (Nelson *et al.*, 2023). Both coaches and analysts recognise the importance of

positive coach-analyst relationships, with trust being fundamental (Wright, Atkins and Jones, 2012; Wright *et al.*, 2013; Bateman and Jones, 2019; Andersen, Francis and Bateman, 2022; Callinan *et al.*, 2023; Nelson *et al.*, 2023). Effective cooperation is crucial for successful match analysis (Gibson and Butterworth, 2023), necessitating strategies to build trust and nurture relationships. These strategies include demonstrating sport-specific knowledge, match analysis proficiency, interpersonal skills, and valued personal traits (Francis *et al.*, 2015; Bateman and Jones, 2019; Nelson *et al.*, 2023).

Thus, understanding analysts' experiences within the match analysis process is essential. The critical representations of analysts in the literature primarily focus on expertise (Bateman and Jones, 2019; Martin *et al.*, 2021). Expert accounts enhance applied knowledge and understanding through experiential and peer learning (Stodter and Cushion, 2017; Van Woezik *et al.*, 2022). However, insights from expert practitioners may not effectively guide novice analysts in their formative development due to disparity in their respective practice. This is important because early career insights have nurtured reflective practice, steered professional development, and shaped support mechanisms in sport psychology and coaching (Collins, Evans-Jones and O'Connor, 2013; Owton, Bond and Tod, 2014; Gomes *et al.*, 2018; Wood *et al.*, 2023). Thus, investigating the experiences of neophyte analysts would be beneficial.

However, few researchers have explored the experiences of neophyte analysts. Butterworth and Turner (2014) noted that embracing uncertainty as a novice analyst was

critical yet provided little contextual depth or theoretical discussion regarding the practical environment. Conversely, Huggan, Nelson and Potrac (2015) investigated the vulnerability of a novice analyst in professional football, highlighting the need to build trust, influence decision-makers, and negotiate their role with the head coach. Thus, further investigation into novice practice is necessary, particularly in men's youth football academies where many early-career analysts start. Therefore, this study aimed to investigate the experiences of analyst interns during their first full season of practice, examining multiple cases of match analysis in professional men's youth football. This exploration was approached through the nested perspectives of culture, motivational climate, and coach-analyst relationship.

4.2 Methods

4.2.1 Design and Background

A multiple-case study design was applied to investigate one full season of professional practice (season 2016/17) across a small number of football squads in professional men's youth football (Ashley, 2012). Each case was initially explored in isolation, then the similarities and differences between cases were compared (Willig, 2022). A multiple-case study design was particularly suited to this research as it enables both a nuanced understanding of real-world phenomena and comparative analysis across settings. This approach mitigates the limitations of single-site studies, allowing the identification of shared patterns and key contextual variations that strengthen the validity and depth of the findings (Crowe *et al.*, 2011). The clear temporal boundaries (a single football season),

spatial boundaries (elite-level academies), and participant boundaries (neophyte analysts with specific experience) ensured a focused and rigorous exploration of the match analysis process. To address the theoretical drive of this research (Morse, 2015b), an inductive approach was taken.

To ensure rich analysis, cases and participants were purposefully sampled (Douglas, 2022). The study involved Under-17 and Under-20 squads from three small to mid-sized Scottish Premier League football clubs with 'elite level' academies on the Scottish Football Association framework. These clubs had recruited analysis interns from a local university to develop new match analysis systems, with many of the squads adopting match analysis for the first time. The timing of the study coincided with the recent introduction of match analysis as a requirement under the elite club licensing system. Consequently, all three clubs were building capacity in this area. The interns, who had completed a performance analysis module and research project under my supervision, voluntarily consented to take part in the study. Inclusion criteria required analysts to have one full season of match analysis experience in professional football and to have a university degree in sport coaching. The analysts' practice over a season was considered important to add to other longitudinal accounts of applied sport science in football (e.g., Orhant, Carling and Cox, 2010; Carling, Le Gall and Orhant, 2011; Falese, Valle and Federico, 2016).

In one case, the first-team analyst provided occasional guidance to the interns, whereas in another, a coach with prior experience of match analysis supported their work. In the third case, the interns operated without formal in-club support, as coaches and management had little prior experience of utilising match analysis. Participants developed skills in filming, designing analysis tools, coding matches, and supporting coaches in the provision of feedback. These experiences afforded each analyst a comprehensive understanding of their case, enabling them to discuss the match analysis process in detail. At the time, few coaches within each club had experience using match analysis in their coaching. However, younger academy coaches, often recently retired players, had experience with analysis as players. Prior to data collection, institutional ethics approval was granted (see [Appendix 2](#)).

4.2.2 Data Collection

The multi-method approach, recognised as a key strength of case study research (Hamilton and Corbett-Whittier, 2013), combined interviews and archival data to provide a comprehensive understanding of participants' experiences and practices. Data collection involved audio-recorded one-to-one semi-structured interviews between the researcher and the analysts. Interviews were conducted in-person, in a private setting at the intern's place of study and each lasted approximately one hour. The semi-structured format maintained the boundaries of interest while allowing participants to fully discuss their experiences and opinions (Willig, 2022). Archival data (Silverman, 2020) played a central role in developing contextual understanding and informing participant interviews.

This data included match analysis outputs (e.g., video highlights, presentations, and match statistics), and coursework reflections produced during participants' university studies. These outputs served as tangible artefacts illustrating participants' evolving analysis practices and experiences. By integrating this archival data, the researcher was able to frame targeted interview questions, enriching the interviews and supporting a deeper exploration of each case (Crowe *et al.*, 2011).

To promote reflexivity and ensure that the dialogue was co-constructed and not directed by bias (Hastie and Hay, 2012), several days were left between each interview. A broad interview guide was used, focusing on topics such as coaching and analysis background, understanding of analysis and coaching, working with players and coaching staff, utilisation of analysis, impact of analysis, and analyst experiences and opinions (see [Appendix 2](#)). Specific questions were designed to explore participants' experiences through the theoretical lenses of culture, motivational climate, and coach-analyst relationships, ensuring alignment with the study's conceptual framework. The interview guide was piloted with a novice analyst who did not participate in the study, and participants were given advanced notice of the interview guide. By asking for detailed examples and explanations, the interviews aimed to move beyond capturing the *what* and *how* of practice and to explore the *why* of practice with the aim of fully understanding each case (Martindale and Collins, 2010; Martin *et al.*, 2023). While ten interns were initially recruited, data saturation was reached after six participants and seven hours of interviews, at that point data collection was concluded (Fusch and Ness, 2015).

4.2.3 Data Analysis

Data collection and analysis proceeded simultaneously, involving regular and systematic transitions between data collection, coding, and analysis, with similarities and differences in the data examined (Peel, 2020). This promoted the generation of theory that was integrated and close to the data. Braun and Clarke's (2021a) six steps of reflexive thematic analysis were utilised to generate themes and a thematic map (see *Figure 4.1*). The theoretical perspectives of culture, motivational climate, and coach-analyst relationships sensitised the researcher to patterns of meaning in the data, guiding the interpretation of themes without restricting the inductive, data-driven approach. This interpretive focus was underpinned by a thorough process of data familiarisation. Some researchers initially use transcription to deepen their data interrogation (Braun *et al.*, 2019). However, this researcher found transcription to be a clerical task that did not support data familiarisation, so audio-based methods were utilised (Halcomb and Davidson, 2006; Stonehouse, 2019; Vindrola-Padros and Johnson, 2020; Ligita *et al.*, 2022). Instead, cycles of listening, note-taking, and reflection were employed until data familiarisation was established. Note-taking involved interpretation rather than merely recording participant responses, and match analysis software was used for audio-coding (Longomatch, Version 1.3.1, Spain, 2016).

To ensure research quality, trustworthiness and its four subcategories were employed (Korstjens and Moser, 2018). Credibility was ensured through iterative questioning,

triangulation, peer review, and the researcher's familiarity with the culture under investigation. Thick descriptions of the context facilitated transferability. Dependability was enhanced by explaining the selection of the methods used in this study. Confirmability was achieved through reflexivity, an audit trail, and participant member checking (Kornbluh, 2015; Korstjens and Moser, 2018). Member checking enhanced credibility by ensuring participants' perceptions were authentically represented (Smith and McGannon, 2018). After the initial thematic analysis, findings were shared in an informal oral report using accessible language to facilitate understanding and engagement (Martindale and Nash, 2013). Participants confirmed their experiences were fairly reflected, with minor clarifications refining the analysis. In parallel to member checking, critical friends with expertise in sports science, coaching, and performance analysis were used to test and challenge the researcher's interpretations. By offering analytical distance, alternative perspectives, and identifying potential bias, they enhanced the thematic structure and strengthened the analytical process (Brewer and Sparkes, 2011; Sparkes and Smith, 2014).

4.3 Results and Discussion

From the thematic review, four themes and ten sub-themes were identified as central to the experiences of the analysts (see *Figure 4.1*). These outline the analysts' typical journey in creating new match analysis systems with their respective squads: (1) *"building of relationships"*, (2) *"establishing an analysis system"*, (3) *"feedback process"*, and (4) *"establishing effect"*.

Figure 4.1: Thematic Map – Study 1

4.3.1 Building Relationships

Building relationships with coaches was vital in successfully establishing match analysis; with sub-themes identified as *“trust and rapport”*, and *“role clarity”*.

4.3.1.1 Trust and Rapport

Analysts recognised that building trust and rapport with coaches was essential (Bateman and Jones, 2019; Nelson *et al.*, 2023), especially given the power relationships within football clubs and their vulnerability as novice support team members (Huggan, Nelson and Potrac, 2015; Thompson, Potrac and Jones, 2015):

“100% you have to get the coaches onside, because if you don’t, you’re knackered, they’ll get you out the club, I’ve seen it happen.”

Coaches act as gatekeepers to match analysis (Bampouras, Cronin and Miller, 2012; Butterworth, 2023e), and control the feedback environment (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2012; Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018; Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2020), in keeping with the micropolitics of professional football environments (Thompson, Potrac and Jones, 2015). Whilst this gatekeeping can protect the integrity of the match analysis process, it also serves as a barrier to innovation and improved practice in clubs where match analysis is less established. Thus, analysts understood that having a positive coach-analyst relationship was crucial because it constrained all aspects of their role:

“Coaches need to trust you to take on board what you’re saying, what you’ve shown, to then relay it to players.”

Analysts found *“it took a while to create relationships”* with coaches initially *“guarded”*, which was *“maybe a respect thing”* or about *“understanding what we’re bringing to the table”*. Across the cases, there was no discernible difference in the general process of building trust and rapport with coaches. All analysts reported employing similar soft power tactics (Rylander, 2016), including demonstrating sport-specific knowledge, completing analysis work quickly, and providing additional support at training sessions and away matches. These methods were similar to those used by other analysts to build positive coach-analyst relationships (Francis *et al.*, 2015; Bateman and Jones, 2019; Nelson *et*

al., 2023). The coach-athlete interactions built interpersonal liking and gave the analysts referent power (Rylander, 2016):

“It took them a month to learn my name ... eventually we ended up talking about normal stuff, social stuff, and from then it was ‘see how we do this, do you think we should do it like that?’ ... it took a while.”

Trust facilitated smoother communication and fostered an environment where coaches felt comfortable sharing their strategic thoughts. This open and honest dialogue was crucial for creating meaningful analysis (Bateman and Jones, 2019; Andersen, Francis and Bateman, 2022). Additionally, some analysts leveraged coach trust to gain responsibility for developing individual player analysis. Analysts with prior experience in performance settings, particularly those working at clubs where a coach or senior analyst provided support, were better positioned to take on these additional responsibilities. This combination of experience and institutional support enhanced their credibility and allowed them to work more closely with players, further strengthening their role within the club. Yet, none of them were asked to deliver player feedback in team meetings. Analysts perceived this to be due to the cultural norm that coaches control team feedback (Bateman and Jones, 2019), rather than a lack of trust. Yet, this exclusion may also stem from doubts about the neophyte analysts' game understanding and tactical knowledge, underscoring the importance of developing tactical literacy alongside technical skills to build trust (Bateman and Jones, 2019; Francis, Kyte and Bateman, 2024). Enhancing their credibility in the eyes of both coaches and players could further expand their influence and involvement in the feedback process.

4.3.1.2 Role Clarity

Role clarity is necessary for role satisfaction and success in applied sport science (Martindale and Nash, 2013; Alfano and Collins, 2023). Consequently, this is important in coach-analyst dyads (Martin *et al.*, 2021). Initially, analysts found it difficult to establish essential information for their role. They enquired about preferred playing styles and key priorities, often receiving vague responses such as “goals, chances and set plays”. This suggests some aspects of coaching knowledge and decision-making were tacit and difficult to verbalise (Collins, Collins and Carson, 2016) and/or that coaches strategically withheld information as a micropolitical test of their knowledge and character (Burns, Collins and Nolte, 2024). However, this reflects a period when Scottish clubs were in the early stages of integrating match analysis into their academy structures. At the time, the absence of clearly defined game models and feedback processes highlighted the initial phases of adaptation and organisational learning. This contrasts with the current state of Scottish academies, where match analysis is now better embedded and formalised. As a result, coaches in this study had experienced match analysis as players but most of them were using it as coaches for the first time:

*“It was the first week and we asked what the coach wanted tagged ...
‘well, you’re the experts’ ... ‘go and pick out the key bits’ ... so to start
with they weren’t sure how to use it.”*

However, the two clubs that provided the neophytes with support from an experienced coach or analyst helped them further understand the analytical process. These analysts could access examples of tagging from other levels of the club, such as first-team analysis, which provided them with valuable practical references. Nevertheless, they were still constrained by the coaches' preferences and their own relative inexperience in applied performance environments. As coaches became more comfortable with analysis, they began making specific requests for additional information, like *"striker movement in behind"*, which enhanced role clarity. However, discussions about operational definitions got *"quite heated"*, as coaches struggled to reach consensus. Although there were shared tactical principles and a common style of play, these had not been developed into a formalised game model (Ribeiro *et al.*, 2019; O'Sullivan *et al.*, 2023), leading to debate and conflict.

The initial freedom analysts experienced contrasted with the rigid power structures and micropolitics within the clubs (Thompson, Potrac and Jones, 2015), where senior academy coaching staff used legitimate power (Rylander, 2016) to control the environment, *"it is that strict, the gaffer's the gaffer"*. Consequently, analysts were often reminded to respect their position in the organisation's micropolitics, *"the analyst needs to remember he's the analyst and not the coach"*. One analyst recalled:

"That was a warning . . . don't follow up with another question . . . it was the way he said it . . . it was a nice warning . . . you weren't embarrassed by it . . . but if you say something else, he would probably just rip you."

Some analysts had experience of playing or refereeing in professional football, which helped them navigate these dynamics, while others were initially unprepared for the environment:

“The personality of the coaches took me back . . . their egos, I wasn’t prepared for it.”

Otherwise, there were ongoing frustrations around the coaches’ understanding of the analysts’ knowledge and skills, *“they thought we were (primarily) whiz-kids with computers”*. This misconception highlights the value coaches placed on technological support, and why analysts must be competent using technology (Martin *et al.*, 2021; Francis, Kyte and Bateman, 2024). However, as coaching graduates, participants felt they could inform the pedagogical application of match analysis. Some coaches, particularly younger ones with prior experience of match analysis as players, were more open to embracing their analyst’s input, while others were less receptive. This reaffirmed the importance of role clarity, micropolitics, and coach-analyst relationships. These experiences reflect the reported misunderstanding and under-utilisation of analysts (Martin *et al.*, 2023) and the need for coaches to develop their use of analysis (Andersen, Francis and Bateman, 2022).

4.3.2 Establishing an Analysis System

Due to the recent introduction of analysis at each club, analysts had responsibility for developing new match analysis systems. The lack of experience among both analysts

and coaches contributed to micropolitical challenges and organisational learning. In particular, the interns' limited authority and inexperience created problems and constrained their ability to establish robust analysis systems. Subsequently, "*team analysis*" and "*individual analysis*", were identified as sub-themes, reflecting how analysts refined their processes and managed competing demands.

4.3.2.1 *Team Analysis*

Analysts initially developed simple post-match analysis around goals, goal scoring opportunities, and set plays, which are often preferred by coaches (Herold *et al.*, 2021). Accessing opposition footage was difficult so opposition analysis was disregarded. Some analysts were able to adapt existing tagging templates as a foundation, while others had to develop their systems entirely from scratch. Despite their frustration around role clarity, analysts appreciated starting with simple systems because it allowed them to prioritise developing technical competencies such as live tagging, using keyboard shortcuts, refining filming, and ensuring validity and reliability checking required for their roles:

*"I had never done it before . . . it was a great opportunity . . . it was scary
. . . once we got into it more . . . it helped."*

With experience, analysts recognised the need for more meaningful information that supplements rather than replicates the players' intrinsic feedback (Pearson *et al.*, 2023):

“they (analysis variables) were so basic and broad, they (coaches and players) weren’t able to learn that greatly from it (match analysis)”.

Through dialogue, the coach-analyst dyads progressively focused on performance indicators related to possession, similar to those highlighted in other practical accounts (Carling, Lawlor and Wells, 2018; Carling and Datson, 2022). This included goalkeeper distribution, crosses into the box, and entries into the final third, with success typically defined by ball retention. They also looked at regains, team shape, and particularly positioning of defenders. However, the specific focus of these indicators varied between clubs. For example, one club gave more attention to building possession from the goalkeeper, whilst another focused more on turnovers and quick transitions. These developments enhanced the understanding of team performance, and in effect, served to formalise their game models.

The ongoing adaptation of analysis systems reflected a common flexible and iterative approach (Wright *et al.*, 2013). Coaches typically considered data from each match in isolation, with only sporadic comparisons to previous matches. Due to their part-time employment, coaches usually reviewed only critical incidents (Cropley, Miles and Peel, 2012). Consequently, one club allowed analysts to tag miscellaneous events, at their discretion, to aid in identifying these moments. Analysts used this tagging to promote a longer-term view by considering performance development across multiple matches. They also used this opportunity to offer positive reinforcement to players criticised in previous matches, with the aim of encouraging player persistence:

“I felt sorry for a player . . . it was only once he let that man slip (past him) . . . twice the coach said in front of everybody . . . ‘you need to do this’ . . . so (next time) I gave it a tag to show he has done it . . . the player was like ‘I’ve tried!’.”

Analysts recognised the potential of match analysis to have a motivational effect on players (Reeves and Roberts, 2013; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018; Fernandez-Echeverria *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, analysts should play a significant role in shaping the pedagogical environment. Despite the developments made, the clubs were still underutilising match analysis. However, this supports the conceptualisation of match analysis as complex and highly nuanced.

4.3.2.2 Individual Analysis

Although sub-unit analysis was overlooked, all the clubs used individual analysis. One club allowed players open access to individual clips, derived from team analysis, via pen drives (Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018). This practice, though now superseded by cloud-based platforms (Carling, 2019; Butterworth, 2023c), can be viewed as an autonomy-supportive strategy that could positively impact player learning (Corbett *et al.*, 2024). Similar to Booroff, Nelson and Potrac (2016), the other clubs politically selected players *“that could progress to the first team. . . that would buy into it”*. In all cases, individual analysis was optional, with some clubs supporting self-directed individual training. Notably, the clubs that facilitated self-directed training were those where an experienced coach or analyst provided support to the neophyte analysts. This guidance

appeared to enhance the practical application of match analysis, linking individual performance reviews with targeted developmental opportunities. One club hoped that by offering this to a few players, it might encourage others to seek similar support:

“There’s so much scope to go much more in-depth, to look at individual stuff. If you were to do that for every player, I don’t have any doubts that each player would see an improvement.”

Performance indicators were selected through coach and player consultation, after which analysts provided video highlights and statistics regularly to facilitate self-reflection (Pearson *et al.*, 2023). Players were encouraged to discuss their feedback with the analyst, who shared ownership of individual feedback sessions. This collaborative approach empowered players to take an active role in their development, including shaping future analysis:

“can you get more clips? . . . can you break it down into sections? . . . passes, tackles? . . . then (sub)sections even further?”

Other requests included saves categorised by shot type and area for a goalkeeper, and individual battles and headers for a full-back (Roberts *et al.*, 2019). Given their exposure to athlete-centred approaches (Hendry and Hodges, 2013), the individual feedback sessions coordinated by analysts were more interactive than the team sessions led by coaches.

4.3.3 Feedback Process

Within the feedback process there were three sub-themes identified: “*balance of feedback*”, “*player engagement*”, and “*delivery particulars*”.

4.3.3.1 Balance of Feedback

Providing a positive learning environment is important to promote player motivation and development (Duda *et al.*, 2018). Therefore, balanced match analysis feedback is important (Reeves and Roberts, 2013; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018; Fernandez-Echeverria *et al.*, 2019). However, feedback should be authentic to maintain player respect and confidence in the coach’s analysis (Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014). In this study, like Raya-Castellano *et al.* (2021), one coach was particularly positive in match analysis feedback sessions with player confidence in mind, focusing less on error correction. This coach had greater experience utilising match analysis and a full-time analyst supporting the youth academy, which may have influenced the feedback environment:

“Feedback (match analysis review with the U17s coach) was a lot more positive (in comparison to U20s and the first team) . . . he wants to make sure he doesn’t dent their confidence . . . his was more constructive . . . he tried to sympathise with them.”

Youth coaches still active as players, used analysis as a positive educational tool, highlighting development opportunities informed by their playing experiences. This

approach appeared well-received and fostered a supportive environment for player development:

“The coach said, ‘I’d rather help them than stand and slaughter them’ . . . he’s good at turning it so they’re learning it without making it a negative.”

Conversely, a bias towards finding fault was evident, particularly among some academy managers who often attended and contributed to feedback sessions:

“‘too many of you guys are going into a tackle and you’re not brave enough’, he (an academy manager) pointed out (around the room) . . . ‘he’s got it, he’s not got it, you’ve got it, you’re brave enough, he’s not brave enough’.”

“An academy manager said to a player ‘that’s because you don’t have the intelligence’ . . . ‘that’s not me being cheeky, I’m just being honest’.”

This controlling and ego-oriented approach risked creating a disempowering and psychologically unsafe environment for players (Duda *et al.*, 2018; Jowett *et al.*, 2023), with success worryingly attributed to inherent traits (Rees, Ingledew and Hardy, 2005). However, similar misuse is echoed across other team sport environments (Bampouras, Cronin and Miller, 2012; Williams and Manley, 2016; Taylor *et al.*, 2017; Manley and Williams, 2022). Additionally, some of their behaviour was perceived as aggressive, with similar abusive leadership linked to demotivation, dissatisfaction, and negative player performance (Sagar and Jowett, 2012; Mazer *et al.*, 2013; Bekiari and Sympas, 2015;

Syrmpas and Bekiari, 2018; Lopez, Dohrn and Posig, 2020). Consequently, the academy managers risked player disengagement or resistance (Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014; Williams and Manley, 2016; Taylor *et al.*, 2017; Manley and Williams, 2022):

*“We won 4-0 . . . an academy manager said, ‘alright boys, ready for this?’
(match analysis feedback) . . . and all the players went ‘uhh!’, moaning.”*

The balance of feedback generally improved over time as coaches became more considered in their application of analysis, avoiding clip selection that focused on significant individual mistakes:

“I said to the coaches (about showing) sending offs . . . what do you want me to do? . . . ‘don’t put it in, we don’t need to make him feel any worse’ . . . I think then they recognised the psychological effect.”

However, the analysts at the club with the most simplistic analysis system, noted that the positivity offered to players was position dependent:

“Defenders mostly saw mistakes . . . the attackers . . . would get a shot away . . . getting a pat on the back . . . midfield didn’t get much.”

It is understood that players can remember performance highlights (Hughes and Bartlett, 2020), including significant mistakes. Addressing these errors during team analysis sessions would be unhelpful, as this feedback may not augment the player’s intrinsic feedback (Anderson *et al.*, 2020). Moreover, showing individual mistakes publicly or giving contrasting feedback to players risks creating an ego-oriented environment with

negative consequences (Hassan and Morgan, 2015). Thus, the balance of feedback and its psychological impact were critical considerations for analysts and coaches.

4.3.3.2 *Player Engagement*

In this study, feedback sessions were classroom-based, and coach controlled, with players typically given a restricted voice, as reported elsewhere (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2012; Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018; Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2020). This is unsurprising given that controlling coaching is common within UK football (Cushion, Ford and Williams, 2012) and that coaching cultures are reproduced (Leeder and Cushion, 2020). Coaches appeared to have low self-awareness and a pedagogical knowledge gap, as highlighted in previous research (Partington and Cushion, 2013; Partington *et al.*, 2015; Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2020; Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2021):

“what we are doing is vital (being interactive), they’re having a say’ (the players) . . . but they weren’t . . . I tried again to have a word . . . but they felt that was interactive . . . that was the problem.”

This frustrated analysts who viewed these sessions as opportunities to enhance players’ tactical understanding through effective questioning. However, the limited questioning used was typically closed, eliciting little player-coach dialogue:

“The coach would freeze it (the video) at points to ask them ‘why’, but it was ‘why you not doing that?’ . . . he wasn’t actually asking them; he was just saying ‘look you have done something wrong’.”

“The players did speak for more (across the season), but it was still something like the coaches spoke for 27 minutes, and the athletes spoke for 1 minute and 15 seconds (referring to a session that was timed).”

As declarative tactical knowledge is crucial for developing game intelligence (García-Ceberino *et al.*, 2020), questioning that challenges this knowledge can facilitate critical thinking, enabling coaches to assess players’ declarative and procedural understanding while fostering a more interactive learning environment (Cope *et al.*, 2016; O’Connor *et al.*, 2022). Beyond assessing comprehension, these interactions help guide discussions towards complex conditional knowledge, such as determining when to press or drop back. This is particularly relevant for U17 and U20 players, who are refining their tactical decision-making, with match analysis serving as a key tool in this developmental process (McRobert and Williams, 2019). However, some analysts stated that players were satisfied with the current arrangements, as opposed to players wanting more involvement (Francis and Jones, 2014). This perceived satisfaction could be due to socialisation into the existing culture (Williams and Manley, 2016), or fear of public discourse far removed from the usual pitch environment (Booroff, Nelson and Potrac, 2016), especially if the environment is psychologically unsafe (Jowett *et al.*, 2023). Additionally, having great respect for their coach can lead players to unquestioningly accepting their opinion (Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014), potentially constraining coach-athlete interactions.

Conversely, some coaches adopted an athlete-centred approach, creating a psychologically safe environment where players could openly and freely communicate with the coach (Griffiths, Mills and Kuklick, 2023; Jowett *et al.*, 2023), with interaction fostered through open questioning (Cope *et al.*, 2016; O'Connor *et al.*, 2022). This approach allowed coaches to better understand player knowledge, subsequently shaping training and further analysis feedback. It also enabled coaches to immediately address points of uncertainty or misunderstanding. Players were considered more engaged during these sessions, likely due to increased autonomy in this interactive environment (Duda *et al.*, 2018). Notably, the club that tended to use a more athlete-centred approach benefited from a first team analyst who supported academy work. This highlights the value of analyst experience in shaping effective feedback processes (Martin *et al.*, 2023). Similar pedagogical thinking suggests fostering active and collaborative learning (Light and Harvey, 2017; Eather *et al.*, 2020). However, coaches still controlled the direction of analysis by selecting clips and leading discussions. Consequently, active learning could have been taken further:

“It wasn’t a case of ‘you have done this wrong, that’s poor, or that’s good’ . . . it was very openminded, open questioning . . . ‘why have you done this’ . . . they would hear what they (the players) had to say . . . ‘could you have done this in the future?’ . . . they would talk about if they’d considered that.”

This open-ended and conditional questioning facilitated deeper discussions, supporting players to reflect on their decision-making and consider alternative actions or situations, shifting the conversation towards more complex conditional knowledge. Similarly, clubs that utilised individual analysis found that players engaged well with the process, which also facilitated deeper reflection on their performance. Individual time with staff to discuss their match analysis feedback promoted player ownership of performance review, goal setting and personalised training. This approach aligns with empowering coaching (Duda *et al.*, 2018) as self-controlled feedback provides autonomy and individual feedback, goal setting instils competence and mastery-orientation, and meaningful one-on-one time with staff fosters the coach-athlete relationship (Jowett and Carpenter, 2015). Therefore, these contrasting approaches to player engagement warrant further investigation, especially from players' perspectives.

4.3.3.3 *Delivery Particulars*

Other delivery particulars were essential in creating the right feedback environment. Duration of feedback sessions was a concern, with some lasting 45–60 minutes, which was too long for players to remain engaged. This was particularly evident at the club without an experienced coach or analyst supporting the process, where the lack of familiarity with feedback delivery contributed to the prolonged sessions. As coaches should avoid providing excessive feedback and instruction (Kinnerk *et al.*, 2023), including in video feedback meetings (Mason, Farrow and Hattie, 2020a), important messages were diluted due to volume of information and repetition:

“At the start, coaches wanted to show everything . . . it was so long . . . it was an hour with 17 year olds . . . I was getting bored, and it was my work.”

Over time, these coaches modified their practice to hold 20–30 minute sessions. The desire to maintain player engagement and improve the quality of feedback drove this change, with shorter sessions proving more effective in conveying key information without overwhelming players. This echoed the preference of football analysts (Wright *et al.*, 2013) and the attempts of other coaches to optimise their feedback volume (Partington *et al.*, 2015; Mason, Farrow and Hattie, 2020b). These adaptations aligned them with the rest of the coaches and seemed to improve player engagement and satisfaction:

“Players seemed a lot more interested because it was (now) only half an hour long . . . at the end (of the season) the players said they actually enjoyed it (match analysis feedback).”

The timing of analysis feedback throughout the week was also well-judged, with all coaches providing feedback early in the week. This allowed players to implement the feedback across the training week (Brümmer, 2019). Particularly, holding feedback sessions 1–2 days after performance was viewed positively:

“I think that time to digest (their emotions) is important . . . to give them (players and coaches) time to deal with it”.

This delay, typically preferred by analysts and players (Wright *et al.*, 2013; Wright *et al.*, 2016), was deemed important for emotional control (Chan and Mallett, 2011), allowing a focused and productive post-match review meeting (McArdle *et al.*, 2010). However, some analysts believed greater regularity of analysis feedback, held immediately before associated training, may be more useful. This method would reduce the volume of information given at once and enable it to be immediately applied. Similar opportunities to apply feedback straightaway in training have been viewed as positive learning experiences by both players and coaches (Francis and Jones, 2014; Mason, Farrow and Hattie, 2020b).

Furthermore, players having restricted access to footage, and distance from the match analysis process, was a limitation (Bampouras, Cronin and Miller, 2012). Those who received individual analysis were given specific clips, not the entire match. Some analysts suggested that increased access for players would enhance their acceptance of and commitment to the analysis process. However, coaches were reportedly resistant, possibly due to their controlling tendencies or unfamiliarity with such technology:

“The match is on the computer . . . ‘I’m terrible with computers me, I don’t know what you’re talking about’ (the coach responded).”

Sport coaches’ reluctance to utilise technology, including match analysis, has been reported (Butryn, 2013; Butterworth and Woodward, 2023). Therefore, coach familiarity with technology is an important consideration when establishing match analysis

(Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018). Since this study was completed, cloud-based data sharing platforms have started to become commonplace (Carling, 2019; Butterworth, 2023c). Subsequently, careful use of technology has the potential to support player development (McCosker *et al.*, 2022), extend an individual's engagement with match analysis, and better facilitate player-led reflection and learning.

4.3.4 *Establishing Effect*

In establishing effect, three sub-themes were recognised: “*data tracking*”, “*player influence*”, and “*coach influence*”.

4.3.4.1 *Data Tracking*

Enhancing match performance and evidencing the impact of analysis is complex. Consequently, researchers have utilised a wide range of situational and contextual variables such as opposition quality, style of play, and scoreline when investigating match performance (McRobert, Fernández-Navarro and Seth, 2023). Therefore, ascertaining team, subunit, and individual contributions to success is difficult. Ultimately, context is key in profiling match performance (Butterworth, 2023d). While analysis focused on critical moments is common (McRobert, Fernández-Navarro and Seth, 2023), relying solely on these moments can be misleading if the analysis is too simplistic:

“The stats did lie because it said they had 60% pass completion, but it was all passing amongst the back four, it wasn't in the final third.”

Decisions about the focus of match analysis are critical, especially when time is restricted, as in this study. These decisions were coach-led, with them relying predominately on subjective information (video over statistics), a flexible and iterative approach to match analysis, and short-term utilisation of analysis (reflecting match-to-match). This approach mirrored typical practices previously reported (Wright *et al.*, 2013; Nicholls *et al.*, 2019; Carling, 2019), and constrained medium- to long-term tracking and planning for performance. When analysts attempted to track performance over time, the data revealed few improvements. Therefore, there was scope to better track performance in these clubs, with multimedia profiling methods having potential utility (Butterworth, 2023d). Given the multifaceted nature of performance, the true impact of match analysis on performance is difficult to ascertain. While match analysis does not directly drive performance change, it plays a critical role in tracking performance and informing the coaching process (Carling, 2019). Although overt practice remains the most influential factor in learning and development, match analysis can support and optimise this process (McRobert and Williams, 2019; Gleeson and Kelly, 2021), which is particularly important given the limited training time between football matches. Therefore, how analysts demonstrate impact warrants further investigation, particularly considering the widespread use of match analysis in football.

4.3.4.2 Player Influence

Despite frustration around the lack of quantifiable changes in performance, analysts agreed match analysis had facilitated dialogue that enhanced coach-athlete relationships (Jowett and Carpenter, 2015):

“The coach felt he had an improved relationship with the players . . . and the players said this was because they were speaking with their coaches a lot more.”

Furthermore, individual analysis was perceived to be particularly impactful in supporting player development and career progression by enhancing their tactical awareness and decision-making (Booroff, Nelson and Potrac, 2016; Wright *et al.*, 2016; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018):

“None of the players were in first team consideration . . . seeing them get in the team was a real success . . . coaches felt the individual analysis had developed them . . . (players) wanted it to carry on because it helped.”

Match analysis was also believed to have strengthened role clarity and team cohesion (Paradis and Martin, 2012; Alfano and Collins, 2023). Furthermore, a player reportedly commented *“the good thing is when we are playing, we can keep each other right”*, and the analyst suggested *“vicarious learning had occurred”*. Therefore, match analysis may have played an important role in revealing player and coach understanding, thus helping

to develop a shared mental model between players and coaches (Giske *et al.*, 2017; Barraclough *et al.*, 2024). This is important as shared knowledge and understanding contribute to satisfied coach-athlete relationships (Jowett and Carpenter, 2015).

4.3.4.3 Coach Influence

As coaches shape the learning environment and facilitate the provision of match analysis feedback (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2011; Taylor, Collins and Cruickshank, 2022), any impact on the coach would be crucial. Notably, there was substantial engagement from younger coaches, proactive in seeking support:

“I want to go into (full-time) management after my (playing) career (ends), and I would definitely have this (match analysis)!’ . . . he properly took it on board.”

“The other coaches (not getting analysis support) would say ‘can you do my team this weekend?’ . . . they all wanted a bit of it.”

Match analysis extended the time coaches spent with players, which was important given the limited pitch time available due to multiple factors, including player recovery. However, the integration of match analysis into their coaching processes took time, with a significant learning curve to negotiate:

“From where we started . . . we were really bad (at using the analysis) . . . to where we left it was completely different.”

Analysts reported that coaches improved the balance of their match analysis feedback. Similar to findings by Booroff, Nelson and Potrac (2016), coaches also learned to use analysis politically to conduct targeted training. For example, *“the coaches changed training . . . using tactics to get them (key players) on the ball (more)”*, but not at the expense of developing other players. Match analysis also influenced other aspects of coach decision-making, such as team tactics and training design as is common in football (Brümmer, 2019):

“Something came up in the video and the coach would tell the players, ‘see that, that’s what we’re going to work on tonight’ . . . before the video was based on the training, but now the training was going to be based on the video.”

Despite these successes, some analysts were left frustrated, *“it’s not being fully utilised . . . the potential’s there”*. In particular, none of the analysts were able to influence the coaches to increase player interaction in feedback sessions. However, as coaching is complex (Collins *et al.*, 2022), decisions to extend the use of match analysis are influenced by the specific context (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2011; Macquet, Ferrand and Stanton, 2015; Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018). Therefore, the thought processes of coaches applying match analysis warrant further investigation.

4.4 Conclusion

This study provides an authentic account of neophyte analysts' experiences, highlighting the cultural, motivational, and relational dynamics that shaped their roles. Adopting a nested theoretical framework (Collins and Cruickshank, 2015), the study examines how analysts strategically navigated micropolitical landscapes (Gibson and Groom, 2018) to build trust in coach-analyst relationships (Bateman and Jones, 2019) by applying soft power tactics (Rylander, 2016). Establishing match analysis systems was constrained by initial role ambiguity, coaches' analytical literacy, and the need to align analysis with coaching priorities (Martin *et al.*, 2021; Andersen, Francis and Bateman, 2022). While match analysis provided tactical and developmental insights, its pedagogical application was underutilised, particularly in feedback processes where coach dominance restricted player engagement (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2012; Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018).

The balance of feedback was critical in fostering an autonomy-supportive and task-involved motivational climate (Duda *et al.*, 2018), yet some environments risked being psychologically unsafe due to controlling or punitive feedback practices (Jowett *et al.*, 2023). Moreover, analysts played a significant role in structuring player learning through individual analysis, promoting self-reflection and tactical development (Brümmer, 2018; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018). Despite these contributions, analysts struggled to demonstrate their broader impact beyond performance tracking, as their capacity to act as curators, translators, and facilitators of match analysis remained undervalued and

misunderstood (Martin *et al.*, 2021). These findings highlight key considerations for embedding match analysis more effectively within performance environments.

To address these challenges, the training of analysts must involve the development of technical expertise and interpersonal skills. Thus, contextualised learning activities that prepare analysts for the micropolitical realities of coaching are key, beginning with role-clarification exercises and trust-building simulations to develop credibility and support integration (Bateman and Jones, 2019; Nelson *et al.*, 2023). Additionally, mentoring from experienced analysts and engaging in critical reflection further supports their ability to refine strategies and adapt to coaching environments (Downham and Cushion, 2022; Cooke, Allen and Paradis, 2023; Mulvenna and Viner, 2024). Strengthening these foundations will allow analysts to contribute meaningfully to feedback processes and learning environments. Beyond this, analysts' pedagogical knowledge should be recognised and utilised, ensuring they contribute not only as data providers but as educators. This necessitates clear job profiles and role expectations that formalise analysts' contributions to coach and player education, reinforcing their role as facilitators of learning rather than purely technical support staff.

Clubs should establish clear performance structures, including game models, tactical frameworks, and feedback processes, to align coaching and analysis. These should underpin formal induction programs for new coaches and analysts, clarifying responsibilities and embedding match analysis within training and decision-making.

Where a game model is not yet established, its development should be prioritised to create a shared tactical language and analytical focus (Ribeiro *et al.*, 2019; O’Sullivan *et al.*, 2023). Inductions should familiarise analysts with club philosophies, key performance indicators, and how analysis integrates into coaching workflows. Beyond induction, ongoing professional development in performance analysis for both analysts and coaches is essential but can often be lacking (Martin *et al.*, 2023).

Analysts often possess pedagogical knowledge, yet this remains underutilised. Clubs should invest in training that enables coaches to harness this understanding, fostering collaborative learning environments. Implementing structured feedback systems grounded in empowering coaching (where match analysis supports task-orientation, autonomy, and social support) can enhance player engagement and decision-making (Duda *et al.*, 2018). Additionally, clubs should establish mechanisms such as coach-analyst tactical meetings, pre-training analysis briefings, and structured post-match debriefs to ensure analysts contribute beyond providing match data. Ensuring analysts have formal platforms to collaborate with coaches would strengthen their integration within performance environments and address their underutilisation.

These findings also have important implications for the design of analyst and coach education programs. This study provides a model of neophyte analyst experiences, which aligns with a nested theoretical perspective (Collins and Cruickshank, 2015), and offers a framework for analyst development (see *Figure 4.2*). While previous research has

examined performance analysts' roles, this study uniquely highlights the micropolitical challenges neophyte analysts face, their potential role in shaping player learning, and the need for structured induction frameworks. These findings build on existing literature by underscoring the need for interdisciplinary understanding to facilitate analyst integration within coaching teams. Therefore, embedding this model within formal training programs would ensure analysts develop both technical expertise and the interpersonal competencies needed for effective integration into high-performance sport environments.

Equally, coach education programs should incorporate inputs on working with analysts, ensuring that coaches are equipped to effectively engage with match analysis, integrate it into feedback processes, and foster collaborative decision-making. By embedding these principles, training programs, clubs, and governing bodies can strengthen the integration of match analysis within coaching structures, ensuring that both analysts and coaches navigate the cultural, motivational, and relational complexities that shape effective performance environments. Ultimately, this study discusses the evolving role of analysts and the potential for their integration as key members of coaching teams, contributing beyond data provision to shaping player learning, decision-making, and performance outcomes.

Figure 4.2: A Model of Neophyte Analyst Experiences

4.5 Bridging Synthesis

This was the first in a series of three linked studies, investigating the experiences of the key stakeholders in the analysis process – analysts, players, and coaches. In this chapter, using a nested theoretical framework encompassing culture, motivational climate, and interpersonal dynamics proved highly effective in exploring the experiences of neophyte analysts in male professional youth football. A key focus for all analysts, given their pedagogical understanding, was the perceived efficacy of their club's match analysis applications, including how players received feedback. However, a significant limitation of the current study was excluding players from the participant sample. Consequently, the next chapter (Chapter 5) will encompass the perspectives of players, who are both the focus and end users of match analysis. Additionally, analysts in the current chapter asserted that the coach-athlete relationship mediated how players engaged with analysis and that the youth academy environment restricted the time available for the application of match analysis. Thus, Chapter 5 will examine players' experiences with match analysis in an international female youth football squad. This context allows for further investigation of these avenues, given the restricted time in international settings and the call for gender-responsive coaching, which suggests that females may require strong bonds with their coach (Norman, 2016; de Haan and Norman, 2019).

5 Players' Experiences with Match Analysis in an International Female Youth Football (Soccer) Squad: An Ethnographic Case Study

5.1 Introduction

Match analysis is widely applied in high-performance team sport contexts (Wright *et al.*, 2013; European Club Association, 2019), providing players with augmented video-feedback. Although often considered to be straightforward, match analysis is a complex, ambiguous, and negotiated social process (Taylor *et al.*, 2017; McKenna *et al.*, 2018), with cultural, motivational, and interpersonal dimensions (Booroff, Nelson and Potrac, 2016; Fernandez-Echeverria *et al.*, 2019; Gleeson and Kelly, 2021). Consequently, understanding match analysis requires insights from its key stakeholders, especially players, who are the focus and primary recipients of the feedback generated (Bampouras, Cronin and Miller, 2012). However, much of the existing literature has neglected player's roles (Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014), necessitating naturalistic studies that emphasise players' central role in this pedagogical process (Mackenzie and Cushion, 2013; McKenna *et al.*, 2018).

Among the limited player accounts, common principles are emerging, from studies based on football, rugby and ice-hockey. High-performance team sport players agree that match analysis can enhance team and individual performance (Reeves and Roberts, 2013; Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014), with video-feedback aiding personal reflection (Francis

and Jones, 2014; Wright *et al.*, 2016; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018). Moreover, players report that video-feedback improves game understanding, decision-making, and can promote helpful in-game recollections (Groom and Cushion, 2005; Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014; Wright *et al.*, 2016; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018). Despite these benefits, negative experiences have been reported, such as over-bearing coaches, relentless surveillance, poor quality match review, and conflict during feedback meetings (Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014; Williams and Manley, 2016; Taylor *et al.*, 2017; Manley and Williams, 2022). Players have also expressed fear and anxiety around public criticism, avoidance of contentious discussions, and disengagement from overly critical reviews (Williams and Manley, 2016; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018). These experiences vary due to the different coaching environments involved. Thus, coaching context should be a key focus in match analysis research.

However, the majority of player accounts offer male perspectives, with few studies on female perspectives. Considering female players is crucial because the application of match analysis is context-specific (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2011; McKenna *et al.*, 2018; Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018), and female players experience distinct environments, characterised by contrasting resources, support, and professional status (Sleeman and Ronkainen, 2020; Fielding-Lloyd and Woodhouse, 2023), and may have different needs compared to male players (Norman, 2016). Female netball players reported that pre-match motivational videos enhanced their performance comprehension, individual and team confidence, and motivation (Jenkins, Morgan and O'Donoghue,

2007), similar to male football players experiencing match analysis (Middlemas and Harwood, 2018). Taylor *et al.* (2017) revealed that a female international hockey player had negative experiences with match analysis due to controlling coaching, similar to the experiences of male rugby players (Williams and Manley, 2016).

Paradoxically, others noted that female players focus more on developmental (negative) feedback (Fernandez-Echeverria *et al.*, 2019; Loo, Francis and Bateman, 2020), with males preferring positive feedback (Groom and Cushion, 2005), possibly stemming from gender differences in goal-orientation (Murcia, Gimeno and Coll, 2008; Hanrahan and Cerin, 2009; Koh and Wang, 2015). These findings support calls for gender-responsive coaching in high-performance sport (Norman, 2016; de Haan and Norman, 2019), which involves being mindful of and responsive to gendered patterns such as female players' needs for enjoyment, discussion of rationale, personal relationships, and democratic coaching (Norman and French, 2013; Norman, 2015). Therefore, gender-responsive coaching requires attention to the relational and motivational aspects of coaching. However, coaches must also account for individual differences, preferences, and needs in the context of match analysis (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2011). Accordingly, Gosai, Jowett and Rhind (2022) advise against gender stereotyping and advocate for tailored coaching that addresses each players' unique characteristics. Differences in match analysis experiences between male and female players are likely shaped not just by gender, but also by contrasting environments and disparities in resources, support, and professional status (Sleeman and Ronkainen, 2020; Fielding-Lloyd and Woodhouse,

2023). Therefore, investigating female players' perspectives is essential for advancing gender equity and to gain a more nuanced understanding of match analysis.

Furthermore, player accounts have mostly focused on club environments (e.g., Francis and Jones, 2014; Wright *et al.*, 2016) despite match analysis also being routinely employed in international settings (Nicholls *et al.*, 2019). While insights from international youth football coaches exist, there is a notable gap in understanding international players' perspectives (Taylor *et al.*, 2017). Investigating international contexts is imperative due to substantial differences from club settings, such as the limited time coaches, players, and analysts spend together during competitions and training camps (Lindgren and Barker-Ruchti, 2017), the varying familiarity with opponents, and the different tactical profiles of teams at the international level. These factors can significantly impact match analysis application, making international contexts essential for study.

Moreover, the theoretical lens in match analysis literature warrants consideration. Although useful insights have been provided, many studies lack a specific theoretical framework, which could enhance understanding, as seen in studies on surveillance and psychological factors in match analysis (Williams and Manley, 2016; Taylor *et al.*, 2017; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018). Despite this, several articles link player experiences with match analysis to culture, motivation, and interpersonal dynamics, as it has in broader coaching practice (Collins and Cruickshank, 2015). For example, a controlling coaching culture and the use of hard power tactics can thwart player involvement in match analysis

(Manley and Williams, 2022). Meanwhile, coaching behaviour in feedback analysis sessions can promote or thwart player engagement (Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018), and with it player motivation. Furthermore, the coach-athlete relationship, and trust in particular, shapes the way players receive and respond to their coaches' match analysis feedback (Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014). Thus, this study aims to explore the perceptions of match analysis in an international female youth football squad through the nested perspectives of culture, motivational climate, and the coach-athlete relationship.

5.2 Methods

5.2.1 Design and Background

To appreciate the multifaceted nature of applied phenomena, investigations within natural settings are required (Willig, 2022). Therefore, an ethnographic case study was conducted, involving longitudinal participant observation, a contextually bounded case, and multiple data collection methods (White, Drew and Hay, 2009). This approach was particularly suited to the research aims, as it facilitated in-depth, context-specific inquiry and offered a nuanced, insider perspective on match analysis practices (Cushion, 2014). An international female youth football squad (Under-19s) was purposefully chosen for the study (Douglas, 2022). The coaching staff, comprising one head coach and three assistance coaches, each with over 5 years of experiences in high-performance women's football, were pivotal in shaping the squad's approach to match analysis. Their awareness of female players' needs (Norman, 2016; de Haan and Norman, 2019) informed an

athlete-centred coaching style that supported player confidence and motivation. Match analysis was delivered in a way that provided players with rationale, opportunities to discuss tactics, and a chance to have their opinions heard, sometimes influencing coach decisions, such as altering the team's defensive pressing strategy based on player feedback. Feedback was also provided in a non-judgmental way, where individual players were not subject to public criticism, fostering a psychologically safe environment (Jowett *et al.*, 2023).

The researcher had access to the case as the squad's performance analyst. The squad typically had only 2-3 days to prepare for each international match, with two pre-match review sessions and a final team practice focusing on team tactics were conducted. The first pre-match review session focused on understanding the next opponent, while the second addressed the team strategy to be deployed. Shortly after each match, a post-match analysis session reviewed the recent performance (see *Figure 5.1*). These sessions were classroom-based team meetings, lasting approximately 20 minutes, with video highlights and presentation slides shown on a large screen. The head coach stood at the front of the room, near the screen, with players seated in a horseshoe arrangement and other staff observing from behind. These meetings were supplemented with occasional sub-unit reviews and open access to all unedited and tagged match video. The ethnographic approach allowed for sustained, real-time observations of players' interactions with match analysis, capturing longitudinal shifts in engagement, squad dynamics, and learning processes. By embedding within the environment over two years,

this study identified changes that may not have been fully realised through cross-sectional or retrospective methods, particularly in how players navigated feedback sessions, informal learning spaces, and evolving roles within the squad.

Figure 5.1: The Squad's Typical Pre-Match and Post-Match Video-Feedback Process

The squad was observed across 2 years, encompassing 9 international trips, approximately 70 days, and 24 competitive matches. The prolonged immersion fostered trust and openness, allowing rich insights into players' lived experiences and relationships with match analysis (Hammersley and Atkinson, 2019). Temporal boundaries (two-year duration), spatial boundaries (the international squad environment), and participant boundaries (players with ≥ 1 year international experience) ensured a rigorous and focused exploration of match analysis practices. Maximum variation sampling (Douglas, 2022) included both regular starters and substitutes, and players from all sub-units of the team. The sample comprised 9 players averaging 18 years of age and ≥ 3 years of international experience, who made every trip. The group comprised 1 goalkeeper, 4 defensive players (2 centre backs, 1 full back, 1 defensive midfielder), and 4 attacking players (2 wingers, 2 centre forwards). The sample also included 5 regular starters and 4 players who spent significant time as substitutes. In terms of wider experience, some players had several seasons of match analysis exposure at their clubs while others had

only engaged with it through this international squad. All players had been playing senior women's football for a minimum of 2 years. Additional player and squad characteristics are withheld to prevent deductive disclosure (Kaiser, 2012), and pseudonyms are used. Prior to data collection, institutional ethics approval was granted (see [Appendix 3](#)).

5.2.2 Data Collection

The multi-method approach, recognised as a key strength of case study research (Hamilton and Corbett-Whittier, 2013), combined interviews and participant-observation to provide a comprehensive understanding of participants' experiences. Participant observations aimed to develop a nuanced understanding of the squad's match analysis (Sparkes and Smith, 2014). These observations were guided by the study's theoretical framework, ensuring a focused examination of match analysis practices and interactions within the team environment. Observations included training sessions, formal team, sub-unit and individual player meetings, staff meetings, informal conversations, and solo analysis work. Initially, unstructured observations described the match analysis process, including its timing, location, content, and communication. Over time, observations became more selective and analytical, such as examining specific incidents where players had a legitimate voice in the coaching process. Field-notes were taken in quiet, private moments shortly after events to combat forgetting (Willig, 2022). These observations, alongside match analysis output, informed the subsequent interview process. The interview guide, refined through piloting, covered topics such as: playing and analysis background, understanding of analysis, experiences with analysis, impact

of analysis, and potential improvements (see [Appendix 3](#)). The interview guide was designed to explore participants' experiences through the theoretical lenses of culture, motivational climate, and coach-analyst relationships, ensuring alignment with the study's conceptual framework.

Semi-structured interviews were conducted to maintain focus and allow useful elaboration (Willig, 2022), and participants had advanced notice of the interview guide. Interviews lasted over seven hours, were audio-recorded, and were interspersed across several trips to promote reflexivity. This prevented the researcher from being guided by prejudice (Hastie and Hay, 2012), or them overlooking important everyday aspects of match analysis (Sparkes and Smith, 2014). Data saturation was determined after interviewing the ninth participant (Fusch and Ness, 2015).

5.2.3 Data Analysis

Data collection and analysis proceeded simultaneously (Peel, 2020) and were both completed by the researcher. Reflexive thematic analysis involved data familiarisation and coding before generating, reviewing, and finalising themes and the thematic map (see *Figure 5.2*) (Braun and Clarke, 2021a). During analysis, the theoretical perspectives of culture, motivational climate, and coach-analyst relationships sensitised the researcher to patterns of meaning in the data, guiding the interpretation of themes while maintaining the inductive nature of the analysis. To engage deeply with these patterns, cycles of listening, note-taking, and reflection established data familiarity (McKenna *et al.*, 2018).

Match analysis software (Longomatch, Version 1.3.1, Spain, 2016) was used for audio-coding (Stonehouse, 2019). Trustworthiness was considered during the initial study design (Korstjens and Moser, 2018). Credibility was addressed through thick description, member checking, and data triangulation across multiple methods and participants.

Member checking was conducted following the initial thematic analysis to ensure the findings authentically represented participants' experiences (Smith and McGannon, 2018). Findings were shared in an informal oral report using accessible language to facilitate understanding and engagement (Martindale and Nash, 2013), enabling participants to confirm their experiences were fairly reflected and provide minor clarifications, which refined the analysis. In parallel, critical friends with expertise in sports science, coaching, and performance analysis tested and challenged the researcher's interpretations. By offering analytical distance, identifying alternative perspectives, and uncovering potential biases, they strengthened the thematic structure and the trustworthiness of the findings (Brewer and Sparkes, 2011; Sparkes and Smith, 2014). Dependability was enhanced by explaining the selection of well-established methods. Reflexive action and critical friends ensured confirmability. Transferability is supported through the theoretical and practical analysis offered in this research.

5.3 Results and Discussion

Three main themes were identified as central to player experiences with match analysis: (1) players perceived the ‘positive impacts’ to include education, decision-making, communication and confidence; (2) ‘team meetings’ primarily facilitated these benefits; and (3) ‘further learning opportunities’ beyond team meetings were valuable (see *Figure 5.2*).

Figure 5.2: Thematic Map – Study 2

5.3.1 Positive Impact

Match analysis was positively received by the female players in this study. It provided 'education' that enhanced game knowledge, which was linked to improved 'decision-making', 'communication', and 'confidence'.

5.3.1.1 Player Education and Decision-Making

The female players understood the personal benefits of match analysis, particularly its role in providing tactical education. They stated that it *“does improve you”*, facilitates *“thinking about the next game”*, and aids *“mental preparation”*, thus creating *“a better chance of performing (well) and winning”*. By reviewing match footage, they gained clearer insights into upcoming opponents, team performance, and tactical instructions and roles, strengthening their declarative knowledge – the foundational understanding of tactical concepts, team strategies, and the rationale behind in-game decisions (McRobert and Williams, 2019). This was especially important in the international context, where players faced unfamiliar opponents and coordinated with teammates they did not regularly train with:

“It helps everyone to understand each other’s positions ... I’ve gained a better understanding ... being able to watch clips.”

Declarative knowledge alone, however, is insufficient for effective in-game performance. Match analysis also supported the players in refining their procedural knowledge, helping them translate tactical insights into action (McRobert and Williams, 2019). Players

highlighted how reviewing video helped them coordinate with others and refine their in-game actions, highlighting the value of match analysis in providing tactical clarity during pre-match preparations:

“now I understand ... how we can get out of different situations ... their team hits big diagonal passes ... we can clearly utilise this.”

“If I went into the game against Ireland without seeing clips of them, I would be unsure of my next steps.”

In addition to knowing what to do and how to do it, match analysis helped players refine their ability to read game situations and adjust accordingly. For example, over time, players developed greater tactical cohesion in their pressing, coordinating movements more effectively as a unit. This demonstrates the development of conditional knowledge, where players learn not just to recognise patterns but to apply solutions in context, making better real-time decisions (McRobert and Williams, 2019). For some players in this squad, this was particularly significant due to their limited prior exposure to systematic match analysis at the club level, reflecting the broader disparities in match analysis support between men’s and women’s football during this time:

“you’ve got more time than you think ... why didn’t I do that! It shows you what you should have done instead of what you did.”

“If you know they pressure the ball hard ... you can anticipate it ... then you’ve got your next pass in your head.”

This underscores how match analysis enables players to assess situations in real time, anticipate tactical patterns, and respond appropriately, thereby bridging the gap between theoretical understanding and applied decision-making. Such real-time adaptability is rooted in the interconnection of declarative, procedural, and conditional knowledge, which collectively foster knowledge-informed decision-making, a concept identified across sport performance (Ashford, Abraham and Poolton, 2021b; Price, Collins and Stoszkowski, 2023). The female players highlighted that match analysis helped them recognise in-game cues, a critical component of perceptual skills development (Engelbrecht, Terblanche and Welman, 2016). This is particularly important since most players adopt a 'take the first' heuristic when making decisions (Raab, 2012). Match analysis thus provides a framework for incisive decision-making (Cotterill and Discombe, 2016), acting as pattern recognition training (Farrow and Raab, 2013), and a means of developing action plan profiles (McRobert and Williams, 2019). This process underscores the perception-cognition-action cycle, where players' ability to perceive game situations informs their understanding and ultimately influences their actions on the field.

Importantly, this study concurs with findings among male players, that enhanced game knowledge from match analysis facilitated better decision-making (Reeves and Roberts, 2013). Moreover, the positivity towards match analysis among the female players in this study echoes previous findings in both male and female team sport contexts (Wright *et al.*, 2016; Fernandez-Echeverria *et al.*, 2019), suggesting that players understand and value the benefits of match analysis regardless of gender. Both genders have reported

negative experiences with match analysis whilst still acknowledging its value (Williams and Manley, 2016; Taylor *et al.*, 2017). A defining difference between these positive and negative experiences is the degree of athlete collaboration within the coaching culture. Player involvement in the coaching process is positively received, whereas controlling coaching is viewed negatively.

Additionally, players noted that comparing their in-game experiences with video feedback enabled them to challenge and refine their perceptions of performance:

“In the video it’s clear that pass isn’t on, but in the game you’re certain it is ... but there are some clips ... where that’s exactly how I remember.”

The players conveyed that video-feedback often delivered a *“very different (perspective) to what it’s like during the match”* (Brümmer, 2018), while some identified problems recalling in-match events, *“sometimes I can’t even remember what I’ve done”*. Subsequently, they credited match analysis as being instrumental in providing a more realistic account of performance, similar to male youth football (Middlemas and Harwood, 2018). Therefore, the players in this study perceived that match analysis facilitated meaningful reflection on-action, which supported their ability to anticipate game situations and react to make better decisions during their reflection in-action (McRobert and Williams, 2019; Stephenson, Cronin and Whitehead, 2020).

5.3.1.2 Confidence and Communication

The female players explained that engaging in match analysis increased their self-competence and subsequently improved their confidence:

“It does help your confidence quite a lot because it is really easy to focus on your mistakes. It’s good reinforcement.”

“I feel like I’ve not done anything in the match ... just done a lot of running. I watch it over; I can see things I actually did well I did do something!”

“When I play left-wing, I am more confident I can go and beat them now because I’ve seen myself do it ... I’m like go again, you can do it. After watching the videos back, I can tell myself I am able to do it.”

Players admitted that their initial post-game reflections, before seeing any video, typically involved “exaggerating” errors and being “negative.” This aligns with previous reports of low self-evaluation among high-performance female team sport players (O’Connor *et al.*, 2020; Trbojević and Petrović, 2021). Furthermore, lower self-confidence has been reported among female athletes compared to male athletes (Rintaugu, Mwangi and Toriola, 2018), and world-class female athletes have increased susceptibility to confidence decrements compared to their male counterparts (Hays *et al.*, 2009). Therefore, match analysis can help reframe performance in more positive terms (McKenna *et al.*, 2018; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018), which is particularly important for those with low self-competence and confidence. This aligns with mastery-oriented

learning climates, where constructive, process-focused feedback reinforces competence by allowing players to reflect on both strengths and areas for growth without feeling undermined (Kingston, Wixey and Morgan, 2020).

Additionally, some players linked increased confidence to reviewing previous successful performances, similar to findings in a female netball squad (Jenkins, Morgan and O'Donoghue, 2007). Others suggested that match analysis positively influenced their self-talk. Match analysis can be a source of esteem, emotional, and informational support as the coach encourages players, demonstrates care, and offers tactical advice. In turn, this support can act as a psychological regulatory mechanism, stabilising confidence and reinforcing positive perceptions of performance (Hays *et al.*, 2009; Thomas *et al.*, 2021), while also influencing the instructional, confidence, and psych-up dimensions of positive self-talk (Zourbanos *et al.*, 2011). In particular the technical instruction in match analysis encourages technical self-talk to help them stay on task. Meanwhile, watching past successes on video can have the positive effect of players telling themselves they can do it thus promoting positive self-affirming statements, like “*you can do it*” and “*go again*”.

When asked about the link between match analysis and confidence, the female players referred to being tactically better prepared, enhancing their in-game organisation, and confidence in the team:

*“we got told how opponents set up ... so the team communicated well,
‘Gill you’ve got this person, Jen drop back’ ... you don’t have to explain.”*

*“If I’m shouting ... information from the video analysis ... they wouldn’t
be annoyed ... they’d be like ‘thanks’, it gives better relationships, more
trust.”*

*“analysis makes you a better teammate ... during the match I talk more.
If they don’t know (what to do), I’ve watched the video ... I’d remind
them.”*

As tactical understanding underpins successful decision-making, it is unsurprising that this was a source of self-confidence, as reported previously among female and male athletes (Hays *et al.*, 2007; Thomas *et al.*, 2021). In this study, the female players described how match analysis developed role clarity and a shared mental model (Giske *et al.*, 2017; Barraclough *et al.*, 2024). This improved confidence in the team to communicate effectively, enhancing collective efficacy and team outcome confidence (Fransen *et al.*, 2017). By reinforcing shared tactical understanding, match analysis also provided players with the confidence to articulate instructions and trust teammates in dynamic match situations. These sessions not only provided tactical insights but facilitated discussions among players outside of the formal analysis, helping to deepen their understanding. This interplay between formal and informal learning (Stoszkowski and Collins, 2016) was evident in comments such as *“after the video analysis, everyone is chatting away about it”*, *“we talk about the video analysis ... it helps you bond as a*

team". Resultantly, the players believed that match analysis indirectly enhanced mutual sharing, open discussion, and team cohesion (Pain and Harwood, 2009; Paradis and Martin, 2012). This social outcome may be connected to previous reports of female athletes having a greater need for personal relationships (Norman, 2016) and viewing social support as a source of confidence (Hays *et al.*, 2007).

5.3.2 Team Meetings

The environment of the match analysis team meeting was crucial in facilitating player engagement across this study. The female players discussed the importance of 'message clarity', the 'balance of feedback', and 'player interaction'.

5.3.2.1 Message Clarity

Team meetings typically lasted 20-minutes, with succinctness unanimously favoured, which was a direct result of structured pre-meeting discussions among the coaching staff and analyst, *"I like how it's straight to the point, short"*. Previously, when participating in other squads, the female players had experienced longer sessions and high volumes of information, which were sources of frustration:

"With a previous squad ... amazing analysis ... every single thing (was covered), this player prefers the left, direct her the other way ... but it was bombarding... we were in there (the team meeting) for over an hour, by the end you switch off."

Coaches can overload players with high volumes of information in match analysis feedback sessions (Williams and Manley, 2016; McKenna *et al.*, 2018). In this study, there was tacit acceptance of conventional wisdom, shared by the head coach and the female players, that players find it difficult to concentrate beyond 20-minutes in a classroom-based presentation, “*the coach knows people switch off, we get the right amount*”. The players’ experiences that 20-minute feedback meetings were about right mirrors typical practice reported in men’s football, although significant variation is apparent (Wright *et al.*, 2013; McKenna *et al.*, 2018; Carling, 2019).

Importantly, these succinct meetings were preceded by a pre-meeting involving all coaching staff and the analyst, where match footage was reviewed, key tactical themes were identified, and the most relevant messages were refined. This ensured that only essential tactical content was presented to players, improving message clarity while preventing cognitive overload (Williams and Manley, 2016; McKenna *et al.*, 2018). The pre-meeting discussions allowed the staff to filter out less critical details, ensuring that team meetings remained focused on actionable insights rather than excessive information. This process was particularly valuable in the international context, where time was limited, and ensuring engagement with key points was essential. However, as these short sessions focused primarily on delivering tactical information, they left little opportunity for players to consolidate their knowledge or for coaches to assess their understanding. While informal peer discussions partially addressed this gap, structured player-led sub-unit meetings could have further supported this process by providing

targeted opportunities for tactical review and active engagement, as suggested in another team sport context (Francis and Jones, 2014).

The female players additionally raised the need for conciseness and clarity in coach messaging, *“a maximum of two or three things ... any more confuses you”*. Beyond the number of key messages received, players also highlighted frustration with conflicting messages when participating in video feedback meetings elsewhere:

“At my club ... they pick out so many things ... ‘we need to keep the ball ... need to take risks, but if we lose the ball, it’s not good’, so you can’t win.”

The female players’ preferences for short, well-prepared meetings, and carefully curated video highlights, broadly represent typical and preferred practice in high-performance male contexts (Francis and Jones, 2014; Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014). It echoes the broader coaching literature that calls for clear and decisive communication from high-performance coaches working with elite athletes (Hodgson, Butt and Maynard, 2017). Yet, players recognised succinctness involved some controlling coach behaviours (Bartholomew, Ntoumanis and Thøgersen-Ntoumani, 2009), and increased the risk of missing key information.

The female players also found onscreen text helpful, *“text on the clip ... I like that ...it gives you a heads up ... look out for that”*. They reported that the use of a laser pen, and immediate manoeuvring to exact points of interest helped focus attention:

“That’s quite useful (the laser pen) ... without it you see where they are starting from (on the pitch), but whereas the laser pen shows you the run they are going to make (drawing your attention).”

“They are always short (clips) ... When the coach says pause, you (the analyst) can do it (freeze the video), and you can take it back straight to the exact points (in the video) the coach wants, which helps us focus.”

These preferences are aligned with the use of telestration reported in elite men’s football, which is linked positively to memory recall (Smith *et al.*, 2022; Jones, Rands and Butterworth, 2020). Therefore, the structure of the team feedback meetings in this study may have contributed to the positive effects on reflection in-action noted earlier.

Additionally, some players suggested that the amount of pre-match analysis information influenced perceptions of the opponent’s quality, with the potential to cause negative affect:

“You were nervous ... overloading it (opposition analysis) ... just a little bit (of information) about them, the stuff you need to know would be better.”

Similarly, negative affect in response to team match analysis sessions has also been reported in male youth football (Middlemas and Harwood, 2018), suggesting that coaches should carefully consider how they structure feedback sessions. Raya-Castellano *et al.* (2021) found that a work-based coach development program enhanced coaches' knowledge and understanding of their delivery of match analysis feedback. Therefore, using pedagogical principles can enhance practice (Otte *et al.*, 2020a), and analysts can assist in this process (McKenna *et al.*, 2018). This is important given the pedagogical knowledge gaps among high-performance sport coaches (Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2020; Kinnerk *et al.*, 2023).

5.3.2.2 *Balance of Feedback*

The female players liked balanced reflections from the coach in post-match review meetings regardless of the outcome:

“The balance is really good, it’s not all positive, when we do something not so good you get advice on how to do it better.”

“Sometimes it’s you’ve lost not through performance ... but because you’re playing an absolute top team, whether you lose or win, the analysis is always pretty balanced”

“it’s so important ... to get the right balance ... everyone wants to hear praise ... but it’s good we recognise common (team) mistakes ... and what we can correct for the next game.”

Balancing positive and negative feedback, as commonly practiced (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2011; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018; Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2020; Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2021), is essential during post-match review meetings to create an athlete-centred environment (McKenna *et al.*, 2018). This reflects principles of empowering coaching, which emphasise the importance of fulfilling athletes’ psychological needs, including developing a positive sense of competence, for optimal motivation and engagement (Duda *et al.*, 2018). Providing a mix of constructive feedback and reinforcement allows players to recognise their progress while identifying areas for improvement, reinforcing their sense of competence and engagement with the analysis process. This finding partially aligns with previous research on female team sport players who preferred constructive (negative) feedback (Fernandez-Echeverria *et al.*, 2019; Loo, Francis and Bateman, 2020), contrasting with male players preferring positive feedback (Groom and Cushion, 2005). This suggests that differences may be due to gender-based variations in goal-orientation (Murcia, Gimeno and Coll, 2008; Hanrahan and Cerin, 2009; Koh and Wang, 2015). Consequently, fostering a mastery-oriented environment (Duda *et al.*, 2018) in match analysis may be of greater importance for female players. However, as female and males are socialised into different coaching climates, any preference may reflect their socio-cultural experiences (Roberts and Quesnel, 2023). Moreover,

researchers have promoted the benefits of creating a mastery-oriented environment for male players too (Kingston, Wixey and Morgan, 2020).

In further support of mastery orientation, the female players also preferred the coach to focus on team performance rather than targeting individuals:

“the coach talks to us (collectively) ... we’re all in it together ... you’re not victimised so you don’t get embarrassed (watching a mistake).”

This finding agrees with several studies from both male and female contexts, where players disliked being targeted with individual criticism in team feedback meetings (Williams and Manley, 2016; Taylor *et al.*, 2017; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018), preferring personal criticism to be raised privately (Reeves and Roberts, 2013). Publicly highlighting individual mistakes can create a fear of judgement, inhibiting player engagement and reducing their willingness to contribute to discussions. In contrast, private feedback allows for constructive dialogue without social pressure, fostering trust and promoting a mastery-oriented environment. This aligns with calls to avoid emotionally abusive behaviour (Kerr, Willson and Stirling, 2020), and to foster psychologically safe environments for players, where players feel secure in expressing themselves without fear of embarrassment or repercussion (Jowett *et al.*, 2023). This approach also reflects gender-responsive coaching principles, which underscore the importance of constructive feedback, emotional support, and athlete collaboration in female team sport settings (Norman, 2016; de Haan and Norman, 2019).

However, if a collective mistake was recurring, players accepted that it needed to be addressed publicly, as this reinforced a mastery-oriented learning climate, where errors were framed as opportunities for team-wide improvement rather than individual blame (Duda *et al.*, 2018). This approach also ensured shared tactical understanding, aligning with the concept of shared mental models, where team-wide discussions of errors help synchronise decision-making and improve tactical cohesion (Barraclough *et al.*, 2024). Players contrasted this with their experiences with ego-oriented match analysis in other settings, identifying that it *“puts your confidence down for the next game”*, akin to research on male youth players (Middlemas and Harwood, 2018). This aligns with the concept of disempowering coaching (Duda *et al.*, 2018), where excessive focus on mistakes can create a controlling environment that undermines athlete motivation (Bartholomew, Ntoumanis and Thøgersen-Ntoumani, 2009). Such an approach not only affects confidence but can also negatively impact the coach-athlete relationship, as players recognised that, *“too much individual negative feedback effects your relationship with the coach”*, similar to the experiences reported by a female international field hockey goalkeeper (Taylor *et al.*, 2017). When negative feedback is delivered publicly in a manner that undermines trust and mutual respect, it can create a barrier to communication, limiting player engagement and willingness to seek further clarification or improvement discussions (Jowett and Shanmugam, 2016). In the current case, when the coach rarely singled players out, it was *“more positive, like ‘Elaine, that was great movement’”*, making the coach *“more approachable”*. However, players still expected to be challenged to improve.

When it came to pre-match opposition analysis, players similarly expected a balanced and process-focused analysis of the opposition, which the coach typically provided. Yet occasionally the players' needs were not satisfied with the analysis inaccurately representing an opponent:

“We start off how they pass from defence, so we know how to organise in opposition ... then we move it on to how they attack ... we see exactly how they set up ... so every position knows exactly what they're doing.”

“When we played a lowly ranked nation, we only really got shown their negatives, but they shocked us a little bit, it was level at half-time.”

This finding relates to a male ice-hockey player's preference for authentic and accurate match analysis (Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014), and aligns with the value of providing relatable position-specific match analysis feedback for all players (Francis and Jones, 2014; McKenna *et al.*, 2018; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018). Thus, coaches should enquire about athletes' expectations around match analysis. Giving players a legitimate voice helps the coach reflect their needs and create an autonomy-supportive environment (Hodge, Henry and Smith, 2014).

Furthermore, players welcomed the coach recognising their ability to remember key highlights and critical errors:

“If you’ve just been hammered off a team, we know ourselves ... it’s good the coach doesn’t constantly tell you.”

Players often remember key events, including significant mistakes (Hughes and Bartlett, 2020). Thus, highlighting these errors in team analysis sessions would be counterproductive, as it would not augment the players' intrinsic feedback (Anderson *et al.*, 2020).

5.3.2.3 Player Interaction

In team feedback meetings, most female players disliked being singled out to answer questions especially under coaches who focused on individual error correction. While they interpreted the coaches' intentions as educational, they noted negative consequences to this approach:

“You’d be put on the spot; you’d try and think ... everybody’s looking ... you would go into the next meeting anxious, thinking I don’t want to answer again.”

“Everyone hated that. I was not really focusing (on the review), I was just thinking, what am I going to say if I get picked ... don’t get it wrong.”

In the current case, players identified they were more comfortable in group meetings, *“you speak up more here knowing it doesn’t matter if you are right or wrong”*, and felt it was important they had been given a legitimate voice by the coach:

“The team meeting ... is good because we are told how the head coach wants us to play ... but the head coach still asks us for our input.”

“It is really important to be heard ... and to be able to ask questions if we don’t understand (tactical information).”

Typically, players were silent despite having autonomy to ask questions. When the coach asked questions, which only happened a few times each session, players were not compelled to answer, with responses usually coming from the same few players. This parallels findings from men’s football and rugby where feedback sessions are coach-controlled and the use of questioning is limited (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2012; Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018; Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2020; McKenna *et al.*, 2018). However, unlike these studies which could be results-focused, the approach taken here was process-driven (Wright *et al.*, 2016; Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2021).

The players that answered mostly had greater match analysis experience and played for higher-performing clubs. Thus, players’ willingness to engage in formal discussions was shaped by their squad status and prior exposure to match analysis, reflecting their confidence and micropolitical positioning within the squad (Potrac and Jones, 2009a; O’Connor *et al.*, 2022). In the first year, participants were new to the squad; by year two, they were the older players, with many taking on more significant roles (e.g., captain, vice-captain, starter). With these roles, many became more vocal, showing how engagement evolved over time in the squad. Differences in game understanding and self-

competence contributed to this pattern, with some players opting to observe only as a strategy to maintain credibility (Denison, Mills and Konoval, 2017; Manley and Williams, 2022). Several players in the squad received no regular match analysis in their club football, with one player identifying, “*you feel less confident speaking in a bigger group, in case it’s a stupid question*”. This lack of access is due to the significant gap in funding and support between men’s and women’s football (Sleeman and Ronkainen, 2020; Fielding-Lloyd and Woodhouse, 2023).

This pattern of engagement could be criticised for representing a typical controlling coaching culture (Denison, Mills and Konoval, 2017), that thwarts the players’ need for autonomy (Bartholomew *et al.*, 2011). This contention is supported by male players welcoming greater discussion in match analysis sessions (Wright *et al.*, 2016; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018). Therefore, coach-athlete interaction is considered important because it is perceived to positively impact player learning (Nelson *et al.*, 2014; Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018; Gleeson and Kelly, 2021), in line with notions of active learning (Light and Harvey, 2017; Eather *et al.*, 2020).

However, players did ask questions and engage in discussions with the coach but preferred to do so informally outside of team meetings. When players had questions, they would “*go to the coach and just ask*”, as the private nature of these conversations and the coach’s approach afford psychological safety (Jowett *et al.*, 2023). Another player suggested the international setting helped to facilitate this as “*you have enough time to*

ask question, and to talk to the coaches” since the squad is based together in a hotel between matches. Players identified that *“having a (close) bond with the coach definitely helps”* to facilitate this interaction. This reflects the coach-athlete relationship model, where closeness and trust encourage open communication (Yang and Jowett, 2017). Players’ autonomy over the time and location of coach-athlete discussions was determined by the collaborative coaching culture fostered by the coach (Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018), aligning with empowering coaching principles, particularly autonomy-supportive practice (Duda *et al.*, 2018). This mediating factor may be particularly pertinent to female players given the importance they place on maintaining close relationships (LaVoi, 2007; Norman, 2015; Roberts and Quesnel, 2023) and being able to ask questions to understand the coach’s rationale (Longshore and Sachs, 2015; de Haan and Norman, 2019).

Beyond the freedom to talk, and the players confidence to do so, the seating arrangement was also cited as a contributory factor:

“The horseshoe is important, if someone is speaking you feel you have the attention of everyone ... and their defence ... you can find someone nodding, which makes it easier (to speak out) ... nobody wants to sit down the front.”

“The horseshoe it’s a better set up compared to rows because if someone is talking ... everybody can see everybody else.”

Player's perceptions of this arrangement agree with research that suggests it promotes active engagement due to enhanced visibility of participants (Syaifullah, Munir and Ariyani, 2022). This arrangement may be of greater significance to female players due to the importance of social bonds mentioned before. The meeting rooms used by the squad always had flexible seating, and adopting this arrangement was a conscious decision by the coach to encourage collaboration.

Furthermore, player selection impacted their interaction with post- but not pre-match analysis, with one player stating:

“If I was mostly on the bench, the (post-match) video review was more for me to learn ... if I took feedback on then it would progress me to get a starting position ... take it as a learning curve.”

However, another player admitted, *“If I don't play much, I don't focus (in post-match analysis), I sulk”*. Therefore, the emotional state of players influences their capacity to engage in meaningful post-match interactions, which may be affected by the lack of delay in feedback in the international environment (McArdle *et al.*, 2010).

5.3.3 Further Learning Opportunities

Players highlighted several further learning opportunities beyond team meetings; particularly, 'sub-unit meetings', 'linked training' and 'video access'.

5.3.3.1 Sub-Unit Meetings

The coach occasionally facilitated sub-unit meetings with a maximum of five players in attendance, with the frequency of these meetings not significantly rising over the duration of this study. The players described these events as follows:

“You tend to talk more, whereas in a (bigger) group you mostly sit and watch ... it’s a lot better.”

“It was useful ... three players in the room ... we watched each other’s clips and were asked what we had done well and what we needed to do.”

There was no pattern to the timing or content of these meetings, with both coach and players instigating them. These meetings provided position-specific and individual feedback, but they also facilitated greater conversation and engagement, providing another opportunity to meet the female players’ need for rationale (Longshore and Sachs, 2015; de Haan and Norman, 2019). Smaller groups provided a psychologically safe environment where more players felt comfortable speaking their mind and asking questions (Jowett *et al.*, 2023). Moreover, the specificity of meetings engaged players and limited social loafing (Jones, Høigaard and Peters, 2014), *“I prefer it ... you are seeing things specific, exactly for you”*.

The players also felt that these active and collaborative conversations facilitated greater focus and recall:

“You are definitely more focused in smaller groups. Everyone is always talking about what is on the screen.”

“It sticks in your mind more ... I remember identifying something specific about my performance ... it feels more personal.”

Sub-unit meetings allowed on-field partnerships to be positively influenced, *“I know what they’re thinking, and they know what I’m thinking”*. This understanding comes from role clarity and shared mental models (Giske *et al.*, 2017; Barraclough *et al.*, 2024) impacting both individual and collective decision-making (Wright *et al.*, 2016). Meetings also helped identify and constructively solve disagreements, *“you debate it out and ... sort it out”*, as well as engaging substitutes more readily in the review process. Players expressed a desire for greater regularity of sub-unit meetings, and therefore more analysis (Francis and Jones, 2014), but for meetings to remain brief. Although, players acknowledged time constraints during international competitions, instead pinpointing missed opportunities during training camps.

5.3.3.2 Linked Training

Having match analysis before training meant important tactical messages could be reinforced when training was linked:

“It helps you as a striker (having watched clips in advance of training). You need to press left as that’s the danger ... so you know exactly what you’re doing. So, when we go on the training pitch, and you set up in that formation you know you must be here ... rather than standing there ... I don’t know, I’ve not seen the clip.”

“Watching it and then going out and actually practising it yourself ... it’s going to be stuck in your head more, so you remember the little things during games ... this is the movement they make, this is where they stand.”

The female players also identified that, *“we mirror the video analysis with what we do on the pitch”*. This supports the process of creating action plan profiles, where players rehearse tactical decisions and refine their anticipatory skills in response to match analysis feedback (McRobert and Williams, 2019). Training was an opportunity to clarify and extend their understanding of the game plan, *“it’s mainly at training that we ask about match scenarios”*. These findings align with coach reports of the debriefing to training link (Macquet and Stanton, 2021), and its role on developing players’ anticipatory knowledge and their capacity to effectively coordinate on the pitch (Brümmer, 2018; Ashford *et al.*, 2022). While match analysis is perceived positively, players prefer learning on the pitch, which is common (Groom and Cushion, 2005). Thus, taking match review pitch-side may have benefits. However, Richards, Collins and Mascarenhas (2017) highlight the importance of experiencing both slow deliberate (off-field) and applied (on-field) learning environments in developing decision-making. The players in this study believed that the

tactical awareness developed through match analysis feedback (Hays, Lane and Thomas, 2016) transfers over to the linked practice of game-related scenarios, helping to prime their on-field decision-making (Collins, Collins and Carson, 2022).

5.3.3.3 Video Access

During tournaments, the female players had unrestricted access to both unedited and edited match footage (Wright *et al.*, 2016). However, they had to secure hard copies of the footage from the analyst due to unreliable hotel internet access. By year two, these requests became more frequent, with players actively seeking video access. This greater engagement led to more follow-up discussions with the coach, as players wanted to review specific match situations and clarify tactical details. Video access allowed players to extend their reflective process, *“it’s good that we get access during free time”, “we sit in our rooms, watch it, talk about it, learn from each other”*. Similar to other studies, there are benefits of peer-evaluation in match analysis (Middlemas and Harwood, 2018), which may include enhanced team cohesion (Paradis and Martin, 2012).

Between international trips, players had access to unedited game footage on a cloud-based platform, but they used this access sparingly:

“I don’t use the cloud a lot because of time. I’m at college ... it’s an intense day. Also, I get bored watching the whole game back.”

“Sometimes I’ll start a game but then I’m like fast-forward ... this is a good bit ... fast-forward. I don’t think I’ve ever sat and watched a full game.”

Most players accessed the footage, but reflection was limited and superficial. Barriers to reflection are common (Knowles *et al.*, 2006), with time and video length both significant issues in this context. As the platform did not meet the players’ needs, it could be considered disempowering due to the limited system flexibility, which thwarted the players’ autonomy.

Despite this barrier, players wanted to engage with additional analysis and reflection as they did in-tournament:

“I’d prefer highlights away from camp ... the coach could put clips up of you ... and at another camp ask, ‘what did you think of those clips?’”

“I’ve had themed clips before ... but I would then prefer to talk about that with someone ... I’m not sure what the coach wants me to do with these?”

This echoes previous findings with male players also wanting to extend their engagement with match analysis (Francis and Jones, 2014). However, several less experienced players were unsure of what to focus on during independent review, and desired coach or peer support (Wright *et al.*, 2016; Vinson *et al.*, 2017), thus video cannot be used

indiscriminately. Therefore, the use of audio notes and telestration could help to guide player attention (Jones, Rands and Butterworth, 2020).

5.4 Conclusion

This ethnographic case study explored match analysis in an international female youth football squad, revealing the pathways through which match analysis influenced player engagement and development, reinforcing its role as an integral component of player learning (see *Figure 5.3*). Players perceived match analysis as beneficial for game understanding, decision-making, confidence, and communication, aligning with research on the cognitive and psychological benefits of performance analysis (Middlemas and Harwood, 2018; Wright *et al.*, 2016).

The longitudinal approach provided insights into evolving player engagement and squad dynamics, reinforcing calls for naturalistic investigations (Mackenzie and Cushion, 2013; McKenna *et al.*, 2018). A key finding was the importance of a psychologically safe environment in shaping engagement, reinforcing coach-athlete relationship principles and highlighting trust and open communication in fostering effective learning (Yang and Jowett, 2017; Jowett *et al.*, 2023). The coach's athlete-centred approach, which promoted open discussion, provided rationale, and cultivated a mastery-oriented climate (Duda *et al.*, 2018), was crucial for positive player experiences. However, engagement varied due to squad hierarchy, prior experience with match analysis, and personal confidence levels.

Figure 5.3: Players' Perceptions of Match Analysis Impacts

While match analysis was largely coach-led, structured yet flexible engagement strategies proved essential, echoing research on autonomy-supportive coaching and motivational climates (Rothwell *et al.*, 2017; Goffena and Horn, 2020). Given time constraints in international football, coaches should optimise existing analysis structures rather than introduce additional processes. Match analysis should be concise yet interactive (Wright *et al.*, 2016; McKenna *et al.*, 2018), ensuring players receive key tactical insights efficiently. Incorporating brief sub-unit discussions within team meetings could reinforce these insights, promoting engagement without significantly extending preparation time.

Gender-responsive coaching principles were equally important, as female players benefited from environments fostering player voice, rationale discussions, and balanced feedback (Norman, 2016; de Haan and Norman, 2019). The coach's avoidance of public criticism while fostering player agency contrasts with controlling coaching styles linked to negative engagement with match analysis (Williams and Manley, 2016; Taylor *et al.*,

2017). However, this study nuances these perspectives by demonstrating that while some players thrived under autonomy-support, others remained passive due to squad hierarchy and experience level. This suggests that a one-size-fits-all approach to match analysis feedback may not support all players equally, reinforcing the need for tailored engagement strategies that account for both individual differences and gender-responsive coaching principles. This aligns with broader calls to avoid gender stereotyping while recognising patterns in male and female engagement with feedback and learning (Gosai, Jowett and Rhind, 2022).

A key challenge in this context was video access, with unreliable internet access during tournaments requiring players to request hard copies of footage. Despite this limitation, players actively sought out match footage, demonstrating a strong desire for independent learning. This self-directed approach appeared beneficial, as it encouraged peer discussion and extended tactical reflection beyond formal team meetings (Francis and Jones, 2014; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018). However, these learning opportunities were not sustained post-tournament due to limited access to structured resources. The cloud-based platform only provided full-match footage, making it difficult for players to engage meaningfully in review. Without curated clips or coach-led prompts, players were often unsure what to focus on, and some desired additional guidance to structure their reflection. This highlights the need for federations to invest in high-quality, interactive digital platforms that offer structured review tools, including key match moments, thematic clips, and embedded coaching insights (Vinson *et al.*, 2017). Providing these post-

tournament resources would ensure that players can extend their engagement with match analysis beyond the international setting, reinforcing learning and decision-making in their long-term development.

Beyond logistical challenges, player engagement with match analysis was shaped by power structures, learning environments, and coach-athlete interactions (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2012; Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014; Williams and Manley, 2016; Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018). While structured delivery helped mitigate time constraints, squad hierarchy and prior experience influenced who contributed to discussions and how feedback was received. This study reinforces how power dynamics and cultural expectations impact engagement, with players responding more positively in environments where psychological safety was fostered through open communication and autonomy-supportive coaching (Duda *et al.*, 2018; Jowett *et al.*, 2023).

However, less experienced players were often hesitant to contribute, highlighting the importance of structured opportunities for all voices in performance environments, particularly within gender-responsive coaching frameworks (Norman, 2016; de Haan and Norman, 2019). While much of the existing research focuses on match analysis from the perspective of coaches and analysts, this study captures the lived experiences of female players navigating these processes within an international squad. The findings also extend motivational climate literature by illustrating how the structure and delivery of match analysis—particularly the balance between directive and autonomy-supportive

feedback—can facilitate or inhibit engagement. These insights reinforce the need for an integrated approach where match analysis serves not only as a performance-tracking tool but as a meaningful learning mechanism.

Ultimately, this study highlights the need for match analysis to function not only as a performance-tracking tool but as an integrated part of player learning and development. By considering match analysis through the nested perspectives of culture, motivational climate, and coach-athlete relationships, this study demonstrates how engagement is shaped by broader contextual factors. Ensuring match analysis is structured, accessible, and embedded within coaching processes can enhance player engagement, tactical understanding, and decision-making. These findings contribute to ongoing research advocating for athlete-centred and psychologically safe coaching environments, reinforcing the importance of tailored approaches that account for the complexities of player engagement in high-performance sport. While future research could explore the optimisation of match analysis delivery across diverse performance contexts, these findings offer immediate, practical implications for enhancing practice in women's international youth football.

5.5 Bridging Synthesis

In this chapter, a nested theoretical framework encompassing culture, motivational climate, and the coach-athlete relationship was effective in exploring players' experiences

with match analysis in a female international youth football squad. The study revealed that these experiences were nuanced, reflecting the complexities of the international female youth football environment. To meet these needs, the coach had to consider multiple factors in constructing the match analysis process. However, a significant limitation of the current study was excluding the coach from the participant sample. Consequently, the next chapter (Chapter 6), will focus on a professional coach's experiences with match analysis in women's football. Given the nuanced application of match analysis in women's football, it is anticipated that a coach would require considerable time to develop their understanding and application of these methods. Therefore, Chapter 6 will explore the career of a coach with extensive experience in match analysis to illuminate concepts of expertise and developmental influences in their practice.

6 A Professional Coach's Career Experiences with Match Analysis in Women's Football (Soccer)

6.1 Introduction

Coaches use match analysis to inform the coaching process (Brümmer, 2019; Andersen, Francis and Bateman, 2022). This practice is widespread in high-performance team sports, as coaches seek competitive advantages (Wright, Atkins and Jones, 2012; Painczyk, Hendricks and Kraak, 2017; Kraak, Magwa and Terblanche, 2018; Martin *et al.*, 2018). The benefits of match analysis are well-documented, with it enhancing players' game understanding, decision-making, confidence, and performance (e.g., Reeves and Roberts, 2013; Wright *et al.*, 2016; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018; Fernandez-Echeverria *et al.*, 2019). These benefits can be linked to collaborative and athlete-centred applications, whereas negative accounts (Williams and Manley, 2016; Taylor *et al.*, 2017; Manley and Williams, 2022) can be associated with controlling coaching. Thus, coaching applications of match analysis are complex and social, requiring careful consideration (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2011; Andersen, Francis and Bateman, 2022; Callinan *et al.*, 2023).

Research indicates that match analysis feedback is typically delivered to players through coach-led, classroom-based team feedback meetings (Wright *et al.*, 2013; Sousa *et al.*, 2021; Andersen, Francis and Bateman, 2022). Coaches strive to deliver balanced

feedback, while being mindful of player confidence and motivation (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2011; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018; Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2020; Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2021). This feedback is influenced by situational and psychological factors, including time, technology, and player characteristics (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2011; Macquet, Ferrand and Stanton, 2015; Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018; Sousa *et al.*, 2021). In team feedback sessions, some coaches use player-led discussions to encourage interaction and deeper thinking (Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018; Brümmer, 2019; Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2021; Kinnerk *et al.*, 2023). Conversely, others limit player engagement (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2012; Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2020; Kinnerk *et al.*, 2023). These feedback approaches can be linked to coaching knowledge, with pedagogical gaps often leading to controlling methods. Therefore, to fully understand how match analysis is applied, it is essential to explore how coaching philosophy influences practice (Gould *et al.*, 2017; Collins, 2021), yet this remains under-researched.

Most of this research has focused on male team sports, neglecting the cultural differences between men's and women's football (Sleeman and Ronkainen, 2020; Fielding-Lloyd and Woodhouse, 2023) and calls for gender-responsive coaching (Norman, 2016; de Haan and Norman, 2019). Female athletes may have greater need for discussion of rationale, personal relationships, and democratic coaching (Longshore and Sachs, 2015; Norman, 2016). Furthermore, high-performance female athletes have reported low self-evaluation, self-confidence, and susceptibility to confidence decrements (Hays *et al.*, 2009; Rintaugu,

Mwangi and Toriola, 2018; O'Connor *et al.*, 2020; Trbojević and Petrović, 2021). Additionally, female players may also prefer task-oriented environments in contrast to male players (Murcia, Gimeno and Coll, 2008; Hanrahan and Cerin, 2009; Koh and Wang, 2015). Relatedly, the limited match analysis research on female players may be explainable through a gender-responsive lens (Fernandez-Echeverria *et al.*, 2019; Loo, Francis and Bateman, 2020).

Consequently, exploring coaches' experiences with match analysis in women's football is required, and should involve consideration of the cultural, motivational, and relational aspects of practice (Denison, Mills and Konoval, 2017; Duda *et al.*, 2018; Jowett and Slade, 2021), alongside coaching philosophy. Furthermore, pedagogical expertise is required to optimise coaching practice (Cope *et al.*, 2016), which takes time to develop (Nash and Collins, 2006; Cushion and Stodter, 2023). Therefore, investigating a professional women's football coach with match analysis expertise can advance our understanding of effective practice.

6.2 Methods

6.2.1 Design and Background

Given the complex application of match analysis a qualitative and interpretative paradigm was followed (Armour and Griffiths, 2012). Specifically, a single case study design was selected to investigate a coach's career experiences with match analysis (Willig, 2022).

This approach was chosen for its intrinsic value, as it offered a focused, in-depth examination of an information-rich participant within bounded temporal and spatial contexts (Yin, 2018). The case facilitated a nuanced exploration of the coach's engagement with match analysis, revealing the interplay between coaching philosophy and practical challenges in high-performance women's football. The participant was selected for their expertise in match analysis and their empowering, athlete-centred approach to coaching, identified through preliminary discussions and the researcher's prior professional experience of working with them.

The recruited coach, Noah (pseudonym), acted as an information-rich case (Palinkas *et al.*, 2015) of applied match analysis in women's football. Positioned as an expert in match analysis through his extensive knowledge and experience (Nash *et al.*, 2012; Turner, Nelson and Potrac, 2012), Noah, a UEFA pro-license coach, has >10 years of experience in designing, delivering, and evolving match analysis processes to enhance team and player performance. His career spans key roles including assistant coach, head coach, head of academy, and head of women's football. These experiences have developed his capacity to adapt match analysis to different levels, challenges, and goals, working with youth and senior squads, across club and international environments, and within amateur and professional settings. He has also coached in European club competitions and has supported the development of many players who have earned professional careers and international caps.

A critical aspect of Noah's expertise is his ability to articulate a clear vision for the role of match analysis within his coaching process, using it to inform decision-making, tailor feedback, and shape training priorities. He applies this approach to target both individual player development and overall team performance. This strategic clarity has been central to his successful employment as Head of Girls' Academy at two of the UK's biggest football clubs, where he has implemented evidence-based systems to drive player progression and academy success. This exemplifies adaptive expertise in identifying and solving context-specific challenges, a skill Noah has developed throughout his career (Ashford *et al.*, 2024). Notably, Noah contributed to the early adoption of match analysis practices within women's football in his country, at a time when its use was still emerging across senior and youth settings. His mentorship of other coaches and analysts has further supported the development and effective application of match analysis.

Reflecting hallmarks of coaching expertise (Nash *et al.*, 2012; Turner, Nelson and Potrac, 2012), Noah's practice demonstrates a balance of intuitive decision-making and critical reflection to continue to evolve his methods. Furthermore, his nuanced understanding of practice enables him to address its inherent complexities effectively. Aligned with best practice, his athlete-centred philosophy emphasises building rapport, empowering players, and tailoring his coaching to individual needs. Noah's ability to combine strategic vision, adaptive expertise, and reflective practice positions him as an authority in applied match analysis and coaching within women's football. As a case study, Noah's expertise provides invaluable insights into the integration of match analysis and coaching

philosophy, offering a robust foundation for understanding its application in dynamic and evolving football contexts.

6.2.2 Data Collection

The multi-method nature of this case study, combining interviews and archival data, strengthened the analysis and enhanced the depth of the findings (Hamilton and Corbett-Whittier, 2013). Interviews were the main data source due to their ability to capture participant thoughts, opinions, and attitudes (Sparkes and Smith, 2014). The interviews were semi-structured to help focus data collection whilst still offering flexibility to explore new and context-specific lines of enquiry (Purdy, 2014). Interviewing focused on gaining insights into the 'what', the 'how' and the 'why' of practice (Martindale and Collins, 2010).

An initial scoping interview provided an overview of Noah's career pathway and key developmental moments, establishing a foundation for subsequent interviews. To ensure continuity and allow for deeper exploration of developing themes, every interview began with a brief summary of the previous conversation. To ensure depth and clarity, each interview focused on asking open-ended questions, probing for elaboration, allowing silence to coax responses, and checking for understanding (Braun and Clarke, 2013). The second interview focused on Noah's early experiences as an amateur coach in high-performance women's football, where he first engaged with match analysis. The third interview explored his transition into professional roles, including part-time and international football contexts, where he successfully tested and refined match analysis

processes. Next, the fourth interview examined Noah's transition into youth football and academy management, highlighting the use of match analysis for player development in head of academy roles. In the fifth interview, focus shifted to his experiences with a professional senior women's team, where match analysis was embedded within a full-time coaching structure. A final summary interview consolidated the insights gained, allowing Noah to reflect on the evolution of his match analysis practice over time.

After six interviews lasting over eight hours, data saturation was achieved with rich accounts collected, recurring themes established, and no significant new information obtained from additional dialogue (Fusch and Ness, 2015). A minimum of 7-days were left between interviews to allow data analysis and data collection to proceed simultaneously (Peel, 2020). This also provided time for reflexive thinking and adjustments to the interview guide as needed. For instance, early interviews revealed the participant's contrasting experiences in amateur and professional contexts, prompting the addition of questions exploring how factors such as facilities, staffing, and time influenced match analysis delivery. Similarly, initial discussions on the role of match analysis in individual development plans and the use of online learning platforms led to specific lines of enquiry in subsequent interviews. This iterative process involved regular and systematic cycling between data collection, coding, and analysis, enabling in-depth comparisons. This process was integral to establishing data saturation (Morse, 2015a). Interviews were audio-recorded to facilitate listening (Patton, 2015; Lavee and Itzchakov, 2021) and were held in a comfortable but private setting at the participant's convenience.

An interview guide was developed through pilot interviewing (Sampson, 2004) and included: participant background, coaching philosophy, analysis practices, critical incidents and lessons, constraints, and future analysis directions (see [Appendix 4](#)). The interview guide was designed to explore the participant's experiences through the theoretical lenses of culture, motivational climate, and coach-analyst relationships, ensuring alignment with the study's conceptual framework.

Meanwhile, the participant provided examples of match analysis output from across their career, including match reports and video highlights. These artefacts served as memory prompts during interviews, facilitating detailed recollections of decision-making processes across distinct phases of Noah's career. Aligning with the retrospective focus of the single case study, this approach enriched contextual understanding (Willig, 2022). These tangible outputs provided a foundation for interviews, enabling more detailed questioning and critical exploration of the coach's evolving appreciation of match analysis. By complementing the interview narratives, the archival data strengthened the analysis, offering deeper, context-specific insights. Prior to data collection, institutional ethics approval was granted (see [Appendix 4](#)).

6.2.3 Data Analysis

Reflexive thematic analysis was undertaken and involved data familiarisation and coding before themes were generated, reviewed and organised into a thematic map (see

Figure 6.1) (Braun and Clarke, 2021a). During analysis, the theoretical perspectives of culture, motivational climate, and coach-analyst relationships sensitised the researcher to patterns of meaning in the data, guiding the interpretation of themes while maintaining the inductive nature of the analysis. To ensure the patterns were grounded in the data, cycles of listening, note-taking and reflection took place until data familiarisation was established (McKenna *et al.*, 2018). Then, match analysis software (Nacsport, Scout, Version 8.4.2, Netherlands, 2022) was used to complete audio-coding (Stonehouse, 2019). The trustworthiness of this research was considered during the initial study design (Korstjens and Moser, 2018). The credibility of study results was enhanced through multiple quality assurance methods including iterative questioning both within and across interviews; data saturation which was achieved by the final interview; and the use of critical friends during the research design and the study write up; and member checking. Confirmability was established by checking for fair representation with research participants prior to research dissemination. Thick description was used to provide context-specific details and enhance the likelihood of practical and theoretical transferability of this research to other contexts. Dependability was considered by using well-established methods, and explaining the methodological decisions taken.

6.3 Results and Discussion

Three main themes were central to the coach's career experiences with match analysis: (1) Noah's '*philosophy of practice*', guided his use of match analysis; (2) creating an '*empowering environment*' was key to delivering match analysis feedback; and (3) careful

consideration of the *'environmental constraints'* was crucial in developing an effective match analysis strategy (see

Figure 6.1).

Figure 6.1: Thematic Map – Study 3

6.3.1 Philosophy of Practice

Noah found that match analysis was useful in *'challenging perceptions'*, aiding *'sense-making'*, and influencing *'coach decision-making'*, highlighting its role in his philosophy of practice (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2011).

6.3.1.1 Challenging Perceptions

Reflecting on his early experiences with match analysis, during the initial phase of his career as an amateur coach, Noah emphasised the challenge of real-time performance evaluation and the additional insights gained from video review:

“Live, you’ll gravitate to where the ball is ... and don’t see off the ball movements (easily) ... and you don’t have a high vantage point (from the touchline) ... and the left winger is on the opposite side of the pitch, it’s difficult to see how effective they are ... and there’s eleven players ... when a game is emotionally charged, your head’s mush, you can’t even recall how goals were scored.”

“I remember the first few games getting filmed. It blew my mind the amount of stuff I missed (watching the video back) ... being able to pause it and replay it helps you absorb it ... It can change your opinion ... but you have to be open-minded and humble enough to admit you were wrong.”

Early in his coaching career, Noah relied on instinct and real-time observations, often struggling to capture the full tactical picture. These comments reinforce the impact of information processing and memory on coach observations (Maslovat and Franks, 2020), the role video plays in augmenting feedback (O’Donoghue and Mayes, 2013; Pearson *et al.*, 2023), and the significance of aerial perspectives (Brümmer, 2018). Noah stressed the importance of being open to new insights (Nelson and Groom, 2012). This is

particularly relevant for coaches facing contested environments, which might constrain the match analysis process (Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014; Gibson and Groom, 2018; Gibson and Groom, 2019). Prompted by these insights, Noah modified his approach to live match observations:

“I’ve tried to find different ways (to recall performance more accurately) I always have a notepad and pen, to write things down, and try to be more analytical and remember... with multiple coaches we can divide things up, for example, looking at the midfielders ... like a unit coach ... narrowing down the picture helps.”

“Also, through experience, and especially using analysis... I understand the game better, and it’s probably helped me to find an eye (for what to watch) in games.”

“I’ve got better at taking a little bit of emotion out of it (during live games) ... I can be more analytical (through note-taking).”

Noah’s ability to process match events, developed over several years, was shaped by both experience and structured observation strategies. By distributing observational tasks among staff and taking notes, he narrowed the focus of real-time analysis and improved the accuracy of performance evaluation. This aligns with research suggesting what a coach notices and prioritises is shaped by their sport coaching knowledge (Ashford *et al.*, 2024). Subsequently, this formative phase laid the foundation for a more refined approach as Noah became more purposeful in his in-game observations, which helped him

maintain focus and regulate emotions during matches. These early lessons remained integral to his match analysis process as he progressed into more professional and senior roles.

6.3.1.2 Sense-Making

From his early experimentation as an amateur coach, Noah developed his purposeful use of video to review team performance. As he progressed into professional roles, he incorporated match statistics to provide further context to his assessments:

“Sometimes as a coach, you watch games live, and you don’t quite figure out how the game panned out. Watching it back (chronologically) ... helps you make sense why the game went the way it did.”

“The tags are more about extracting the detail and identifying the patterns. Watching a game live, you might not see the trends. You didn’t realise that most of the time the play was down the left-hand side, or one player’s passing was very poor... but then you see the series of tagged events and you go... that’s so obvious.”

“The stats add a bit more context to what you see ... they can clearly tell you that you didn’t create enough chances, or a lot of your chances came from crosses ... also we had definitive markers ... we’d always aim to get

more than 50% of the ball ... 50% of our shots on target ... most of our regains within 5 seconds.”

Match analysis informs coaching decisions (Jenkins, Morgan and O'Donoghue, 2007; Wright *et al.*, 2013), but how coaches review this analysis is under-researched. Noah used tagged videos to identify tactical patterns and match statistics for performance benchmarking (Herold *et al.*, 2021; Sousa *et al.*, 2021), developing a detailed understanding of team tendencies in the process. This enhanced his declarative knowledge (*what teams do*), such as their preferred attacking and defensive structures, his procedural knowledge (*how they do it*), including their pressing triggers and build-up play, and his conditional knowledge (*when they do it*), recognising when teams adjust their approach based on game state or opposition tactics (McRobert and Williams, 2019). Additionally, he watched unedited video chronologically to enhance his ability to recognise typical event sequences in real-time (Brümmer, 2019). These methods helped Noah refine his tactical understanding, shaping his decision-making (Almeida *et al.*, 2019), game models (Ribeiro *et al.*, 2019; O'Sullivan *et al.*, 2023), and shared mental models (Giske *et al.*, 2017; Barraclough *et al.*, 2024). This may have particular relevance for women's football, due to its relative lack of support (Sleeman and Ronkainen, 2020; Fielding-Lloyd and Woodhouse, 2023), or for coaches moving into new football environments.

6.3.1.3 Coach Decision-Making

Noah identified that match analysis positively affected his strategic decision-making:

“The tags help you to identify trends quickly ... it’s about informing training, game strategies, and team selections ... say we’re working on building or pressing, I would watch all those tagged events and focus on that, get a picture in my head and devise a training session from that. I also watch the tags to efficiently select clips for the (pre-match and post-match) analysis feedback sessions ... As the first team manager I often watched the full-game back and then reviewed the tags. When I had multiple roles, my time was limited, and I would tend to just watch the tags of the match.”

This approach aligns with literature on match analysis informing short-term planning (Wright, Atkins and Jones, 2012), tactical review (Sarmiento *et al.*, 2013; Sousa *et al.*, 2021), and the design of team briefings and training sessions (Sarmiento, Bradley and Travassos, 2015; Brümmer, 2019; Macquet and Stanton, 2021). The aim was to be well-prepared for the next match (Andersen, Francis and Bateman, 2022; Callinan *et al.*, 2023). Noah highlighted the time pressures of managing multiple roles, a challenge common in women’s football that reflects broader structural inequalities (Sleeman and Ronkainen, 2020). Unlike in men’s football, women’s football coaches frequently operate with minimal resources, requiring adaptability across multiple roles and reducing the time available for in-depth analysis. As a result, efficiency often takes precedence over deeper analytical review, with tagged video helping to streamline the process.

Noah's evolving approach to match analysis, using it to check and challenge his initial thoughts on performance, demonstrates the integration of intuitive and deliberative decision-making, a key aspect of developing adaptive expertise (Collins, Collins, & Carson, 2016; Ashford et al., 2024). This balance between instinct and structured review underscores the importance of professional judgements when using match analysis was highlighted:

“Be balanced with it. Don't go overboard. It's there to guide you, but it shouldn't be the be all and end all. You've still got to trust your instincts ... The context behind what you're doing is not always visible on the video.”

This contention contrasts with the metric-driven approach to match analysis in some high-performance team sport environments (Williams and Manley, 2016; Manley and Williams, 2022). This aligns with practitioners advocating for considered use of technology in sport coaching, given the complexity involved and the potential negative consequences of misuse (Collins, Carson and Cruickshank, 2015; McCosker *et al.*, 2022; Griffiths, Mills and Kuklick, 2023).

Match analysis also supported Noah's player recruitment strategy, initiated during his time coaching an amateur team without formal scouting resources early in his career:

“(At player recruitment meetings) we used it to show (potential signings) what we could do for them and how they would fit in the team and stuff like that (using our match analysis footage).”

Despite extensive experience in high-performance women's football, Noah often lacked access to a scouting department or player database (Stanway and Boardman, 2020), highlighting an area for significant growth in women's football. This reliance on match analysis for recruitment reflects a broader systemic lack of support in women's football (Fielding-Lloyd and Woodhouse, 2023), with underdeveloped formal scouting networks being a key example. In such contexts, coaches must take on additional scouting responsibilities, creating inefficiencies that could otherwise be alleviated by dedicated recruitment structures. Accordingly, Noah creatively used opposition analysis to identify signing targets and compile video highlights for recruitment meetings. Thus he leveraged match analysis to persuade players through informational power (Rylander, 2016), while showcasing the club's focus on player development and commitment to positive coach-athlete relationships (Yang and Jowett, 2017).

6.3.2 Empowering Environment

Noah's athlete-centred approach aimed to cultivate an empowering culture for female footballers, enhancing their development and performance through engagement with match analysis. His efforts focused on team feedback meetings and involved 'fostering relationships' with players, facilitating the 'players' voice', 'delaying feedback' to leave time for self-reflection, and carefully considering the challenges of 'public review'.

6.3.2.1 *Fostering Relationships*

Building relationships with players and staff was a cornerstone of Noah's practice from the outset of his career:

“If people can trust and respect you, you've got everything you need ... When you're on the training pitch or in the analysis room ... players might disagree with you, but there's an undertone of respect, trust and buy-in ... so feedback can be constructive ... and we all know it's not personal, and I think that's important.”

Trusting relationships foster open and constructive communication in match analysis feedback sessions (Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014; Taylor *et al.*, 2017). Subsequently, Noah prioritised positive relationships and a psychologically safe environment where individuals could voice concerns and admit mistakes without fear of negative consequences (Jowett *et al.*, 2023). This aligns with empowering coaching (Duda *et al.*, 2018), which emphasises autonomy-supportive environments that enhance motivation. As his career progressed, he developed structured strategies to strengthen relationships. For example, he dedicated considerable effort to achieve this with a full-time senior squad:

“I would make a point every week to do a walk and talk with a player ... just have a conversation about everything, football, life, family ... It makes that bond a little stronger”

Noah's approaches included open, transparent, and consistent communication, and ethical, athlete-centred practices, aligning with research on fostering positive coach-athlete relationships (Jowett and Shanmugam, 2016; Raabe, Readdy and Zakrajsek, 2017; Li, Gao and Hu, 2021), which he grew to understand more deeply over time. He believed building social bonds was particularly important for female players, aligning with gender-responsive coaching (Norman, 2016; de Haan and Norman, 2019). However, trust and respect have been linked to both female and male player engagement in match analysis feedback (Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014; Taylor *et al.*, 2017), and quality of coach-athlete relationships more broadly (Jowett and Slade, 2021). Thus, trust is crucial in women's football to facilitate match analysis, but it may also benefit men's football given that male and female players are socialised into contrasting cultures (Roberts and Quesnel, 2023).

Throughout his career, Noah frequently transitioned into new women's football settings, and prioritised forming key relationships:

“Early on its important to target the senior and influential players, the leaders in the group, and get their buy-in... it can sometimes be harder to get them on board... if they get on board others follow.”

This strategy demonstrated micropolitical awareness and action (Booroff, Nelson and Potrac, 2016; Gibson and Groom, 2019), which was critical early in his career when he had limited legitimate and expert power. Therefore, he established bonds with players,

building his referent power (Rylander, 2016), to facilitate the cooperation needed for successful coaching and match analysis. Relatedly, Noah highlighted the risks associated with poor relationships with players:

“Our analyst left ... we got someone else to step in ... and they didn’t have trust and respect ... you could smell it in the room ... they would stare intently at the coaches as if to say, ‘am I getting that right’... and players weren’t having it... In that instance, having a trusted coach to deliver the feedback would have been better.”

The lack of respect for this member of staff, and their uncertainty, risked players disengaging from the review (Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014; Williams and Manley, 2016; Taylor *et al.*, 2017; Manley and Williams, 2022), reducing the impact of match analysis.

6.3.2.2 Players’ Voice

Noah believed in holding interactive team feedback sessions due to their positive impact. In his early years, he took a more directive approach, but over time he became increasingly conscious of fostering an open dialogue, recognising that players could provide valuable insights:

“Never use match analysis to batter anyone. Use it as a tool to learn and grow, both for the coach, and the individuals you're coaching.”

“I’m very conscious to never come in with a fixed opinion because as you know football isn’t a case of right and wrong ... You open up to the players and ... you quickly realise, God, there’s another two or three options here, and I never thought of that one; and that’s actually a better one than I came up with. So, you share that bit of vulnerability with your players, and they start to take a bit more ownership and get more comfortable and confident with it.”

This empowering approach focused on task-oriented discussions and players autonomy (Duda *et al.*, 2018). It contrasted with controlling, ego-oriented accounts where the coach’s voice dominates (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2012; Williams and Manley, 2016; Taylor *et al.*, 2017; McKenna *et al.*, 2018). By encouraging players to debate different solutions, Noah helped them build an understanding of tactical patterns while refining their ability to judge how and when to apply decisions in different game situations, progressively developing their declarative, procedural, and conditional knowledge (McRobert and Williams, 2019). His knowledge of athlete-centred learning, developed across his career, facilitated the effective use of divergent questioning and silence in promoting player-led discussion (Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018; Brümmer, 2019; Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2021; Kinnerk *et al.*, 2023), and player learning (Light and Harvey, 2017; Bowles and O’Dwyer, 2019; McCleery *et al.*, 2022). Noah also avoided *“jumping on the negatives”*, offering balanced post-match analysis feedback (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2011; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018;

Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2020; Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2021). This extended to pre-match analysis to prevent players from underestimating or fearing opponents (Carling, 2019).

Noah was also cognisant of female players' needs and understood that effectively managing match analysis feedback sessions took time to develop. As he gained experience, he recognised that fewer, well-chosen clips encouraged deeper discussion, enhancing players' critical engagement and prompting him to refine his methods:

"I found very quickly ... they wanted to know why ... to analyse the minute details ... to have every scenario covered ... there has to be a balance between discussion and direction ... and if that's not quite right, that can have a negative impact ... but that's down to the skill of the presenter."

"I initially crammed 10 clips over 10 different themes into feedback sessions ... and (I would) just give players the answer (due to time constraints) ... Now I'm ok using three clips and letting that discussion go for half an hour ... and we don't get to show clip 4 or 5 ... it's worth it because of the player debate."

It has been reported that female athletes are more mastery-oriented and intrinsically motivated (Hanrahan and Cerin, 2009; Koh and Wang, 2015; Wendling *et al.*, 2018), which echoes the scarce match analysis literature with female players preferring more developmental feedback (Fernandez-Echeverria *et al.*, 2019; Loo, Francis and Bateman, 2020). Consequently, female players' greater need for rationale (Longshore and Sachs,

2015; de Haan and Norman, 2019), and democratic coaching (Norman and French, 2013; Norman, 2015) influenced Noah's approach. It took Noah several years to develop this approach, especially the effective questioning required (Cope *et al.*, 2016; O'Connor *et al.*, 2022). This mirrors a group of international women's football coaches who transitioned over time from autocratic to democratic coaching to focus on player development, well-being, and conversation (Lindgren and Barker-Ruchti, 2017). However, while Noah welcomed debate, on occasion discussions had to be curtailed, with players guided towards the correct approach regarding non-negotiable elements of team strategy.

6.3.2.3 *Delaying Feedback*

Noah preferred delaying his post-match review in contrast to some of his peers that conducted an immediate review:

"I've never watched a game straight after. I hate it, but Lewis (another coach) will go home and watch the game and stay up to three in the morning. I just don't think you can be the best person. Win, lose or draw. I'll always wait 24 hours ... If you are watching it the next day, and in 30-minute chunks, you're more calm and collected. You can take things in a lot more that way."

Noah's preference for delay extended to team post-match debrief meetings. While working with a full-time professional club, a structured approach incorporating both "hot" and "cold" debriefs (Kojman *et al.*, 2022) was implemented. Engaging with these

processes refined his approach to managing post-match reviews. Hot debriefs offered the opportunity to capture, validate, and record immediate post-performance emotions and reflections (Dixon, 2023):

“Getting the raw emotion out after a game... ‘that was great’ or ‘that was shit’ ... write it down on a bit of paper instead of having a shouting match in the changing room ... emotions were swayed by results.”

The insights from the hot debrief were put aside and utilised in in post-match analysis meetings 2 days later (cold debrief):

“The majority of the time, (player perspectives) had changed (by the time of the cold debrief) and were more well-rounded ... if they had watched some of the game back and started to analyse it.”

Noah’s preference of a 24-48 hour delay before post-match debriefs matched player and analyst preferences (Wright *et al.*, 2016; McKenna *et al.*, 2018). Emotional control facilitated a focused and productive review (Chan and Mallett, 2011; Mc Ardle *et al.*, 2010), contributing to psychologically safe team meetings (Jowett *et al.*, 2023). Delaying feedback aligns with empowering coaching by promoting self-reflection and autonomy (Duda *et al.*, 2018). Rather than imposing immediate evaluations, Noah’s approach encouraged players to regulate emotions and take control of their learning. Players were given online access to match analysis output around 24 hours post-match, and were encouraged not required to engage in self-reflection before team meetings. Yet, coaches should acknowledge that athletes might feel compelled to engage if the coaching culture

is controlling rather than empowering (Vinson *et al.*, 2017; Brümmer, 2019; Manley and Williams, 2022).

It could also be contested that delaying team feedback meetings was advantageous for the female athletes due to their tendency for self-criticism:

“Female players are more receptive to it (match analysis) ... and more self-critical ... they beat themselves up about mistakes ... so it probably acts a little bit like therapy.”

Allowing players to compare their views in the hot and cold debriefs served to positively reframe their self-evaluations (McKenna *et al.*, 2018; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018). Therefore, this delay may be particularly important for high-performance female players reporting low self-evaluation (O’Connor *et al.*, 2020; Trbojević and Petrović, 2021), by giving them the time and means to engage in critical reflection.

6.3.2.4 Public Review

Over time, Noah refined how he managed public feedback, increasingly incorporating small-group discussions. He focused on team performance in match analysis feedback sessions, reserving individual performance reviews for private discussions, with the aim of preventing negative player reactions (Williams and Manley, 2016; Taylor *et al.*, 2017; McKenna *et al.*, 2018; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018). However, players were inevitably confronted with their own mistakes while collectively addressing team performance.

Therefore, establishing a supportive and productive way of navigating these moments was critical (Jowett *et al.*, 2023). Noah highlighted unwritten rules where players openly admitted significant errors before the team collectively accepted responsibility:

“If there’s an obvious error, like a fullback not tucked in, the player responsible ... will own their mistake. Then another player will go, ‘that’s right, but look at me, I didn’t communicate’ ... and the team start to share responsibility.”

“We lost last year (to our rivals) in the cup. We let them have the ball and tried to get them on the counter(attack) ... our tactics didn’t work ... Now at the analysis (meeting) ... there was a real atmosphere in the room ... until the coaches took responsibility.”

However, Noah recounted instances where players were publicly challenged during match analysis sessions for disregarding the unwritten rules:

“I’m going to address the elephant in the room (said a player), you could have done this better in that moment, I think you could have tracked that runner, I think you switched off ... but listen, that could be me, or anyone of us next time, we need everyone to do that next time, it’s not personal.”

“One of our players presses the ball out of possession but stops 3 yards to go. The opponent plays a long diagonal (pass), that leads to a goal, we lose 2-0. I was waiting for her to own up ... I then asked her if she

would do anything differently. She got her back up, and said no. I then put it to the group ... You happy with that? Nobody answered, so I gave my opinion. The player then disagreed, and we had a debate.”

Shared mental models are crucial for coordinating team efforts (Filho and Tenenbaum, 2020; Simon and Richards, 2022). Successful teams leverage these to enhance team cohesion, decision-making, and performance by aligning members' perceptions through communication, training, and reflection (Filho, Tenenbaum and Yang, 2015; Giske *et al.*, 2017). To realise these benefits, teams need to engage in reflective conversations proactively and respectfully (Richards, Mascarenhas and Collins, 2009). Creating a psychologically safe space (Jowett *et al.*, 2023) and having unwritten rules help players and coaches to navigate these conversations. Dividing the squad into smaller groups for discussion reduces the risks associated with public evaluation, enhancing player interaction (Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018). Noah occasionally used this tactic, supported by formally arranged sub-unit meetings. This may be especially useful with female players, given calls for gender-responsive coaching (Norman, 2016; de Haan and Norman, 2019), which emphasises psychological safety and autonomy-supportive learning environments, both key features of this approach.

6.3.3 Environmental Constraints

Various environmental constraints shaped Noah's approach to match analysis, including 'players' ages', the 'coaching context', and the 'technology' available.

6.3.3.1 Players' Ages

Noah observed notable differences in applying match analysis influenced by players' ages. During his time as Head of Girls' Academy, having a pre-established game model and coaching curriculum informed his match analysis (Ribeiro *et al.*, 2019; O'Sullivan *et al.*, 2023). The game models varied across age groups, starting simpler and growing more complex to facilitate players' progression:

“For the younger players the level of detail you go into is a lot less and the language used is easier... For the youngest children its ‘you have the ball’, ‘I have the ball’, ‘we try to win the ball back’. This developed from 3 to 7 key parts by the upper end of the academy.”

Early on in a player's development, match analysis primarily reinforces declarative and procedural knowledge, providing players with a foundation for tactical understanding and execution. As they advance through the academy, the emphasis shifts towards conditional knowledge, enabling them to adapt their decisions based on in-game contexts (McRobert and Williams, 2019). Match analysis has traditionally been shaped by coaching philosophy and analyst experience (Wright *et al.*, 2013; Sarmiento *et al.*, 2014b; Nicholls *et al.*, 2019). However, aligning match analysis with an athlete's age and stage of development ensures that insights are delivered in a way that supports progressive learning, reflecting calls for contextualised player development frameworks (O'Sullivan *et al.*, 2024). Consequently, the organisational coordination in football academies offers a

new area for exploration in relation to the role of match analysis. In youth football, match analysis aims at long-term player development, thus post-match review is used more frequently (Wright *et al.*, 2013; Stanway and Boardman, 2020). Noah also noted that the emphasis transitioned from individual development in youth to team performance at senior levels, reflecting youth academies' focus on preparing players for professional play (Booroff, Nelson and Potrac, 2016) and the importance of victories in senior football (Carling, 2019).

The relative inexperience of young female players affected their initial interaction with match analysis, influencing how Noah instructed his coaching staff to deliver analysis while head of academy:

“You put young players in a classroom, unfamiliar with analysis, and start asking them questions, you're not going to get a lot of conversation out of them ... seeing themselves on a screen is challenging, and can be embarrassing, never mind starting to critique things that they or their teammates have done.”

“If you can show things that you're doing well, it's a great motivational tool. Players can get a lot of energy from that and gain in confidence. Eventually they start to take ownership of it and speak up ... they then learn to be more analytical, to move beyond commentating, and coaches scaffold this learning with the critical questions asked.”

Scaffolding players' learning from the outset was essential (Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014). This process initially focused on providing positive feedback to enhance the players' perceived competence and intrinsic motivation (Appleton and Duda, 2016). This strategy may be particularly relevant in women's football, where players are likely to have less experience with match analysis. Additionally, lower self-confidence has been reported among female athletes (Rintaugu, Mwangi and Toriola, 2018), and world-class female athletes may have increased susceptibility to confidence decrements (Hays *et al.*, 2009). Meanwhile, player age may impact concentration and cognitive ability, requiring more coach instruction to scaffold understanding before engaging in discussions (Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2021; Kinnerk *et al.*, 2023). This strategy gradually empowered the players to become active participants in the analysis process as their game knowledge and interpretation of game situations developed (Macquet, Ferrand and Stanton, 2015).

As Head of Academy, Noah also noted observable differences in the engagement patterns with match analysis depending on the players' ages:

“Younger ones (12-13 years) were always far more engaging than the older ones ... they wanted to impress the coaches, so they'd shout out ... The older ones (16-17 year olds), it's more like getting blood from a stone, requiring all your experience to try and get answers out of them, and it's the same on the football pitch as well as the classroom.”

These observations agree with the importance of recipient qualities in contextualising the delivery of match analysis (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2011). Additionally, they suggest extending these qualities to include emotional, social, and cognitive development as players progress through sport (Gould and Carson, 2008).

6.3.3.2 Coaching Context

The quality of facilities available to Noah varied based on his coaching context, with differences largely tied to whether clubs operated at an amateur, part-time, or professional level. These variations influenced how he delivered match analysis:

“Twice a week players would finish a hard (2 hour) training session (at 9am) ... They’re wet, cold, sweaty. They want up the road for a shower and something to eat. But they get in their cars and drive to the club’s stadium (5-minutes away) for a half hour analysis session in a small, cramped room.”

“You’re full-time and walk along a corridor and have the auditorium at your fingertips ... or at the University we had access to multiple spaces... at time we would use a lecture theatre format, then we did small groups (in flexible seating) ... and used the computer suite to review clips as individuals or in twos or threes.”

Noah appreciated the flexibility some coaching contexts afforded, recognising how room set-up impacts adult learning by enhancing comfort and promoting engagement and interaction. Configurations that supported visibility and participation, like U-shaped layouts, encouraged active involvement (Syaifullah, Munir and Ariyani, 2022). Additionally, flexible furniture supported collaborative and active learning, and may have enhanced player motivation and reduced anxiety during match analysis feedback meetings. However, such logistical considerations were often dictated by broader funding disparities in women's football (Sleeman and Ronkainen, 2020). Limited financial investment frequently results in poorer quality and less accessible facilities, restricting coaches' ability to create optimised learning environments. In contrast, better-funded settings often provide dedicated on-site resources for immediate post-training video review, facilitating greater engagement with match analysis insights.

The quality of engagement with colleagues also influenced match analysis:

“Working with colleagues all the time, you start to develop a shared mental model very quickly ... where we almost knew each other's thoughts ... nine times out of ten whatever I wanted to focus on in the match analysis the others (coaches and analyst) would be thinking the same.”

In contrast, less familiar working relationships, typical in amateur and part-time clubs, made it challenging to produce high-quality match analysis. In particular, alignment

between coaches and analysts was critical, shaping both the focus and delivery of match analysis (McKenna *et al.*, 2018; Bateman and Jones, 2019). Where strong relationships existed, discussions were more cohesive, but in clubs with limited support staff, Noah had to rely on informal discussions with trusted colleagues to refine his approach. To foster professional growth, he actively sought out seasoned coaches, analysts, and coach educators for reflective conversations (Mulvenna and Viner, 2024). These relationships, based on trust and mutual respect, helped to challenge assumptions and explore new perspectives (Cassidy, Potrac and Rynne, 2023), enhancing coaching effectiveness and player development.

6.3.3.3 Technology

Technology played a significant role in Noah's application of match analysis. Early in his career, resources were limited, restricting the tools available for video analysis. However, as he moved into better-resourced clubs, access to more advanced technology transformed how match analysis was delivered. Heading up an elite women's football academy in England introduced him to smartboards, significantly changing how match footage could be presented and analysed:

“At one club we had interactive smartboards. I think that really made it come to life for a lot of people. It made it better for me to deliver it, more enjoyable. The telestrations, the visuals, help paint the pictures for the players and for them to use the interactive tools was really beneficial.”

Telestration has become commonplace in recent years (Butterworth, 2023c). Research supports Noah's perspective that this technology is pivotal in highlighting key tactical information and aiding memory recall and learning (Jones, Rands and Butterworth, 2020; Smith *et al.*, 2022). One reason for this may be that these technologies better engage players actively in the learning process. Thus, the application of technology can make a significant contribution to meeting the needs of female players.

Meanwhile, another technological advancement that has more recently permeated applied match analysis is cloud-based data sharing platforms (Butterworth, 2023c). Noah explained how this technology has been used:

“This platform (hudl) provided an opportunity for players to reflect in their own time ... in the comfort of their own house ... Match footage got uploaded, players could watch it back, clip their own game, and share those clips and messages with coaches and teammates. This has helped make massive strides in a short space of time ... educating the players on the game model ... without massive amounts of analysis.”

Older youth players preferred engaging in match analysis through the club's online platform, possibly due to psychological safety (Jowett *et al.*, 2023) and the convenience of online communication. Subsequently, adapting coaching strategies to collaboratively use the players' preferred method may improve the team's performance culture (Vinson *et al.*, 2017). This may include providing personalised video clips for pre-match and post-

match analysis (Carling, 2019), enabling players to undertake self-directed review and facilitating asynchronous communication with coaches. However, players new to match analysis might need guidance to effectively review their performance.

Noah also encountered issues related to parental involvement in youth players' use of the video-based platform:

“I was starting to find out the parents were using it almost to deliver their own analysis, but not necessarily in the right way ... ‘You know, I was telling her she should have done that, and I showed her, we had it on the telly, on the big screen.’”

This was an unexpected consequence of providing youth players with access to this technology. Coaches needed to set expectations around parental involvement (Horne, Woolf and Green, 2022; Gao *et al.*, 2024). In this case it was explained to parents how to support the players in athlete-centred ways. These experiences suggest the importance of developing structured frameworks to guide players' self-analysis using cloud-based platforms while clarifying the roles of parents and coaches in the development process. By doing so, coaches can leverage technology effectively while addressing the challenges of its application.

6.4 Conclusion

This study provides an in-depth exploration of how a professional coach's match analysis practices evolved over time, shaped by their coaching philosophy. By tracing Noah's journey across different coaching contexts, from amateur to elite women's football, this study extends research by highlighting the relational, pedagogical, and contextual factors that influence a coach's use of match analysis. Rather than a neutral technical tool, match analysis is inherently nested and dynamic, shaped by culture, motivation, and coach-athlete relationships.

A key contribution of this study is its emphasis on athlete-centred learning within match analysis, considering the role of motivational climate in shaping effective feedback. Noah's approach reflects the pillars of empowering coaching (Duda *et al.*, 2018): autonomy, by encouraging player ownership of analysis discussions; mastery, by using match analysis as a developmental tool rather than a performance-driven critique; and social support, by fostering trust and shared learning (McKenna *et al.*, 2018; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018; Gleeson and Kelly, 2021). Match analysis should be seen as a collaborative learning process rather than a data delivery tool, actively engaging players rather than passively transmitting information (Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2021; Kinnerk *et al.*, 2023). To achieve this, feedback sessions should promote critical reflection, with delayed feedback allowing players time to process performance before reviewing video

(Francis and Jones, 2014; Wright *et al.*, 2016). Encouraging player-led discussions in small-group or unit-based settings fosters collaborative sense-making and the development of shared mental models (Filho, Tenenbaum and Yang, 2015). Maintaining psychological safety ensures that players feel empowered rather than scrutinised (Jowett *et al.*, 2023), while aligning feedback with team culture, game models, and player development goals ensures that analysis remains meaningful and actionable (Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018; O'Sullivan *et al.*, 2023). While previous research has considered athlete engagement in match analysis, this study extends understanding by framing these practices through the lens of empowering coaching.

This study also suggests the need for gender-responsive coaching within match analysis (Norman, 2016). Noah's emphasis on coach-athlete relationships ensured players felt valued and supported, while his careful management of public review settings and focus on shared mental models framed match analysis as a mastery-driven, task-focused process. This is consistent with research suggesting female athletes respond more positively to rationale-driven, developmental feedback (Longshore and Sachs, 2015; de Haan and Norman, 2019). His shift towards discussion-based learning, moving away from directive coaching, reflects democratic, autonomy-supportive coaching (Norman, 2015; Lindgren and Barker-Ruchti, 2017). These findings challenge traditional coach-led match analysis approaches, advocating for relationally attuned, interactive methods that better align with players' learning preferences. However, rather than assuming gendered preferences, Noah took an individualised approach (Gosai, Jowett and Rhind, 2022),

using open communication and relationship-building to determine both individual and collective needs. By fostering an environment where players could express their learning preferences, engagement styles, and feedback sensitivities, he ensured that match analysis was player-centred rather than coach-imposed. This highlights the importance of acknowledging gendered patterns in athlete engagement, while ensuring they inform rather than override the process of understanding players as individuals.

Another major finding relates to the increasing role of digital platforms in match analysis (Butterworth, 2023c). While cloud-based tools offer flexibility and accessibility, this study highlights the risks of unstructured player-led analysis. Without clear guidance, players may struggle to extract meaningful insights or become disengaged (Vinson *et al.*, 2017). Additionally, the study uncovered a novel challenge with parental involvement in youth match analysis, where some parents provided unsanctioned and potentially counterproductive feedback.

This extends concerns about athlete well-being and psychological safety to digital learning environments (Jowett *et al.*, 2023). To address these issues, clubs and coaches should implement structured self-review frameworks that define specific roles for players, coaches, and parents. Players should receive training on how to critically engage with match footage, while coaches should provide structured video breakdowns with clear thematic focus to prevent cognitive overload and ensure analysis supports key learning outcomes (Williams and Manley, 2016; McKenna *et al.*, 2018). Parents should also be

guided on appropriate engagement, with clear boundaries preventing unsolicited feedback that could undermine coaching messages or player confidence (Horne, Woolf and Green, 2022; Gao *et al.*, 2024). By implementing these structured frameworks, digital match analysis can be embedded within athlete-centred learning principles, ensuring that video analysis remains a tool for learning and development rather than a source of stress or confusion.

Finally, this study reinforces the need for match analysis to be embedded as a core component of coaching education (Andersen, Francis and Bateman, 2022). Current education pathways focus on the technical provision of feedback, but this study highlights that effective analysis goes further, requiring an athlete-centred approach. Simply possessing analysis skills is insufficient as coaches must understand how players learn, structure feedback effectively, and adapt match analysis to different developmental contexts. Noah's career illustrates how match analysis expertise develops through informal learning, reflection, and collaboration, challenging the reliance on certifications alone (Martin *et al.*, 2023; Francis, Kyte and Bateman, 2024; Mulvenna and Viner, 2024). Future coach education should integrate peer mentoring, interactive workshops, and case studies that explore match analysis through relational and pedagogical lenses (Downham and Cushion, 2022; Cooke, Allen and Paradis, 2023). Embedding these elements will ensure that coaches develop not just technical proficiency, but also the knowledge and skills needed to make match analysis a powerful learning tool rather than just a data-reporting exercise.

This study reinforces the need to view match analysis as a relational, cultural, and motivational process, rather than a neutral technical tool. Future research should explore athlete-centred delivery, gender-responsive coaching, digital platforms, and coach education, ensuring match analysis continues to evolve as a meaningful learning tool. Importantly, this study demonstrates the value of a nested perspective, highlighting the interconnected factors that shape its effectiveness in coaching and player development.

7 Thesis Synthesis

In this final chapter, a synthesis of the original research chapters is presented. The implications of the findings are examined, highlighting their originality and contribution to the field of applied match analysis. Practical recommendations for practitioners are provided based on the research outcomes. The chapter also acknowledges limitations and suggests directions for future research. Finally, personal reflections on how the researcher's experiences have shaped the work are shared.

7.1 Research Implications

This thesis aimed to enhance understanding of applied match analysis by exploring under-researched perspectives from its three main stakeholders, analysed through a nested perspective of culture, motivational climate, and interpersonal dynamics. Firstly, it examined the experiences of neophyte analysts in male professional youth football (Chapter 4). Next, it investigated player experiences in a female international youth football squad (Chapter 5). Lastly, it interpreted a professional football coach's career experiences with match analysis in women's football (Chapter 6). An 'overview of studies' is now considered before discussing 'collaborative match analysis', a 'nested theoretical perspective', and 'context-specificity' as the main research implications.

7.1.1 Overview of Studies

Chapter 4 advances our understanding of novice analysts' experiences in professional male youth football by applying a nested theoretical framework (Collins and Cruickshank, 2015) to examine the cultural, motivational, and relational dimensions of their role. This approach offers a nuanced perspective, extending beyond the traditional technical focus of match analysis research. Analysts play a vital role in supporting coaching decisions and shaping learning opportunities (Martin *et al.*, 2021), yet their experiences remain poorly understood. This study investigated how novice analysts acclimate to professional environments and develop their practice. A qualitative multiple-case study was conducted with six analysts working with Under-17 and Under-20 squads across three professional clubs. A multi-method design, incorporating semi-structured interviews and archival data, was analysed using reflexive thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2021a).

Findings revealed that analysts struggled to establish trust and role clarity (Bateman and Jones, 2019), as coaches often viewed them as technical support rather than pedagogical contributors. Analysts relied on soft power tactics (Rylander, 2016) to gain credibility, but their involvement in team feedback remained constrained by coaching micropolitics (Thompson, Potrac and Jones, 2015). The motivational climate influenced how match analysis was applied, with some coaches fostering autonomy-supportive environments that enhanced learning (Duda *et al.*, 2018), while others reinforced controlling structures that risked disengagement. Some analysts were entrusted with leading individual analysis

and feedback, demonstrating their pedagogical capacity, and expanding their influence beyond a purely technical role.

This study shifts the focus from match analysis as a technical process to a social and political one (Nelson *et al.*, 2023), reframing analysts as pedagogical contributors. It highlights the underutilisation of analysts in feedback processes (Andersen, Francis and Bateman, 2022), the need for coach education on integrating match analysis into long-term player development, and the importance of analysts developing interpersonal, tactical and pedagogical knowledge alongside technical skills (Francis, Kyte and Bateman, 2024). While this study provides a transferable model of analyst acclimation, it focused solely on analysts' perspectives, leaving players' experiences of match analysis unexplored. Given that coaching culture, motivational climate, and gendered experiences (Norman, 2016; Denison, Mills and Konoval, 2017; Jowett and Slade, 2021) likely shape not only how analysis is delivered but also how it is received, the next study examined players' experiences of match analysis in female international youth football.

Chapter 5 enhances our understanding of match analysis by examining player experiences within female international youth football. While previous research has explored male footballers' engagement with match analysis (Reeves and Roberts, 2013; Wright *et al.*, 2016), this study applies a nested theoretical framework to examine how cultural, motivational, and relational factors shape female player's experiences (Collins and Cruickshank, 2015). Gender is considered as a contextual factor, acknowledging how

coaching environments and player interactions can differ in female football settings. To investigate these dynamics, a longitudinal ethnographic case study was conducted with nine female international youth players, spanning 24 matches and nine international camps. A multi-method design, incorporating semi-structured interviews, observations, and reflexive thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2021a), captured the nuances of match analysis in this context.

Findings revealed that players universally valued match analysis, recognising its role in enhancing tactical understanding, decision-making, communication, and confidence (Brümmer, 2018; Fernandez-Echeverria *et al.*, 2019). Crucially, match analysis helped players counteract negative memory biases, improving self-evaluation (Middlemas and Harwood, 2018). Engagement evolved over time, influenced by squad hierarchy, prior exposure to match analysis, and coaching behaviours, with some players becoming more active participants as they gained confidence or took on leadership roles. Players preferred concise, structured coach-led sessions with opportunities for interaction but without compulsion, balancing structure, autonomy-support, and psychological safety (Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2021; Jowett *et al.*, 2023). While formal sessions were valuable, players also sought informal discussions with coaches to clarify tactical details, and peer-led video review provided additional learning opportunities. Players disliked public individual criticism (Williams and Manley, 2016), but valued coach rationale (Rylander, 2016), particularly in moments of tactical uncertainty.

This study extends understanding by framing match analysis through an athlete-centred and motivational climate perspective, demonstrating how coaching environments and player-coach interactions shape engagement. Findings reinforce the relevance of gender-responsive coaching (Norman, 2016), with players valuing task-oriented feedback with clear rationale (Longshore and Sachs, 2015; de Haan and Norman, 2019). Technology facilitated self-reflection, but accessibility barriers constrained engagement between international trips (Vinson *et al.*, 2017). Additionally, informal coach-athlete interactions provided critical learning spaces, reinforcing the need for psychologically safe environments. Recognising that coaching philosophy fundamentally shapes practice (Collins, 2021), the final study shifts focus from player experiences to the coach's role in integrating match analysis within their coaching methodology, while navigating pedagogical, environmental, and gender-related constraints.

Chapter 6 improves our understanding of coaching experiences with match analysis in women's football, marking the first study to investigate a coach's evolving engagement with it across their career. Given that coaching philosophy shapes match analysis practices (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2011; Callinan *et al.*, 2023), this study examines how a coach refined their methods, adapting to different contexts while striving for an athlete-centred approach. A single case study was conducted with Noah (pseudonym), a UEFA Pro-License coach with over 10 years of experience in women's football. Data collection included six semi-structured interviews, archival match reports, and video outputs, analysed using reflexive thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2021a).

Findings revealed that Noah's use of match analysis evolved significantly. As an amateur coach, he initially used video review to make sense of matches and challenge perceptual biases. By the time he moved into professional roles, he had developed a structured approach, incorporating tagging systems and tactical reviews, but continued adapting it across different contexts. In youth football, analysis focused on long-term player development, reinforcing game models and progressive learning (Stanway and Boardman, 2020; O'Sullivan *et al.*, 2023).

In senior football, it had a short-term focus, supporting pre-match preparation, opposition analysis, and post-match debriefs (Wright *et al.*, 2013; Carling, 2019). While Noah always prioritised player empowerment, trust, and open feedback (Duda *et al.*, 2018; Jowett *et al.*, 2023), his ability to apply match analysis in line with these values developed over time. He progressed from directive feedback to facilitating open discussions and player-led analysis, fostering greater player ownership (Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2021). His recognition of female players' preference for rationale and discussion further shaped this evolution (Longshore and Sachs, 2015; de Haan and Norman, 2019). However, logistical constraints like multi-role responsibilities posed additional challenges (Sleeman and Ronkainen, 2020). Access to technology, such as cloud-based platforms, played a key role in enhancing engagement (Butterworth, 2023c), but also introduced unexpected issues such as parental over-involvement.

This study illustrates how match analysis evolved across coaching contexts, shaped by philosophy, experience, team needs, and structural constraints. Findings reinforce the importance of embedding match analysis within athlete-centred coaching. Additionally, it highlights key environmental challenges, including resource limitations, technology integration, and the role of key relationships. By providing a longitudinal perspective on expertise development, this research advances understanding of match analysis as a learning tool rather than a control mechanism.

7.1.2 Collaborative Match Analysis

Coaches have control over the match analysis process, often relegating analysts to technical roles and players to passive recipients of feedback (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2012; Andersen, Francis and Bateman, 2022). However, this thesis reveals that analysts, players, and coaches all desire active participation in match analysis. Analysts, often university graduates with robust knowledge in statistical and performance analysis methodologies and coaching pedagogy (Wright *et al.*, 2013; McKenna *et al.*, 2018), expressed a strong desire to contribute meaningfully. However, the ability of analysts to contribute meaningfully was contingent upon establishing trust and credibility within the coaching team (Andersen, Francis and Bateman, 2022; Callinan *et al.*, 2023). Effective cooperation between analysts and coaches is fundamental to successful match analysis (Gibson and Butterworth, 2023), yet newly appointed analysts often faced restricted access to coaching discussions, limiting their influence on tactical decision-making. To overcome this, analysts needed to actively develop rapport and credibility by

demonstrating sport-specific knowledge, match analysis proficiency, and interpersonal skills (Francis *et al.*, 2015; Bateman and Jones, 2019; Nelson *et al.*, 2023), which allowed them to gain influence.

In Chapter 4, some power-sharing was evident, with analysts demonstrating tactical competence through their ability to contextualise performance trends, which led to them negotiating the focus of match analysis and leading individual feedback sessions. Crucially, demonstrating tactical knowledge earned analysts the trust to deliver individual feedback to players, yet cultural norms kept team feedback sessions strictly under the head coach's control. This was particularly important during this period (2016/17 season in Scotland) as it coincided with a critical phase in the evolution of performance analysis, particularly in youth football. During this time, policy changes mandated the inclusion of performance analysts in elite youth academies, resulting in a transitional period where organisations and coaches were still defining the analyst's role within their structures. Analysts faced significant challenges in role clarity, trust-building, and establishing their expertise within coaching hierarchies. Over time, as analysts have taken on greater responsibility for examining performance data, the need for coaches to recognise and trust their expertise in designing and delivering match analysis, including in team feedback meetings, has become increasingly apparent (Andersen, Francis and Bateman, 2022).

In Chapter 6, analysts led team sessions, transitioning from peripheral technicians to valued coaching team members. By this stage, analysts were more embedded in the coaching process, reflecting broader industry trends in performance analysis (Francis, Kyte and Bateman, 2024). This shift has seen analysts not only gain trust but also expand their roles into areas traditionally led by coaches, with specialist tactical analyst roles emerging (e.g. tactical analysts, recruitment analysts, data analysts). Tactical analysts work closely with coaches, focusing on game strategy, opponent scouting, and tactical decision-making. Additionally, some coaches are being trained and deployed as analysts (Andersen, Francis and Bateman, 2022), further integrating match analysis into the broader coaching framework. This evolution suggests a shift towards greater collaboration and knowledge-sharing between analysts and coaches, reinforcing the idea that match analysis is not merely a technical support role but an embedded part of the coaching process (Martin *et al.*, 2021; Martin *et al.*, 2023). This empowerment is crucial as coaches often have gaps in their pedagogical knowledge that analysts can help address. Despite positive interventions showing the influence of systematic coach observation and feedback on coaches' understanding and behaviour (Partington *et al.*, 2015; Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2021), the role of analysts in shaping the pedagogical aspects of match analysis has been underexplored, offering an original perspective in this research.

Players' accounts of match analysis align with athlete-centred practice, though few researchers have made this direct connection. This research supports giving players a

central role in the match analysis process, with agreement from analysts, players, and the coach across all three studies. Engaging players and having them actively participate in their development is critical in sport coaching (Light and Harvey, 2017; Eather *et al.*, 2020), and should apply to match analysis as well. However, this research also highlights that players' ability to engage in match analysis discussions is shaped by their tactical knowledge (McRobert and Williams, 2019; Gleeson and Kelly, 2021). More experienced players, often those with greater match exposure or leadership roles, were more likely to contribute, as they possessed both the game understanding and social capital to confidently share insights (Potrac and Jones, 2009a; Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014). In contrast, less experienced players, particularly those new to match analysis, were often reluctant to speak in group settings, even when given the opportunity (Giske *et al.*, 2017; Jowett *et al.*, 2023). This suggests that for match analysis to be fully collaborative, knowledge development must be considered, ensuring that all players, not just senior ones, have the confidence to engage meaningfully (O'Connor *et al.*, 2022).

While tactical knowledge enabled engagement, players also needed the platform to contribute. In all three studies, players welcomed opportunities to actively discuss their game understanding. In Chapter 5, players emphasised the importance of discussing the game with the coach and having autonomy over when to utilise their voice, extending beyond team meetings. In Chapter 6, the coach highlighted the benefits of developing a shared mental model (Giske *et al.*, 2017; Barraclough *et al.*, 2024) to optimise performance, requiring players to have a significant voice in team meetings and beyond.

Individual meetings, training sessions, and asynchronous online discussions were all means of communication afforded to players to instil a collaborative culture.

Additionally, there was general agreement that players should have significant ownership in the match analysis process. Analysts, coaches, and players agreed on the importance of individual access to match analysis output and constructive conversations with coaches or analysts to enhance game understanding (Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018). Previous research indicates players desire more involvement in the process (Wright *et al.*, 2016) and the importance of coaches providing structure in match analysis (Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014; Gleeson and Kelly, 2021). However, this research provides new insights into the approaches used by coaches and analysts to facilitate players' self-reflection, goal-setting, and individualised training through match analysis. In Chapter 4, players were central to selecting and adjusting KPIs, influencing match analysis discussions and individualised training. In Chapter 5, female international youth players appreciated access to match analysis output and follow-up discussions with coaches, often reviewing team performance in small groups/sub-units. In Chapter 6, individual performance review was integrated into high-performance women's football culture, with players offered significant flexibility and ownership in applying match analysis to their player-led performance reviews. Moreover, players in Chapter 5 and the coach in Chapter 6 noted that match analysis can prompt players to think more deeply about past and future games (Kinnerk *et al.*, 2023). This process, combined with linked training, can

better prepare players for matches and enhance their critical thinking and decision-making during games (Middlemas and Harwood, 2018).

Therefore, match analysis functions at the intersection of reflection on-action and reflection in-action (Stephenson, Cronin and Whitehead, 2020), strengthening the connection between these reflective processes by enhancing players' anticipatory knowledge and decision-making (McRobert and Williams, 2019). Through structured video feedback, players analyse past performances, refine tactical decisions, and adjust action plan profiles (Evans, Whipp and Lay, 2012). These insights inform real-time decision-making, reinforcing how reflection-on-action refines reflection-in-action. For example, in Chapter 5 players credited match analysis with challenging memory biases, sharpening self-evaluation, and reinforcing tactical understanding (Middlemas and Harwood, 2018). Telestration tools, such as onscreen text and laser pens helped direct attention to key cues, supporting in-game adjustments (Jones, Rands and Butterworth, 2020). Similarly, in Chapter 6 a professional women's coach described using iterative match analysis cycles (post-match debriefs → training applications → pre-match tactical meetings) to embed key tactical concepts, fostering faster and more informed decision-making under pressure (Ashford, Abraham and Poolton, 2021a). These findings illustrate that match analysis is more than a retrospective tool; it is an active learning mechanism that integrates reflection processes, shaping perceptual and cognitive skills in high-performance football. This offers a novel perspective, emphasising its pedagogical role in refining player decision-making beyond traditional performance assessment.

Consequently, this thesis offers original insights into the pedagogical integration of match analysis in various high-performance football contexts. Although this research was primarily conducted in women's football, the collaborative approach to match analysis is believed to be broadly applicable. Contextual application varies based on specific performance environments, aligning with the call for coaches to understand their players' needs and provide individualised coaching rather than relying on gender stereotypes (Gosai, Jowett and Rhind, 2022). This requires creating an environment where players feel valued and connected to their coach, thereby facilitating collaboration (Gosai, Jowett and Nascimento-Júnior, 2023). Therefore, a paradigm shift is proposed towards match analysis as a collaborative enterprise developed in partnership by analysts, players, and coaches. How this can be achieved is subsequently discussed from a nested perspective of culture, motivational climate, and the coach-athlete relationship.

7.1.3 Nested Theoretical Perspective

Match analysis is a complex social activity requiring a theoretical framework that embraces this complexity. Collins and Cruickshank (2015) noted that cultural, motivational, and interpersonal perspectives are central to a coach's nested thinking. This thesis adopts this framework and demonstrates its usefulness for future research in match analysis.

Creating a high-performing culture requires explicit purposes, identity, hierarchical structure, and procedural systems to meet team objectives (Cruickshank, 2019). Match analysis significantly contributes to shaping performance culture by reinforcing the team's tactical identity. In Chapter 4, introducing match analysis challenged coaches to articulate their tactical system, leading to some systems lacking tactical nuance. In Chapter 5, pre-match opposition analysis, focused systematically on attacking and defending through the thirds of the pitch, leading to process-driven analysis tightly linked to the tactical plan. In Chapter 6, clubs created an analysis system closely linked to their organisational game model (Ribeiro *et al.*, 2019; O'Sullivan *et al.*, 2023), adapted to suit the age of each squad across their performance pathway. Thus, match analysis is inherently tied to tactical identity and high-performance culture in men's and women's football.

High-performance culture in football also involves pressure to succeed (Carling, 2019), making it a highly contested environment (Booroff, Nelson and Potrac, 2016). Consequently, coaches need to navigate this political environment if they are to establish effective collaboration towards their team objectives. In Chapter 4, coaches were controlling, using legitimate power (Rylander, 2016) and coercion to dominate feedback meetings, thus risking player disengagement or confrontation (Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014; Williams and Manley, 2016; Taylor *et al.*, 2017; Manley and Williams, 2022). Controlling forms of power can yield short-term benefits, but in the long-term they risk negative effects (Mills and Boardley, 2017). Conversely, in Chapters 5 and 6, coaches utilised expert, informational, and referent power, which have been linked to positive long-

term outcomes (Rylander, 2016). For example, providing rationale and fostering interpersonal connections encouraged female players to engage with match analysis. In Chapter 6, this was micropolitical action (Potrac and Jones, 2009b) based on the belief that female players prefer a democratic coaching style (Norman, 2016).

This tendency towards control is further reinforced by the replication of authoritarian approaches that coaches themselves have experienced (Bartholomew, Ntoumanis and Thøgersen-Ntoumani, 2009; Denison, Mills and Konoval, 2017). High-pressure environments reinforce this approach, as expectations and accountability promote control, affecting even experienced coaches (Morbée *et al.*, 2020). Additionally, pedagogical knowledge gaps constrain athlete-centred approaches (Partington *et al.*, 2015; Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2020; Kinnerk *et al.*, 2023). While control can offer short-term benefits like tactical clarity and structured execution, excessive control fosters distrust and performance decline over time (Cruickshank and Collins, 2015a; Mills and Boardley, 2017).

In match analysis, this manifests as player disengagement and passive compliance, limiting tactical learning (Williams and Manley, 2016; Taylor *et al.*, 2017). Thus, controlling coaching approaches risk creating an environment where players comply rather than actively engage with analysis. Coach education is key to addressing this issue, as structured reflection can improve coaches' self-awareness, pedagogical understanding, and match analysis delivery (Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2021). Providing opportunities for

structured self-evaluation may help coaches recognise the long-term drawbacks of excessive control, allowing them to refine their approaches and foster more engaging analysis environments.

Beyond its humanistic value, structured, task-focused dialogue enhances shared mental models, tactical clarity, and decision-making efficiency (Giske *et al.*, 2017; Ribeiro *et al.*, 2019). This process is essential for developing conditional tactical knowledge, knowing when and how to act in dynamic scenarios (Barraclough *et al.*, 2024). Even in tightly controlled environments, allowing some tactical dialogue should reduce ambiguity and increase player buy-in without undermining coach authority (Duda *et al.*, 2018; Jowett *et al.*, 2023). Additionally, reinforcing task-oriented thinking fosters the effort and persistence required for performance optimisation (Kingston, Wixey and Cropley, 2021). Therefore, a collaborative approach to match analysis is particularly valuable in controlling coaching environments.

Coaching culture is also critical when considering the analyst. The vulnerability and role ambiguity experienced by analysts in Chapter 4 and reported elsewhere, contrasted sharply with the trust, responsibility, and role clarity granted to analysts in Chapter 6, elevating them from technicians to valued coaching team members (Huggan, Nelson and Potrac, 2015; Gibson and Butterworth, 2023; Martin *et al.*, 2023). Analysts were allowed to lead sessions and were involved in decision-making processes (Wright *et al.*, 2013; Andersen, Francis and Bateman, 2022; Nelson *et al.*, 2023). Notably, the most

collaborative environment in this thesis was a senior professional women's team. Relatedly, contextual factors like gender, professional status, and club environment appear to mediate the performance culture (Barker-Ruchti *et al.*, 2016) and the application of match analysis, which are discussed later in this chapter.

Motivational climate is also crucial in match analysis due to its influence on the direction and intensity of player effort (Keegan *et al.*, 2011; Appleton and Duda, 2016). Engaging positively with match analysis enhances players' game understanding, decision-making, confidence, and performance (Reeves and Roberts, 2013; Francis and Jones, 2014; Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018). Therefore, empowering coaching (Duda *et al.*, 2018), which includes task-orientation and autonomy, is vital in match analysis. This is supported by its links to enhanced competence and success in elite sport (Gillet *et al.*, 2010; Gillet, Vallerand and Paty, 2013), and that high-performance players prefer autonomy-supportive coaching (Rothwell *et al.*, 2017; Goffena and Horn, 2020). In Chapters 5 and 6, players received detailed task-involved feedback, facilitated by the tactical nuance in the analysis systems used. This approach provided meaningful feedback that augmented the players' self-evaluations of performance (Anderson *et al.*, 2020). In contrast, the goal-focused analysis in Chapter 4 was perceived to be ego-oriented and disempowering due to its direct link to performance outcomes and potential for negative comparisons between players involved in scoring and conceding goals. Chapter 5 also discussed the anxiety and negative affect associated with confronting individual errors in team feedback meetings (Middlemas and

Harwood, 2018). Conversely, in Chapters 4-6, analysts, players, and coach agreed on the importance of providing balanced and team-focused feedback in meetings.

Autonomy was also crucial when evaluating the motivational climates created around match analysis. In Chapter 4, analysts were frustrated with coach-controlled team feedback meetings where male youth players had little opportunity to speak (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2012). This contrasted with the player-led individual analysis detailed in Chapters 4 and 6, where female players had significant voice and ownership over these sessions. This aligns with research that suggests females prefer more autonomy-supportive coaching (Norman, 2016). Additionally, international women's football coaches have learned to listen to players and transition from an autocratic to a democratic coaching style (Lindgren and Barker-Ruchti, 2017). However, the female players discussed in Chapter 6 were mandated to engage in individual match analysis, unlike the opt-in approach seen in Chapter 4. In both settings, players had autonomy over the focus of this analysis. Meanwhile, female international youth players in Chapter 5 could choose whether to ask questions or discuss feedback in team sessions. Conversely, in Chapter 6, a senior professional women's team evolved from opt-in discussions to players co-leading discussions, reflecting the perceived benefits of unpacking game-related problems together. This development occurred as players and staff bonded, and the analysis room became a safe space (Jowett *et al.*, 2023). These findings highlight the importance of autonomy in delivering empowering match analysis, while also demonstrating how its implementation varies depending on the context.

Coach-athlete relationships are crucial in applying match analysis due to their impact on players' motivation, communication, and performance. Relationship quality is determined by closeness, commitment, complementarity, and co-orientation (Yang and Jowett, 2017). In Chapter 4, analysts strategically gained trust and respect from coaches. In Chapter 5, female players needed to trust the coach to engage in meaningful match analysis conversations. In Chapter 6, the coach emphasised that building interpersonal bonds was central to their philosophy and practice, including how they approached match analysis. Therefore, closeness, which involves mutual trust and respect, was essential in establishing high-quality coach-athlete and coach-analyst relationships across this thesis (Santos, Camire and MacDonald, 2018; Li, Gao and Hu, 2021; Bateman and Jones, 2019; Nelson *et al.*, 2023). Closeness fostered meaningful dialogue required to develop role clarity around match analysis processes. This may be particularly important when establishing new relationships and new ways of working, such as introducing match analysis as discussed in Chapters 4 and 6.

Role clarity (Alfano and Collins, 2023) then facilitated complementarity, with key stakeholders cooperating in support of the match analysis process. In Chapters 5 and 6, female players sought out coaches for clarification and tactical discussions, with coaches reciprocally providing clear tactical information and meaningful support. This cooperation was crucial in developing co-orientation, where the coach and player share similar views and understandings regarding their relationship and roles. Across this thesis, match

analysis served as a means of fostering a shared understanding of team tactics, which could be considered an important facet of co-orientation in high-performance football.

In conclusion, this thesis demonstrates the utility of a nested theoretical perspective, incorporating culture, motivational climate, and interpersonal dynamics, to enrich the understanding of applied match analysis. These perspectives highlight the importance of collaborative match analysis and the need to consider the context-specificity required in application.

7.1.3.1 Beyond the Nested Perspective

While the nested theoretical perspective (Collins and Cruickshank, 2015) provided a strong framework for interpreting applied match analysis, this research highlights the need to integrate knowledge development into future iterations. Match analysis has been widely recognised as a tool for improving decision-making and tactical understanding (Reeves and Roberts, 2013; Francis and Jones, 2014; Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018), but few studies have examined how declarative, procedural, and conditional knowledge (McRobert and Williams, 2019) are developed in applied practice. Across the thesis, match analysis facilitated knowledge progression from recognising tactical patterns (declarative), to refining execution (procedural), to applying knowledge dynamically in competitive settings (conditional). In Chapter 5, players developed declarative knowledge by reviewing match footage to understand tactical roles and opposition tendencies, with structured video feedback supporting pattern recognition

(Evans, Whipp and Lay, 2012; Cotterill and Discombe, 2016). In Chapter 6, procedural knowledge was enhanced when match analysis was integrated into training, enabling players to refine decision-making through targeted review and rehearsal (Ramos *et al.*, 2021). Conditional knowledge was most evident when players used match analysis to anticipate game situations and make real-time adaptations, reinforcing the match analysis to training to performance link (Brümmer, 2018).

However, this progression was not uniform across contexts and was shaped by the environment. In athlete-centred cultures (Chapters 5 & 6), match analysis was interactive, with players encouraged to discuss decisions and apply insights through guided questioning (Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2021). The motivational climate also influenced engagement. Task-oriented coaching environments (Duda *et al.*, 2018) promoted deeper reflection, while structured video feedback reinforced iterative learning, progressively refining players' tactical understanding.

Coach-athlete relationships played a key role in knowledge development (Yang and Jowett, 2017), particularly through trust and communication. When coaches actively scaffolded knowledge-building, providing rationale and allowing discussion, players engaged more meaningfully, taking greater ownership of their learning. In Chapter 6, this approach led to players co-leading discussions and applying tactical insights with increased confidence. These findings reinforce that match analysis is not just a technical tool but a socially mediated learning process (Martin *et al.*, 2021). Its effectiveness

depends on how it is structured within a coach's applied environment (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2011). By embedding knowledge development within the nested perspective, the model better captures the mechanisms driving learning, decision-making, and performance outcomes.

Psychological safety also plays a crucial role in shaping how players engage with match analysis, yet it has been largely overlooked in applied performance settings. It determines whether players feel comfortable expressing themselves, asking questions, and offering tactical insights without fear of negative consequences such as criticism, dismissal, or loss of status (Jowett *et al.*, 2023). Match analysis inherently involves reviewing performance, receiving feedback, and discussing tactical decision-making (Carling, 2019). This requires a trust-based environment where players feel secure about contributing. Across this thesis, psychological safety influenced whether players actively participated in match analysis discussions or remained passive. In Chapter 4, controlling coaching styles resulted in closed team environments, where players were hesitant to voice their perspectives due to fear of criticism (Williams and Manley, 2016; Taylor *et al.*, 2017), aligning with research that low psychological safety environments reinforce passive compliance and limit learning (Smittick, Miner and Cunningham, 2019). In contrast, Chapters 5 and 6 demonstrated how fostering open and interactive environments allowed players to contribute meaningfully, drawing important links between engagement, learning, and decision-making quality. In these contexts, match analysis became somewhat player-driven, with them discussing tactical adjustments,

seeking clarification, and refining their in-game decision-making through guided questioning.

The findings further illustrate how psychological safety interacts with cultural, motivational, and relational factors in shaping match analysis outcomes. Coaching culture dictated the extent to which players felt secure engaging in discussions, with hard power tactics (e.g. coercion) leading to players feeling anxious over speaking in team meetings (Rylander, 2016). Similarly, task-oriented environments encouraged players to discuss performance openly, particularly in smaller group settings where the risk of public scrutiny was reduced (Duda *et al.*, 2018). Finally, coach-athlete relationships played a key role, with players more willing to show vulnerability and seek tactical input when they had a close, trusting relationship with their coach (Yang and Jowett, 2017). This supports the broader understanding that psychological safety is a prerequisite for high-quality coach-athlete interactions and effective learning environments (Jowett *et al.*, 2023). By embedding psychological safety within the nested perspective, the model better accounts for the social dynamics that influence match analysis.

Additionally, confidence plays a fundamental role in shaping how players engage with match analysis, influencing their interpretation of feedback, willingness to contribute, and their ability to apply tactical insights in performance settings. Confidence in sport is multifaceted, encompassing sources such as preparation, past performance accomplishments, coaching support, social validation, and self-awareness (Hays *et al.*,

2007). While confidence is often broadly referenced in the performance analysis literature (Reeves and Roberts, 2013; Francis and Jones, 2014; Wright *et al.*, 2016; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018), it is rarely broken down into these distinct sources, which are particularly relevant when considering how players engage with and respond to match analysis.

In this thesis, the players in Chapter 5 drew confidence from multiple sources during the match analysis process. Players were reassured when analysis sessions provided clear tactical guidance, reinforcing their readiness for competition, and as such this preparation was an important source of confidence (Middlemas and Harwood, 2018). Similarly, when players reviewed previous successful performances and received positive feedback from the coach these also had a positive impact on their confidence (Jenkins, Morgan and O'Donoghue, 2007; Francis and Jones, 2014). Players also reported that reviewing video footage helped reframe their performances (McKenna *et al.*, 2018; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018), often shifting initial negative self-evaluations toward a more balanced perspective. This aligns with previous research indicating that female athletes may have lower self-evaluation tendencies compared to their male counterparts (O'Connor *et al.*, 2020; Trbojević and Petrović, 2021), making structured feedback mechanisms crucial in supporting confidence stability. Accordingly, reviewing positive video clips in team meetings enhanced their self-awareness and also provided social validation, which in turn raised their confidence (Wright *et al.*, 2016). Watching previous positive actions was also linked to enhanced self-talk (Zourbanos *et al.*, 2011), with players internalising messages

such as “you can do it” and “go again,” consistent with research on self-regulation and confidence reinforcement (Hays *et al.*, 2009; Thomas *et al.*, 2021).

Confidence in match analysis is shaped by cultural, motivational, and relational factors. Culturally, coaches who used informational power (Rylander, 2016) to provide rationale enhanced players’ understanding and preparedness, strengthening confidence in their tactical awareness. Motivationally, coaches who provided positive feedback created an environment where players felt competent and capable (Duda *et al.*, 2018), reinforcing their confidence. From a relational standpoint, a close, trusting coach-athlete relationship (Yang and Jowett, 2017) can increase a player’s willingness to engage with feedback (Nelson, Potrac and Groom, 2014), fostering cooperative behaviour and confidence. Incorporating confidence within the nested perspective strengthens the model’s ability to capture the psychological and social dynamics that shape match analysis.

7.1.4 Context-Specificity

Coaching contexts are complex and ambiguous (Raabe, Readdy and Zakrajsek, 2017; Collins *et al.*, 2022; Nichol *et al.*, 2023). Thus, calling for collaborative match analysis and a nested theoretical perspective have value, but the effectiveness of match analysis also depends on practitioners carefully considering the influence of context. Given the contexts investigated across this thesis, this section will consider how gender, setting (club vs international), age, and other environmental factors appeared to constrain the application of match analysis.

Chapter 5 and 6 focused on women's football, examining match analysis from the perspective of female international youth players and a coach with extensive experience in women's football. The coach reported that female players were inquisitive, consistently seeking clarity, conversation, and ownership of their development. Similarly, the international players valued understanding tactical decisions and welcomed the coach's provision of rationale, aligning with previous research. They recognised the benefits of match analysis including enhanced game understanding, preparedness, and performance, and thus their preference for balanced feedback. Moreover, players and coach agreed that social bonds were critical, underpinning effective communication. These findings align with research that female players require rationale, discussion, personal relationships, and democratic coaching (Norman, 2016; de Haan and Norman, 2019). This research supports extending the concept of gender-responsive coaching to match analysis.

However, males may also benefit from collaborative match analysis, with differences in how male and female players respond to match analysis influenced by socialisation, contrasting cultures, and gender stereotypes (Gosai, Jowett and Rhind, 2022; Roberts and Quesnel, 2023). While gendered engagement patterns are evident, assuming a universal approach based on gender alone risks oversimplification. Players' responses to match analysis are also shaped by squad hierarchy, prior exposure to analysis, and trust in the coach-athlete relationship, reinforcing the need for an individualised approach

(Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2011). This study demonstrated that while some players thrived under autonomy-supportive environments, others remained passive due to experience level and squad dynamics. This highlights the importance of adaptable engagement strategies that balance structured tactical guidance with opportunities for player-driven reflection. By recognising that players' needs are shaped by a combination of gender, experience, and team role, a more tailored and effective match analysis process can be implemented. This aligns with broader calls to avoid gender stereotyping while ensuring match analysis is player-centred rather than coach-imposed (Gosai, Jowett and Rhind, 2022).

Subtle differences between international and club contexts in women's football were identified across this thesis. In Chapter 5, international players had little time between matches for recovery, post-match debriefs, pre-match opposition analysis, and training sessions. Consequently, post-match opposition analysis was deemphasised. Conversely, the clubs in Chapter 6, particularly the full-time squad, had more time between matches to effect performance change, so they conducted more post-match review and training. Time constraints also impacted the timing of feedback. Study participants across this thesis all preferred delayed feedback and agreed it helps to facilitate a more productive review (McArdle *et al.*, 2010; Wright *et al.*, 2016). However, the international players recognised its infeasibility, with post-match review typically delivered within 12 hours. Pre-match opposition analysis was more critical in the international context due to facing unfamiliar opponents more regularly. Feedback meetings were more structured and

coach-controlled (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2012), compared to some club practices. Players understood the rationale for this approach and welcomed the conciseness and structure, which helped them become familiar with the next opponent and game plan. Although, the coach's voice dominated, players were satisfied that they could ask questions publicly in team meetings or privately afterwards.

Time was also important in facilitating the most extensive analysis meetings, which occurred in a full-time professional women's club in Chapter 6. Here, the match analysis sessions were extended whilst players were engaged in meaningful problem-solving, giving the players significant voice and ownership. However, this approach also meant it was the setting where the most difficult conversations between staff and players were held. The coach linked this approach to developing a shared mental model across the squad (Giske *et al.*, 2017; Barraclough *et al.*, 2024), which required public discussions of both collective and individual performance. Therefore, this required the analysis room to be a psychologically safe space (Jowett *et al.*, 2023) where mastery intentions predominated. The time spent together as a full-time squad promoted the trust required to utilise this approach constructively.

The age of players also influenced the application of match analysis, with post-match analysis predominating as previously reported (Wright *et al.*, 2013; Stanway and Boardman, 2020). In Chapter 6, clubs contextualised their game model and match analysis, adding complexity as players progressed through the development pathway.

Additionally, there was more extensive use of an online cloud-based platform in youth environments than in senior football, given the limited training time. This was perceived to be particularly important for the older teens who did not communicate openly with the coach and peers in match analysis sessions and training but used their voice on their shared online platform. This approach was not seen in Chapter 4, reflecting the organisations' relative inexperience utilising match analysis. In developing elite youth players in women's football, parents became a fourth key stakeholder, especially given the online platform. Coaches found that well-meaning parents tried to coach players at home, leading to conflicting messages from coaches and parents (Horne, Woolf and Green, 2022; Gao *et al.*, 2024). Thus, informing parents on how players should engage with the online platform and their role in supporting this learning was an important lesson learned by the coach in Chapter 6.

Other environmental factors also constrained the application of match analysis. The utilisation of cloud-based platforms discussed in Chapter 6 was not readily available to the clubs in Chapter 4, meaning that alternative, more time-intensive methods were used to share data, taking time away from other analysis tasks. The club utilising smartboard technology in Chapter 6 was considered rich, with the capacity to invest more extensively in their football programme. This also resulted in the coaches having fewer responsibilities and the support of a full-time analyst, thus giving coaches more time to reflect meaningfully upon performance. The coach identified that having time to rewatch games and carefully consider the performance data enhanced his application of match analysis.

In conclusion, effective match analysis requires practitioners to carefully consider multiple factors relating to the complexity of the coaching environment.

7.1.5 Extended Theoretical Framework

This extended theoretical framework (see *Figure 7.1*) builds on the work of Groom, Cushion and Nelson (2011), who developed a grounded theory for understanding the delivery of video-based performance analysis by youth football coaches. Their model identified contextual factors, delivery approaches, and targeted outcomes, emphasising the role of coaching philosophy, social environment, and player engagement. While this provided a valuable foundation, it primarily framed match analysis as a coach-led process, focusing on how analysis is delivered rather than how players actively engage with and benefit from it.

Building on this, the present framework extends beyond coaching delivery to offer a holistic, athlete-centred perspective on match analysis. It identifies key factors that influence player engagement and the psychosocial dynamics shaping its effectiveness:

- **Contextual Factors:** define the structural conditions shaping match analysis implementation, including the level of play, technological access, and logistical constraints.

- Environmental Factors: capture the immediate match analysis climate, incorporating team culture, motivational environment, relationships between analysts, coaches, and players, and the presence of psychological safety.
- Athlete Factors: recognise individual differences, such as experience levels, game knowledge, confidence, and micropolitical position within the squad, which influence how players interpret and apply analysis insights.
- Outcomes: represent the intended effects of effective match analysis, including enhanced tactical knowledge, improved decision-making, greater confidence, and performance development.

By integrating these dimensions, this framework broadens the scope of match analysis, moving beyond coach-led instruction to consider the interplay between contextual, player, and environmental factors. It reinforces the need for tailored, psychologically safe, and interactive analysis settings that optimise learning, confidence, and performance, offering a new conceptualisation of match analysis for both research and applied practice.

Figure 7.1: An Extended Theoretical Framework for Athlete-Centred Match Analysis

7.2 Practical Recommendations

In this section, practical recommendations for analysts, players, and coaches are formulated based on the thesis findings to enhance the application of match analysis.

7.2.1 Analysts: From Technical Support to Strategic Influence

Analysts should develop micropolitical literacy to navigate the complexities of high-performance environments (Gibson and Butterworth, 2023). This requires immersion in the environment, observation, reflection, continued professional development, and

mentorship (Downham and Cushion, 2022; Cooke, Allen and Paradis, 2023). Building effective relationships based on trust and respect with head coaches and support staff is crucial for securing the responsibility, collaboration, and inclusion in decision-making required to effectively execute their role (Huggan, Nelson and Potrac, 2015; Bateman and Jones, 2019; Nelson *et al.*, 2023). However, simply having access to decision-makers is insufficient, analysts must actively demonstrate competence in performance analysis methodologies, tactical literacy, and pedagogy, as these underpin key aspects of the analyst's role (Martin *et al.*, 2021; Callinan *et al.*, 2023; Francis, Kyte and Bateman, 2024).

Building on the findings of this thesis, analysts' career progression can be conceptualised in three stages: early-career, mid-career, and senior analyst development. This structure extends beyond existing frameworks of analyst expertise (Martin *et al.*, 2021; Martin *et al.*, 2023) by explicitly considering analyst integration, pedagogical strategies, and impact measurement as important developmental landmarks.

7.2.1.1 Early-Career Analysts: Developing Technical and Tactical Foundations

Early-career analysts often occupy peripheral roles, primarily providing technical support and data processing. At this stage, mastery of performance analysis software, data collection, and reliability testing is essential (McKenna *et al.*, 2018). However, technical proficiency alone is insufficient for career progression. To transition beyond a purely technical role, analysts must actively build trust and credibility within the coaching environment. Analysts can establish trust by delivering accurate and reliable data

consistently, demonstrating an understanding of team tactics and coaching philosophy, and anticipating the coach's needs, such as preparing relevant clips before they are requested or adapting feedback formats to suit the coach's preferences (Nelson *et al.*, 2023). Additionally, observing team meetings, engaging in informal discussions with coaching staff, and seeking feedback on their work signals a willingness to learn and align with the team's objectives.

Demonstrating competence, both in technical expertise and in understanding the tactical and strategic elements of the sport, is critical to gaining acceptance and influence (Nelson *et al.*, 2023). Analysts who fail to establish their value risk being overlooked in key decision-making processes, limiting their impact on team performance. Given that novice practitioners can struggle to establish credibility within coaching teams (Huggan, Nelson and Potrac, 2015; McKenna *et al.*, 2018), early-career training and education should explicitly address navigating power dynamics, communicating insights effectively, and developing effective coach-analyst relationships (Bateman and Jones, 2019). Developing these capacities are essential if the analyst is to demonstrate the value and transition into more player-facing and influential roles.

To facilitate this progression, clubs should develop induction and support processes that familiarise analysts with the realities of practice, including club philosophies, tactical frameworks, the coaching process, and feedback protocols (McKenna *et al.*, 2018). Mentorship, whether formal or informal, is valuable, as early-career analysts benefit from

guidance from experienced analysts and coaches (Bateman and Jones, 2019). Without proactive engagement in these learning opportunities, analysts may struggle to develop the knowledge and skills, professional behaviours, and contextual awareness to progress beyond technical support roles (Martin *et al.*, 2021), limiting their ability to impact team performance.

7.2.1.2 *Mid-Career Analysts: Pedagogy and Impacting Analysis Processes*

Building upon technical and relational foundations, mid-career analysts must develop pedagogical expertise and tactical fluency to meaningfully contribute to performance environments. Their role extends beyond data provision to contributing to and potentially leading player feedback meetings with credibility, ensuring tactical insights are trusted by both coaches and players (McKenna *et al.*, 2018; Andersen, Francis and Bateman, 2022). Analysts should actively contribute to the shaping of KPI selection, feedback structures, and training design, influencing team selection and match strategies (Wright *et al.*, 2013; Carling, 2019). This stage also requires analysts to refine their ability to use statistics and track data, and to be proficient in integrating statistic with video analysis in match evaluation. To lead effective player feedback, analysts must facilitate player engagement rather than simply present data (Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2021), using athlete-centred pedagogy (Duda *et al.*, 2018) and effective questioning strategies to enhance tactical understanding (Cope *et al.*, 2016; O'Connor *et al.*, 2022). This requires mastery of video feedback techniques, awareness of cognitive load management, and the ability to guide players through decision-making scenarios. Their credibility is built through tactical

knowledge, communication skills, and trust from both coaching staff and players (Nelson *et al.*, 2023), allowing them to directly impact match preparation and post-match evaluation.

At this stage, analysts can support the development of others, mentor early-career analysts and support coaches in refining their own match analysis processes (Bateman and Jones, 2019). Professional development through peer-led reflective conversations, workshops, or postgraduate education enables analysts to refine pedagogical and tactical expertise (Mulvenna and Viner, 2024). This should help mid-career analysts to assess the impact of their work, which is an important milestone on the way to becoming a senior analyst. For example, evaluating how well players engage with match analysis, whether insights are successfully integrated into training, and how analysis contributes to improved decision-making on the field allows analysts to showcase their effectiveness as learning facilitators. Additionally, to remain effective, analysts must continually evaluate new methods and technologies, ensuring their practice evolves with AI-driven tools, predictive modelling, and automation in performance analysis workflows (Butterworth, 2023c). By staying at the forefront of innovation, they strengthen their role within high-performance environments.

7.2.1.3 Senior Analysts: Shaping Performance Strategy and Institutional Change

Senior analysts transition from operational delivery to strategic leadership, shaping long-term performance planning and ensuring analysis is embedded within club-wide tactical

models and decision-making structures (O'Sullivan *et al.*, 2023). Their role extends beyond informing coaching strategies to influencing broader organisational priorities, including analysis methodologies, departmental workflows, and resource allocation (Martin *et al.*, 2023). They oversee performance analysis provision, managing staff, budgets, and infrastructure, ensuring efficiency and alignment with club philosophies and performance objectives (Andersen, Francis and Bateman, 2022). This includes making strategic decisions on technology acquisition, developing in-house analysis tools, and refining data systems to optimise efficiency and insight generation (Carling, 2019).

A defining feature of senior analysts is their ability to bridge the gap between data and coaching strategy, translating analysis into meaningful coaching interventions while advocating for the role of match analysis within the wider performance team. Political acumen is critical, as they must navigate multi-disciplinary environments, negotiate competing interests, and secure buy-in from senior stakeholders to integrate analysis effectively into performance planning (Gibson and Butterworth, 2023). Mentorship and succession planning are key responsibilities at this level, with senior analysts ensuring junior staff develop the necessary tactical knowledge, analytical skills, and professional behaviours to progress within the field (Bateman and Jones, 2019). Their own development remains crucial, requiring continued engagement with professional networks, leadership training, and applied statistical methodologies to strengthen their strategic influence. Reflective practice, combined with ongoing research into emerging

technologies, allows them to maintain a forward-thinking approach, reinforcing their value within elite sport environments.

7.2.1.4 Enhancing Analyst Education: Moving Beyond Technical Proficiency

Despite the increasing complexity of applied performance analysis, most analyst education programs remain overly focused on technical skill acquisition (Martin *et al.*, 2023). Given that match analysis is embedded within cultural, motivational, and interpersonal dynamics, education should extend beyond data collection and video analysis to include pedagogical strategies, psychology, and interpersonal and intrapersonal skills (McKenna *et al.*, 2018; Martin *et al.*, 2021).

Informed by the nested perspective established in Chapter 4, this thesis suggests that future analyst training should integrate coursework on understanding coaching philosophies and team culture, facilitating player learning and decision-making through match analysis, building relationships and navigating micropolitical environments, and strategic communication to influence coaching decisions. By embedding these elements, analysts will be better equipped for the realities of applied practice, ensuring they function as active contributors rather than technical support staff. Thus, analyst development should be seen as a progressive journey, from technical proficiency to strategic leadership, with education and training reflecting this trajectory. Those who successfully integrate pedagogical and tactical expertise into coaching structures will not only enhance

their career prospects but also elevate the role of match analysis in high-performance sport.

7.2.2 Players: Enhancing Engagement with Match Analysis

Match analysis is a critical tool for improving players' understanding, decision-making, confidence, and performance (Wright *et al.*, 2016; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018). However, its effectiveness depends on how it is delivered and received. Coaches must create an environment that fosters engagement, ensuring match analysis aligns with players' developmental needs, as active learning enhances the effectiveness of this process (Light and Harvey, 2017; Eather *et al.*, 2020). This section outlines the key principles for delivering match analysis in an athlete-centred way, before providing specific recommendations for youth and senior players, considering factors such as psychological safety, scaffolding learning, and the integration of digital platforms. Additionally, different contexts, such as professional vs amateur settings and club vs international environments, are considered.

7.2.2.1 Creating an Active Learning Culture

A fundamental prerequisite for effective player engagement with match analysis is the creation of an active learning culture. The responsibility for setting this culture lies primarily with the coaching staff, who must foster an environment where players feel psychologically safe, valued, and empowered to engage with the performance analysis

process (Duda *et al.*, 2018; Jowett *et al.*, 2023). The TARGET framework (Kingston, Wixey and Morgan, 2020) offers a structured approach to developing this environment: match analysis feedback should be task-oriented (challenging but realistic), provide players with authority (giving players some control in discussions), recognise effort and improvement rather than outcomes in evaluating and rewarding players, structure group feedback to limit ego-orientation, and ensure sufficient time is allocated for reflection and discussion. Implementing these principles allows match analysis to be embedded in a mastery-oriented climate, which supports motivation and learning (Kingston, Wixey and Morgan, 2020). A key challenge in match analysis is that public review can create anxiety, particularly when mistakes are highlighted in front of peers. Research suggests that some players are more likely to disengage when feedback feels highly evaluative or judgmental (Williams and Manley, 2016; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018). To reinforce a mastery-oriented climate, coaches should structure feedback to prevent unnecessary anxiety. Strategies such as using smaller sub-groups for analysis, allowing private review before discussion, and balancing criticism with positive reinforcement can help create a psychologically safe environment.

Psychological safety is another critical factor that influences players' willingness to engage in match analysis. Ensuring that players feel comfortable voicing opinions, reflecting openly, and making mistakes without fear of judgment is essential (Taylor *et al.*, 2017; Jowett *et al.*, 2023). Psychological safety can be broken down into three key components: trust and coach-athlete relationships, a supportive environment for framing

feedback, and clear communication regarding role expectations. Trust between players and coaches is crucial for encouraging engagement with match analysis, and close, supportive relationships have been shown to enhance motivation and learning (Li, Gao and Hu, 2021; Solstad *et al.*, 2022). A strong foundation of closeness and mutual respect (Yang and Jowett, 2017) ensures that players feel secure in discussing their performances honestly. Coaches must also frame feedback as collaborative learning rather than critique, reinforcing the notion that match analysis serves as an opportunity for development rather than punishment (Williams and Manley, 2016; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018; Gleeson and Kelly, 2021). Furthermore, players must clearly understand their role in the PA process, ensuring co-oriented thinking, where both coach and player align on tactical expectations, feedback interpretation, and performance objectives (Filho and Tenenbaum, 2020).

Subsequently, coaches should actively facilitate dialogue, encourage players to set learning objectives, and frame mistakes as opportunities for tactical improvement. An example of good practice is using video clips to showcase both effective and ineffective decision-making, allowing players to critique scenarios without personalising mistakes. Coaches can also use pre-session briefings to set expectations for analysis, ensuring clarity on the purpose and learning objectives of the session.

7.2.2.2 *Delivering Match Analysis to Youth and Less Experienced Players*

Young or inexperienced players require a structured introduction to match analysis, as they may not initially possess the skills to critically engage with video feedback. Early-stage delivery should focus on scaffolding learning (Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2021; O'Connor *et al.*, 2022; Kinnerk *et al.*, 2023), ensuring players understand what match analysis is, how it is used, and why it is beneficial. This can be achieved through a player induction process, where coaches gradually introduce video analysis by first reviewing external examples rather than immediately focusing on the players' own performances. One effective strategy is to begin with pre-recorded examples, such as first-team footage, to introduce tactical principles. Players can then be guided through reflective exercises on others' performances before transitioning to self-analysis. This can help to reduce the self-consciousness youth players experience when reviewing their own performances, and to increase objectivity (Middlemas and Harwood, 2018).

Additionally, linking video review to training cycles reinforces learning by ensuring that players see the direct application of feedback in their development (Brümmer, 2018; Macquet and Stanton, 2021; Ashford *et al.*, 2022). Structured group sessions should also be interactive and discussion-based, encouraging players to engage in problem-solving exercises and tactical scenario analysis (Francis and Jones, 2014; Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018). Group-based video sessions should maintain a constructive tone, highlighting strengths while also outlining areas for improvement (Wright *et al.*, 2016). Coaches should also use delayed feedback, allowing players time to reflect on their

performances before engaging in team review meetings. This enhances self-awareness and helps mitigate impulsive emotional reactions to criticism (McArdle *et al.*, 2010; McKenna *et al.*, 2018).

When integrating digital platforms for youth match analysis, progressive implementation is crucial (Vinson *et al.*, 2017). Players should first develop face-to-face analysis skills before engaging in self-review online. A guided transition to online analysis should include providing structured self-reflection tasks. For instance, young players should receive specific objectives when reviewing footage, such as identifying one moment where they demonstrated a tactical principle. Monitoring engagement is also important. Coaches should track how effectively players engage with video tasks to ensure self-analysis remains beneficial rather than overwhelming. Additionally, managing parental involvement is important (Horne, Woolf and Green, 2022), as well-intentioned but misinformed feedback can undermine the coaching process. Parents should be educated on how to support their child's engagement with match analysis without imposing external pressures or offering conflicting advice. Providing structured guidance on how parents can reinforce learning, such as asking reflective questions rather than critiquing performance, ensures that match analysis remains a positive developmental tool rather than a source of stress (Gao *et al.*, 2024). Clubs should establish clear guidelines on parental engagement, ensuring they facilitate rather than hinder their child's development.

7.2.2.3 *Delivering Match Analysis to Senior and More Experienced Players*

In senior squads, match analysis should shift towards greater player ownership and peer collaboration. Players should be encouraged to critique and discuss match footage collectively, reinforcing tactical awareness and decision-making responsibilities (McRobert and Williams, 2019). Senior players can take on leadership roles in analysis meetings, engaging in peer-to-peer feedback while still following a structured framework (Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018). However, for senior players to engage effectively in match analysis and contribute meaningfully to discussions, they must also navigate the micropolitical landscapes evident in football. The effectiveness of peer and coach-led feedback is not only shaped by tactical knowledge but also by the social and power dynamics within a team (Potrac and Jones, 2009b). Understanding when to challenge, accept, or negotiate tactical decisions can influence how players engage with feedback, particularly in interactions with coaches and senior teammates. Developing awareness of these dynamics can empower players to use match analysis as a tool for both personal development and team contribution.

At the same time, coaches must ensure that discussions remain constructive and inclusive, preventing dominant voices from overpowering quieter team members (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2012). Varying feedback formats can help achieve this by creating a more psychologically safe environment, allowing players to engage in settings that suit their confidence levels. Therefore, coaches should incorporate hybrid team, sub-unit, and individual analysis sessions (Wright *et al.*, 2013; Francis and Jones, 2014; Middlemas,

Croft and Watson, 2018). Whole-team meetings ensure alignment with the team's tactical principles (Filho, Tenenbaum and Yang, 2015), but they may discourage some players from speaking openly. Smaller groups offer a more supportive space for quieter players to contribute while also providing more role-specific insights (Hughes *et al.*, 2012; Barraclough *et al.*, 2024). Individual sessions allow for deeper, personalised feedback, helping players engage with match analysis in a way that best supports their development. Encouraging collaborative discussions across all these formats (McKenna *et al.*, 2018; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018) can further enhance engagement. Allowing players to propose tactical adjustments based on their in-game experiences and video observations is another way to engage them in an autonomy-supportive manner, which high-performance athletes prefer (Rothwell *et al.*, 2017; Goffena and Horn, 2020). To support this process, educating players about the team's game model ensures they have the necessary tactical knowledge to engage in meaningful discussions (Ribeiro *et al.*, 2019; O'Sullivan *et al.*, 2023).

For senior players, digital platforms should be optimised for self-directed learning. Unlike younger players, experienced players should be empowered to manage their own analysis. More experienced players are better able to engage in self-analysis, identify tactical insights, and connect their decisions to broader game contexts (Gleeson and Kelly, 2021). Therefore, while the capacity for meaningful reflection on individual clips varies among players, it develops with experience. Best practices include providing access to pre-tagged clips aligned with individual player objectives, allowing players to

focus on performance aspects relevant to their development. Encouraging peer review and discussion through shared video platforms, where teammates can annotate and provide constructive feedback on each other's clips, is also beneficial. Ideally, online analysis should supplement in-person discussions rather than replace them, ensuring face-to-face engagement remains the primary mode of interaction (Vinson *et al.*, 2017).

7.2.2.4 *Considerations for Different Contexts*

Match analysis practices vary significantly depending on the coaching environment (Wright, Atkins and Jones, 2012; Wright *et al.*, 2013; Nicholls *et al.*, 2018; Nicholls *et al.*, 2019). In professional settings, players typically have greater access to technology, full-time analysts, and structured feedback sessions, allowing for more in-depth, data-driven insights. However, the increased volume of data and analysis can lead to information overload and contribute to a disempowering coaching culture (Williams and Manley, 2016; Manley and Williams, 2022), potentially overwhelming players and reducing the effectiveness of key tactical messages. Coaches must carefully curate analysis to ensure clarity and retention (McKenna *et al.*, 2018). Amateur teams, by contrast, may have limited technological resources and time constraints, requiring coaches to be more selective in their use of video and focus on key learning points.

Similarly, club and international settings present different challenges. In clubs, coaches work with players consistently over a season, allowing for progressive integration of match analysis into training cycles (Brümmer, 2018; Middlemas, Croft and Watson, 2018).

In contrast, international squads have limited preparation time, meaning match analysis must be efficient and focused on immediate tactical application rather than long(er)-term development. Meanwhile, coaches in amateur or resource-limited environments must be creative in their approach. For example, where dedicated online platforms are unavailable, coaches can utilise social media platforms (e.g., WhatsApp, Facebook, YouTube) to share video clips and tactical insights. Additionally, where facilities are sub-optimal, match analysis sessions may need to be delivered in dressing rooms using portable projectors. While these conditions present challenges, the core principles of structured, athlete-centred feedback can still be applied effectively.

7.2.2.5 Integrating Match Analysis into Training

Match analysis should not exist in isolation but be embedded within training to help players apply insights in context-specific decision-making scenarios (Ashford, Abraham and Poolton, 2021c; Macquet and Stanton, 2021). Its effectiveness is maximised when feedback aligns with different stages of knowledge acquisition (declarative, procedural, and conditional knowledge), which shape player learning and tactical application (McRobert and Williams, 2019). Structuring training around this progression helps players move from passive analysis to active decision-making, reinforcing tactical understanding and adaptability. In the early stages of learning, players develop declarative knowledge, focusing on understanding what is happening in a game and why certain tactical principles are applied (Ribeiro *et al.*, 2019; O'Sullivan *et al.*, 2023). Structured video analysis sessions allow coaches to explain team shape, movement patterns, opposition

tendencies, and tactical expectations. Players should be encouraged to verbalise their understanding of positional roles and team strategies, reinforcing conceptual knowledge before applying it on the pitch (Francis and Jones, 2014; Brümmer, 2018). This is particularly important for younger or less experienced players, who benefit from scaffolded tactical learning.

As players progress, they transition from understanding tactics to practising and refining tactical actions in structured training environments. At this stage, match analysis should inform position-specific drills, small-sided tactical games, and structured rehearsals, enabling players to move beyond recognising tactical concepts to executing them in controlled, coach-led scenarios. These exercises provide a predictable environment where players can rehearse tactical patterns, reinforcing decision-making before applying them in live match conditions (Ramos *et al.*, 2021; Ashford *et al.*, 2022). Video review during or immediately after training drills aims to refine positioning, movement timing, and decision-making. At this stage, coaches should provide targeted, actionable feedback that links match analysis insights with on-field execution, ensuring training directly reinforces tactical learning.

In the final stage, players develop conditional knowledge, where they must not only execute tactical patterns but also adapt their decisions based on live match contexts. Match analysis should inform modified game scenarios, tactical training games, and match-based problem-solving drills (Macquet and Stanton, 2021). The aim is to transition

from structured rehearsal to adaptive, in-game decision-making, ensuring players can apply insights under pressure (Ashford *et al.*, 2022). Coaches can pause training to link real-time decisions with previously analysed footage, reinforcing reflection-in-action and reflection-on-action (Ashford, Abraham and Poolton, 2021a). This process helps players interpret game cues, adjust to opposition strategies, and make independent tactical decisions in competitive environments. By aligning match analysis with progressive learning stages, training shifts from pattern recognition to execution and adaptation in high-pressure situations. This ensures match analysis is not just a reflective tool but an active driver of player development, fostering autonomy, confidence, and tactical adaptability in real-world match scenarios.

7.2.3 Coaches: Developing Match Analysis Expertise

For match analysis to be fully embedded within coaching practice, coaches must develop a structured, informed, and iterative understanding of its application. While performance analysis is widely recognised as a key component of elite football (Carling, 2019), many coaches gain their expertise informally through trial and error, mentorship, and self-reflection (Cushion, Stodter and Clarke, 2022; Ferner, Ross-Stewart and Dueck, 2023). Subsequently, the use of match analysis in coaching varies considerably, shaped by experience, resource availability, and organisational culture (McKenna *et al.*, 2018). Some teams embed match analysis within their tactical and developmental frameworks (Stanway and Boardman, 2020), others apply it in a more limited capacity, primarily for post-match review, highlighting key incidents, and reinforcing coaching messages (Wright

et al., 2013; Nicholls *et al.*, 2019). To maximise its impact, coaches should refine their analytical literacy, integrate it effectively into their pedagogical process, and foster strong coach-analyst relationships.

7.2.3.1 *Building Analytical Literacy*

Early-career coaches often lack formal education on match analysis, which can lead to underutilisation or misapplication (Andersen, Francis and Bateman, 2022; Martin *et al.*, 2023). This stage requires a combination of structured learning and informal or formal mentoring to develop a clear understanding of match analysis and build confidence in its application. Exposure to video review early in their development helps coaches recognise what they initially miss in live performance, reinforcing the value of systematic analysis. As coaches become familiar with match analysis, they engage in progressive sense-making. Initially, they may review footage chronologically, mirroring live observations, before transitioning to tagged footage that allows them to identify patterns more efficiently (e.g., penalty box entries, pressing triggers, or set-piece routines). Over time, this enables the development of declarative knowledge (what teams do), procedural knowledge (how they do it), and conditional knowledge (when they adapt their tactics) (McRobert and Williams, 2019). Learning to navigate analysis software effectively is an important technical skill, but true expertise develops when coaches can extract meaning from the data and apply it to decision-making in training and competition. This learning process can be accelerated through formal match analysis training courses and mentorship from experienced analysts.

7.2.3.2 *Developing Pedagogical Awareness*

Integrating match analysis effectively into coaching practice is not instinctive; it is a pedagogical skill that develops through experience, structured reflection, and exposure to good practice. Much like novice teachers refining their instructional techniques, early-career coaches often prioritise detail over clarity, leading to information overload rather than targeted learning (McKenna *et al.*, 2018).

A common early challenge is treating match analysis as a review of events rather than a tool for learning. Coaches may initially present chronological footage, focusing on thoroughness rather than key tactical principles. However, with experience and feedback, they learn to curate their analysis, filtering key insights to highlight patterns, themes, and decision-making moments (Sarmiento *et al.*, 2013; Hewitt, Greenham and Norton, 2016; Sousa *et al.*, 2021). Another area of progression is shifting from instruction to interpretation. Novice coaches often rely on directive feedback, explaining what happened and what should have been done differently (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2012). As they develop, coaches may prioritise selective feedback, focusing on guided questioning and self-assessment rather than merely providing answers (Middlemas and Harwood, 2018; Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2021). Learning to pitch feedback at the appropriate level, like balancing corrections with actionable insights (Raya-Castellano *et*

al., 2020), is a critical coaching skill that can evolve over time with experience and reflection (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2011; McKenna *et al.*, 2018).

However, to fully maximise the impact of match analysis, high-level sporting knowledge alone is insufficient, coaches also require deep pedagogical expertise (Ashford *et al.*, 2024; Moran, Taylor and Macnamara, 2024). Effective coaching is not just about understanding tactics but about facilitating learning, fostering player autonomy, and structuring feedback in a way that enhances decision-making (Côté and Gilbert, 2009). Many traditional coaching courses only superficially address match analysis and pedagogy, focusing primarily on technical and tactical knowledge. As a result, coaches may struggle to translate match analysis insights into meaningful player learning experiences. To bridge this gap, coaches should seek learning opportunities beyond national governing body qualifications. University courses in sports coaching and performance analysis (Francis, Kyte and Bateman, 2024), mentorship from experienced coaches and analysts (Downham and Cushion, 2022; Cooke, Allen and Paradis, 2023), and collaboration with sports scientists and learning specialists can provide a deeper understanding (Raya-Castellano and Uriondo, 2015; Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2021). Without this pedagogical foundation, match analysis risks becoming a passive exercise rather than an active tool for player development.

7.2.3.3 Strengthening the Coach-Analyst Relationship

Despite the increasing sophistication of performance analysis in elite sport, the coach-analyst relationship often remains underutilised (Andersen, Francis and Bateman, 2022). Analysts are often perceived as technical support staff rather than key contributors to tactical planning and player development, which limits their impact (Bateman and Jones, 2019). However, when this partnership is fully leveraged, analysts provide far more than just data, they offer tactical insights, developmental tracking, and pedagogical expertise that can transform a coach's ability to prepare, adapt, and evolve (Martin *et al.*, 2021). To move beyond basic match review, coaches must actively engage analysts as strategic collaborators who not only produce information but can also help structure its delivery to enhance player understanding and engagement (Martin *et al.*, 2023). A well-integrated coach-analyst partnership can enhance tactical analysis by helping coaches go beyond event-based tagging, such as passes and tackles, to identify deeper patterns such as positional play, pressing intensity, transition efficiency, and defensive compactness (McRobert, Fernández-Navarro and Seth, 2023). These insights can help to refine game models and support opposition scouting (Barraclough *et al.*, 2024). Analysts also play a critical role in long-term player development by tracking individual and team performance trends over multiple seasons, identifying developmental patterns that may not be apparent from isolated match reviews (Raya-Castellano *et al.*, 2021). This enables targeted improvements in technical and tactical areas, ensuring players progress is optimised.

Beyond video analysis, analysts can integrate GPS data, workload monitoring, and biomechanical tracking, offering a more holistic view of player performance (Carling and Datson, 2022). Emerging technologies and methods may also speed up analysis workflows, helping coaches make quicker, data-driven decisions. Match preparation and in-game adjustments also benefit from analyst involvement. Analysts are instrumental in preparing detailed opposition reports, highlighting tactical weaknesses and key threats. Some teams now use live coding to provide real-time insights to coaching staff, allowing for more effective in-game tactical adjustments (Nicholls *et al.*, 2019). However, the role of the analyst extends beyond tactical and physical insights. A skilled analyst can act as a pedagogical bridge, supporting coaches in refining how match analysis is communicated to players (Martin *et al.*, 2023). This includes structuring analysis sessions in a way that avoids information overload, designing interactive video reviews that engage players in tactical problem-solving, and ensuring that insights are delivered in a way that aligns with how players learn best (Groom, Cushion and Nelson, 2011). Rather than simply presenting statistics, analysts can support coaches in fostering reflective learning environments where players take ownership of their development, using video and data as tools for self-assessment and tactical awareness.

To maximise this relationship, coaches should fully integrate analysts into tactical meetings, training sessions, and match debriefs, ensuring their insights inform real-time decision-making rather than simply being post-match reports. Developing a shared tactical and pedagogical language between coaches, analysts, and players is crucial, as

without its valuable insights risk being lost in translation (Barracough *et al.*, 2024). Analysts must be seen as a trusted member of the coaching team (Nelson *et al.*, 2023), helping bridge the gap between data and tactical execution while also enhancing the learning process. By fostering a closer collaboration, teams can shift from passive review to proactive performance enhancement, ensuring match analysis not only documents past events but actively shapes future success (Callinan *et al.*, 2023). The modern analyst is not just a data provider, they are an essential figure in high-performance sport, capable of delivering genuine competitive advantages by helping coaches and players extract meaningful learning from performance analysis.

7.3 Limitations

While the research paradigm and design were relevant, they imposed limitations. Interpretivism and constructivism (Gray, 2021) facilitated the exploration of applied match analysis contexts, but subjectivity is inherent in this approach. Despite efforts to mitigate bias (Cushion, 2014), the researcher's perspective inevitably influenced the work. Case study designs provided detailed insights into cultural norms and participants' lived experiences (Willig, 2022), but they constrain the generalisability of the findings. However, readers can derive valuable insights through naturalistic and analytical generalisations (Sparkes and Smith, 2014; Smith, 2018) and user generalisability (Ahumada, Galdames and Clarke, 2016). The use of interviews was another limitation. While they allowed for deeper insights, the recollections captured were subject to memory bias (Smith and Sparkes, 2020). To mitigate this, iterative and probing questions fostered

repetition and elaboration, ensuring participant memories were anchored to specific events. Participant triangulation was also utilised to explore commonalities and discrepancies between experiential accounts (Korstjens and Moser, 2018). Additionally, archival data and observations helped generate a realistic picture of practices, experiences and perceptions (Sparkes and Smith, 2014; Silverman, 2020). The theoretical perspective applied was another limiting factor. Considering culture, motivational climate, and the coach-athlete relationship tied the research to a coach's nested thinking (Collins and Cruickshank, 2015), ensuring the research was novel and practically relevant. However, this approach limited the attention each theoretical perspective received, impacting the analysis. Moreover, coaching science research extends beyond these theories, offering alternative interpretations of match analysis.

7.4 Future Research

Future research should prioritise conducting case studies across diverse contexts to further understand the contextual factors influencing applied match analysis. Valuable contributions could include autoethnographic accounts (Preston and Fraser-Thomas, 2018). Research into how match analysis dyads develop and maintain their collaborative practices would be particularly useful, similar to research in sport coaching (Mueller, Ruiz and Chroni, 2018). Additionally, there is merit in validating the broader pedagogical assertions made in this thesis, extending survey research already conducted on match analysis (e.g., Wright, Atkins and Jones, 2012; Nicholls *et al.*, 2018). As the efficacy of match analysis has typically been evaluated indirectly through stakeholder perceptions

(Wright *et al.*, 2016; McKenna *et al.*, 2018; Middlemas and Harwood, 2018), alternative assessment is required. In particular, participatory action research (Ollis and Sproule, 2007; Castro and Morgan, 2023), or think-aloud methods (Quick and Lyle, 2024) would be ecologically valid ways of evaluating the development of game understanding, decision-making, and shared mental models. Furthermore, given the lack of theoretical interpretations of match analysis, there is scope for extending this further. For example, servant, transformational, and tripartite models of leadership would generate useful interpretations related to the role match analysis plays in performance management processes (Arthur, Wagstaff and Hardy, 2016; Macquet and Stanton, 2021; Crossan, Copeland and Barnhart, 2023). Investigating these areas would make substantial contributions to the understanding of applied match analysis.

7.5 Personal Reflections

My first role as a performance analyst involved part-time work for a full-time team in the second tier of Scottish men's football, where performance analysis had not been utilised before. Analysis sessions were lengthy, coach-led, and focused on performance. Attempts were made to provide balanced feedback, but this varied depending on results. While most players appreciated the detailed information and opportunities for reflection, some disliked the delivery style. Despite having rapport with the coach, my influence was limited as I couldn't regularly access the training environment. Nonetheless, these early experiences underscored the significance of power dynamics, motivation, and relationships in the application of match analysis. Consequently, my early experiences

and the lack of applied literature on match analysis served as the inspiration for this thesis. While the scarcity of practical accounts to guide this practice led to investigating neophyte analyst experiences in Chapter 4.

I then transitioned to working with a part-time team in the top tier of Scottish women's football. With an open-minded coach, we embraced the complexities of practice and utilised our evolving understanding of athlete-centred coaching to adapt our methods. After several years of club experience, I became the analyst for an international youth football squad. These experiences prompted reflection on the similarities and differences between club and international environments and men's and women's football. My understanding of the context-specificity of applied match analysis, the scarcity of research in international and female contexts, and calls for ethnographic research were the catalysts for Chapter 5. In-depth discussions with women's football coaches around their nuanced construction of practice motivated me to complete Chapter 6. Subsequently, the focus of this thesis allowed me to leverage over 10 years of applied practice to enrich these investigations.

8 References

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9 Appendices

Appendix 1: Published Study – Chapter 4

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Neophyte Experiences of Football Match Analysis: A Multiple Case Study Approach

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Neophyte Experiences of Football Match Analysis: A Multiple Case Study Approach

Performance analysis is extensively used in sport, but its pedagogical application is little understood. Given its expanding role across football, this study explored the experiences of neophyte performance analysts. Experiences of six analysis interns, across three professional football clubs, were investigated as multiple cases of new match analysis. Each intern was interviewed after their first season, with archival data providing background information. Four themes emerged from qualitative analysis: (1) 'building of relationships' was important, along with trust and role clarity; (2) 'establishing an analysis system' was difficult due to tacit coach knowledge, but analysis was established; (3) the quality of the 'feedback process' hinged on coaching styles, with balance of feedback and athlete engagement considered essential; (4) 'establishing effect' was complex with no statistical effects reported; yet enhanced relationships, role clarity, and improved performances were reported. Other emic accounts are required to further understand occupational culture within performance analysis.

Keywords: match analysis, analyst perceptions, video feedback, coach-athlete relationship, case study.

Introduction

Performance analysis is well-established within elite sport (Wright et al., 2013), and augments subjective observations of sport performance. Whilst performance analysis research is plentiful (e.g. Mackenzie & Cushion, 2013), most has focused on analysis methods (e.g. Lorains et al., 2013) or outputs (e.g. Liu et al., 2016). However, due to the individuals involved and their cognitive processes (Jones, 2009; Martindale & Collins,

2010), coaching is complex (Cushion, 2007), with interrelated factors such as role, interaction, and power (Jones et al., 2002). Therefore, as performance analysis sits within coaching, researchers are now acknowledging its complexity and are discussing its pedagogical application (Groom et al., 2011; Nelson & Groom, 2011).

There is initial agreement that pedagogical, cultural, and individual factors are all important in performance analysis (Bampouras et al., 2012; Reeves & Roberts, 2013; Wright et al., 2012); suggesting that both emic and etic accounts are important. More specifically, the learning environment, the social setting, relationships and motivation, have all influenced application. For example, the health of the coach-athlete relationship, and more precisely trust, can greatly affect athlete acceptance of performance analysis (Nelson et al., 2014). Similarly, coaches act politically with a range of motivations (Potrac & Jones, 2009). For example, analysis has been used to assert power, and this can negatively affect athlete perceptions, relationships and club culture if managed incorrectly (Booroff et al., 2016). Whilst technological development has been positive in facilitating growth in performance analysis (James, 2006); reliance on technology can be perceived negatively if coupled with a coach-centred culture (Williams & Manley, 2014). Despite these negatives, there are benefits when a positive coaching environment is created. For instance, netballers found analysis to be motivational when integrated into coaching (Jenkins et al., 2007). Additionally, elite rugby players wanted more analysis (Francis & Jones, 2014), suggesting that they embraced its worth. Although few of these studies indicated the experience of participants, this distinction is important as it can influence research transferability.

As the study of expertise can be highly effective in sharing applied knowledge (Fifer et al., 2008), experiential and peer learning in coaching is common (Erickson et al., 2008); therefore, studies that provide expert perspectives should be encouraged.

Subsequently, expertise research provides an understanding of fundamental professional attributes (Côté & Gilbert, 2009). Relatedly, practical accounts of analysis from experienced coaches, analysts and players should promote vicarious modelling in less experienced practitioners (Groom et al., 2011). An insight into the role of performance analyst at elite football clubs was achieved by Wright et al. (2013). This survey established that analysts play an important role in the provision of feedback, and their relationships with coaching staff were considered crucial. Yet, in-depth investigations of analyst interactions are required to further understand the full extent of their role. However, accounts from expert practitioners may not be transferable enough to guide neophyte analysts during their training.

Despite extensive application of performance analysis (Wright et al., 2014), only two studies have investigated the experiences of neophyte analysts. One study discussed an educational pathway towards becoming a performance analyst, and the other focused on micropolitics (Butterworth & Turner, 2014; Huggan et al., 2015); but many of the analysts' experiences within their roles remained hidden. However, role specifics have been investigated across other related professions. In physical education, the transition from trainee teacher affects practitioner independence and capability (Shoval et al., 2010). In sport psychology, knowledge of early professional development and conflicts is helpful for interns, supervisors, and educators (Tod et al., 2009). In sport coaching, coach development is influenced by context (Lemyre et al., 2007). Therefore, the aim of this study is to explore the experiences of performance analysis interns across multiple cases of match analysis in professional football.

Methods

A multiple-case study design was applied, involving in-depth investigation within and across a small number of football squads (Ashley, 2012). Each case was initially explored followed by comparisons of similarities and differences between cases (Willig, 2013). In addressing theoretical drive (Morse et al., 2006), an inductive approach was taken to this study, with both emic and etic viewpoints adopted.

To ensure rich analysis, cases and participants were purposefully sampled (Hastie & Hay, 2012). Prior to data collection, institutional ethical approval was granted. Under-17 and Under-20 squads at three Scottish professional football clubs formed the cases. Each club had recruited analysis interns from a local University to facilitate the development of new match analysis. These analysts had completed a performance analysis module and research project supervised by the first author, and were recruited via informed consent. For inclusion purposes, analysts also had one season's experience of match analysis within professional football and an honours degree in Sport Coaching. Conducting a long-term investigation, was considered important to add to other longitudinal accounts of sport science applications in football (e.g. Carling et al., 2011; Falese et al., 2016; Orhant et al., 2010). Analyst experiences also had to include: filming matches, designing computerised notational analysis tools, completing match analysis using these tools, supporting coaches and athletes, and facilitating feedback. These experiences afforded the analysts in-depth understanding of their case. Furthermore, their degree gave them an in-depth appreciation of match analysis.

Data collection involved audio-recording one-to-one semi-structured interviews between the first author and the analysts. Interviews were conducted in-person, in a private setting at the intern's place of study. The semi-structured nature of the

interviews maintained the boundaries of interest, but also permitted participants to fully discuss their experiences and opinions (Willig, 2013). Archival data consisting of analyst coursework revealed applications unique to each squad, and thus informed the interviews. Data included video reflections, notational data, and research projects. Participants were interviewed once for approximately one hour, with several days between participants. This promoted reflexivity, ensuring that dialogue was co-constructed and not directed by bias (Hastie & Hay, 2012). A broad interview guide was used with questions focused on coaching and analysis background; understanding of analysis and coaching; working with players and coaching staff; utilisation of analysis; impact of analysis; and analyst experiences and opinions. The interview guide was piloted prior to data collection, and participants had advanced notice of the guide through informed consent. In asking for detailed examples and explanations there was a focus on moving beyond capturing 'what' they did and 'how' they did it. By asking 'why' we gained a fuller understanding of each case (Martindale & Collins, 2010). While ten interns were initially recruited, data saturation was reached after random selection of six participants and seven hours of interviews; so at this point data collection was concluded (Fusch, 2015).

Data analysis proceeded simultaneously with data collection, using constant comparative analysis (Holt et al., 2012). This involved regular and systematic shifting between data collection, coding, and analysis, with in-depth comparison of similarities and differences in the data. This promoted the generation of theory that was integrated and close to the data. Braun and Clarke's (2006) six progressive steps of thematic analysis, barring transcription, were utilised to generate themes for discussion. Transcription is not a clerical task, but a method to increase familiarity and determine meaning, therefore an alternative process was employed (Halcomb & Davidson, 2006).

Initial notetaking and reflection was followed by a cycle of listening to interviews, reviewing and updating notes, and the generation of themes. Notetaking involved interpretation not recording of participant responses; and match analysis software was used to tag audio sections for review (Longomatch, Version 1.3.1, Spain, 2016).

To ensure research quality, trustworthiness and its four subcategories were employed (Shenton, 2004). Researcher familiarity with the culture under investigation, iterative questioning, triangulation, and peer review ensures credibility. Thick description of context facilitates transferability. The research design, methods, and analysis used demonstrates dependability. Confirmability was recognised through reflexivity, an audit trail, and participant member-checking (Shenton, 2004).

Results and Discussion

From the thematic review, four themes were identified as central to the experiences of the analysts. These outline the analysts' typical journey in creating new analysis with their respective squads: (1) 'building of relationships', (2) 'establishing an analysis system', (3) 'feedback process', and (4) 'establishing effect'.

Building relationships

Building relationships with coaches was vital in successfully establishing analysis; with sub-themes identified as 'trust and rapport', and 'role clarity'.

Trust and rapport

Analysts suggested that building trust and rapport with coaches was essential (Reade et al., 2008), especially given power relationships within clubs (Potrac et al., 2006):

“100% you have to get the coaches onside, because if you don’t you’re knackered, they’ll get you out the club, I’ve seen it happen.”

The importance of this relationship is outlined previously from coach and analyst perspectives (Wright et al., 2012; Wright et al., 2013). Coaches act as gatekeepers to notational analysis (Bampouras et al., 2012) and players can adopt a well-respected coach’s view unconsciously (Nelson et al., 2014). Subsequently analysts believed that relationships with coaches would constrain all aspects of their new role:

“Coaches need to trust you to take on board what you’re saying, what you’ve shown, to then relay it to players.”

Analysts reported that *“it took a while to create relationships”* and that coaches were initially *“guarded”*, citing this as *“maybe a respect thing”* or it being about *“understanding what we’re bringing to the table”*. To build trust and rapport, analysts used a range of tactics to demonstrate commitment and competence, factors also important in coach-athlete relationships (Mageau & Vallerand, 2003). Tactics included observing training sessions; travelling to away matches; completing analysis work quickly; and demonstrating sport specific knowledge. Informal opportunities to talk also helped to build initial relationships with coaches (Reade et al., 2008):

“It took them a month to learn my name ... eventually we ended up talking about normal stuff, social stuff, and from then it was ‘see how we do this, do you think we should do it like that?’ ... it took a while.”

Forming these bonds ensured coaches were willing to share their beliefs, with this knowledge essential in developing analysis. Whilst analysts were afforded access to coach-athlete interaction, most of them had little contact with the players independently. This was not due to distrust, instead it was explainable through role clarity (Jones & Wallace, 2005), with team feedback from match analysis controlled by the coach. An exception was through individual player analysis.

Role clarity

Role clarity is necessary for role satisfaction (Beauchamp et al., 2005) and success (Bray & Brawley, 2002), so awareness of roles within a team is essential (Fletcher & Arnold, 2011). Subsequently, coach and analyst required role clarity to foster effective communication. Initially, there was role ambiguity with analysts finding it difficult to establish information essential to their role. Analysts enquired about preferred playing style and key priorities, but received general answers such as “*goals, chances and set plays*”. This perhaps demonstrates that coaching know-how was tacit (Nash & Collins, 2006) and therefore difficult to verbalise (Lyle, 2003). Most of the coaches were new to analysis so “*as players they’d used it (a lot), but not as coaches*”. Indeed, one set of analysts experienced the following:

“It was the first week and we asked what the coach wanted tagged ... ‘well you’re the experts’ ... ‘go and pick out the key bits’ ... so to start with they weren’t sure how to use it.”

As coaches were unable to verbalise the nuances of their preferred playing style, analysts used observation to understand philosophy and common language; for example, in team talks. However, coach appreciation of, and comfort with analysis

improved. Subsequently, coaches asked for specific analysis to be added, like “*striker movement in behind*”. Yet, agreement of operational definitions was challenging as “*some of the debates would get quite heated*”. Nevertheless, clarity was necessary to improve communication and establish analysis system reliability.

Meanwhile, initial analyst freedom contradicted the power relations evident across the clubs, “*it is that strict, the gaffer’s the gaffer*”. The responsibility to shape the analysis information was in stark contrast to role clarification recalled, “*the analyst needs to remember he’s the analyst and not the coach*”. Other warnings of knowing your place in the organisation’s micro-politics (Thompson et al., 2015) were shared:

“That was a warning ... don’t follow up with another question ... it was the way he said it ... it was a nice warning ... you weren’t embarrassed by it ... but if you say something else he would probably just rip you.”

Two interns had prior experience of professional football as a player and referee, helping them negotiate their roles. In contrast, the others were initially unprepared for the environment:

“The personality of the coaches took me back ... their egos, I wasn’t prepared for it.”

Otherwise, there was ongoing frustration around the understanding of the analysts’ capabilities, “*they thought we were (primarily) whiz-kids with computers*”. This misconception highlights the value coaches placed on technological support. Subsequently, as technology constrains performance analysis (James, 2006), analysts must be competent with technology (Wright et al., 2013). However, as coaching

graduates, participants felt they could inform pedagogical application. Some coaches embraced this, but others did not, reaffirming the importance of role clarity and power relationships.

Establishing an analysis system

Given the newness of analysis at each club, the analysts played a significant part in shaping the system. Subsequently, 'team analysis' and 'individual analysis' were identified as sub-themes.

Team analysis

Initially analysts developed simple team analysis around goals, goal scoring opportunities, and set plays. This analysis focused on their own team as accessing opposition footage was difficult. Analysts were grateful to start with simple systems because of pressures such as live tagging, using keyboard shortcuts, refining filming, and ensuring accuracy:

"I had never done it before ... it was a great opportunity ... it was scary ... once we got into it more ... it helped."

With experience, analysts became aware that their initial system could be enhanced, "*they (analysis variables) were so basic and broad, they (coaches and athletes) weren't able to learn that greatly from it*". Subsequently, analyst attempted to develop their performance indicators, concentrating on possession. New performance indicators included goalkeeper distribution (e.g. build and long), crosses into the box, and final 1/3 entries; with success typically defined by ball retention. The number of

passes before the ball was regained, team shape, and back four distances when defending were also notated. This demonstrates progression in analyst-coach relationships and increasing analysis know-how.

Similar informal adaptation to analysis systems have been reported previously (Wright et al., 2013). This shifting focus demonstrates the short-term approach to analysis, with match highlights and statistics viewed in isolation. Comparison to previous matches was done subjectively from memory, therefore analysis was seemingly under-utilised. Yet, there are several legitimate reasons for this approach. Part-time coaches made detailed review of analysis challenging, with coaches focusing on critical incidents (Cropley et al., 2012) in the limited time available. Indeed, one club extensively used miscellaneous events at the analyst's discretion, highlighting positive clips based on negative feedback given the previous week. The aim was to give positive reinforcement, counteract public criticism, and encourage athlete persistence. Therefore, the use of analysis is complex and highly nuanced:

"I felt sorry for a player ... it was only once he let that man slip (past him) ... twice the coach said in front of everybody ... 'you need to do this' ... so I gave it a tag to show he has done it ... the player was like 'I've tried!'."

Individual analysis

Whilst sub-unit analysis was not used, individual analysis was. One club let players access individual clips on a pen drive, derived from team analysis. This is adjudged good practice, as athlete autonomy (Ryan & Deci, 2000) and self-controlled feedback (Chiviacowsky & Wulf, 2005) can positively influence athlete learning. Additionally, two clubs selected players politically *"that could progress to the first team... that would buy into it"*. This was similar to the approach taken at another professional club with

team analysis and training focussed on key individuals (Booroff et al., 2016). Conversely, across this study, individual analysis was optional with self-directed individual training facilitated. One club hoped that by offering this to a few players it might encourage others to ask for similar support:

“There’s so much scope to go much more in-depth, to look at individual stuff. If you were to do that for every player I don’t have any doubts that each player would see an improvement.”

Prior to individual analysis, performance indicators were selected through coach and athlete consultation. Analysts sent players video and statistical feedback electronically to facilitate reflection (Carson, 2008). Athletes were also encouraged to discuss their feedback with the analyst. Each analysis was basic to start, but player engagement with the process saw requests for more detailed information

“can you get more clips? ... can you break it down into sections? ... passes, tackles? ... then (sub)sections even further?”

Examples of analysis included: saves by shot type and area for a goalkeeper, and individual battles and headers for a full-back. Given their exposure to athlete-centred approaches (Hendry & Hodges, 2013), analysts shared ownership of individual analysis with players, in contrast to the typically coach-centred team analysis.

Feedback process

Within the feedback process there were three sub-themes identified: ‘balance of feedback’, ‘athlete engagement’, and ‘delivery particulars’.

Balance of feedback

Most athletes prefer positively weighted feedback (Høigaard et al., 2008), and relatedly a mastery environment (Pensgaard & Roberts, 2002). However, feedback should be legitimate if athletes are to have respect for and confidence in their coach's analysis (Nelson et al., 2014). Across the squads, one coach was particularly positive when giving team feedback from match analysis, with others focused on error correction. The particularly positive coach had greater experience in utilising analysis, and had a full-time analyst paying attention to application across the youth academy; perhaps influencing the environment created:

"Feedback (match analysis review with the U17s coach) was a lot more positive (in comparison to U20s and the first team) ... he wants to make sure he doesn't dent their confidence ... his was more constructive ... he tried to sympathise with them."

In contrast, bias towards finding fault is unsurprising given the significant role coaches play in athlete development, and the political and pressured nature of professional football (Booroff et al., 2016). At the club perceived to be most negative, there was a dichotomy between the youth coaches and their publically critical supervisors:

"'too many of you guys are going into a tackle and you're not brave enough', he pointed out (around the room) ... 'he's got it, he's not got it, you've got it, you're brave enough, he's not brave enough'."

*“A supervisor said to a player ‘that’s because you don’t have the intelligence’ ...
‘that’s not me being cheeky, I’m just being honest’.”*

This misuse of analysis is echoed across other performance contexts (Bampouras et al., 2012; Taylor et al., 2015; Williams & Manley, 2014), with success worryingly attributed to inherent traits (Rees et al., 2005). Supervisor body language was also noted as being aggressive, with similar communication perceived unfavourably by athletes (Kassing & Infante, 1999):

“We won 4-0 ... a coaching supervisor said, ‘alright boys, ready for this?’ (match analysis feedback) ... and all the players went ‘uhh!’, moaning.”

Conversely, the youth coaches still active as players, although highlighting errors, attempted to use analysis feedback as a positive educational tool; highlighting development opportunities. This approach, informed by personal playing experiences, appeared to be well received, but player opinion was not sought directly:

“The coach said, ‘I’d rather help them than stand and slaughter them’ ... he’s good at turning it so they’re learning it without making it a negative.”

The balance of feedback was generally improved as coach experience grew, highlighting coach awareness. Additionally, it is understood that we remember highlights from performances (Hughes & Bartlett, 2015), which would include significant mistakes. Subsequently, it could be unhelpful to address such errors during team analysis feedback, where extrinsic feedback from the coach would only recap the athlete’s intrinsic self-assessment (Wrisberg, 2007):

*“I said to the coaches (about showing) sending offs ... what do you want me to do?
... ‘don’t put it in, we don’t need to make him feel any worse’ ... I think then they
recognised the psychological effect.”*

Likewise, positivity in match analysis feedback was reported as being dependent upon playing position. This was particularly true at the club with the most simplistic of performance indicators, centred around goals. Yet, coaches should provide balanced feedback for all playing positions to optimise learning:

*“Defenders mostly saw mistakes ... the attackers ... would get a shot away ...
getting a pat on the back ... midfield didn’t get much.”*

Athlete engagement

Athlete-centred coaching is engaging for athletes (Hendry & Hodges, 2013), yet the typical approach within UK football is coach-centred (Cushion et al., 2012). Analysis feedback sessions were classroom based with most coaches controlling in their feedback; but they were perhaps unaware of their behaviours (Partington et al., 2015):

*“‘what we are doing is vital (being interactive), they’re having a say’ (the players)
... but they weren’t ... I tried again to have a word ... but they felt that was
interactive ... that was the problem.”*

Players were typically given a restricted voice during match analysis feedback. This frustrated the analysts, who viewed these sessions as opportunities to check

understanding and build rapport. Having declarative tactical knowledge is important in the development of game intelligence (Raab, 2003), and questioning is an effective coaching tool (Williams & Hodges, 2005). Yet, questioning tended to be closed, eliciting little dialogue, and this was reflected in the imbalance seen in coach-athlete interaction:

“The coach would freeze it (the video) at points to ask them ‘why’, but it was ‘why you not doing that?’ ... he wasn’t actually asking them; he was just saying ‘look you have done something wrong’.”

“The players did speak for more (across the season), but it was still something like the coaches spoke for 27 minutes, and the athletes spoke for 1 minute and 15 seconds (referring to a session that was timed).”

However, analysts at one club stated that players were happy with the current engagement. This is in direct contrast to Francis and Jones (2014), where athletes wanted more involvement. This difference could be due to socialisation of players into typical patterns of engagement (Williams & Manley, 2014). Another reason might be a fear of engagement in a public forum, far removed from the usual pitch environment (Booroff et al., 2016). Also, having great respect for their coach can lead to blindly accepting their opinion (Nelson et al., 2014), and may be reducing interaction.

Yet, some coaches took an alternative athlete-centred approach. These coaches created a non-threatening environment, where athletes were encouraged to share their thoughts through open questioning. This approach should allow coaches to better understand player knowledge, subsequently shaping training and further analysis feedback. This interactive style also allowed coaches to immediately address points of

uncertainty or misunderstanding. Athletes were considered more alert during athlete-centred analysis feedback; perhaps due to awareness of the increased athlete ownership in this interactive environment. Similar pedagogical thinking suggests active and collaborative learning should be fostered (Zepke & Leach, 2010); yet coaches controlled the general direction of analysis feedback by selecting clips and leading sessions. Subsequently, active learning could have been taken further:

“It wasn’t a case of ‘you have done this wrong, that’s poor, or that’s good’ ... it was very open-minded, open-questioning ... ‘why have you done this’ ... they would hear what they (the athletes) had to say ... ‘could you have done this in the future?’ ... they would talk about if they’d considered that.”

Similarly, the clubs utilising individual analysis found players engaged well with the process and reflected upon performance. Having individual time with staff promoted ownership and development of performance review and goal-setting, and encouraged individual training; subsequently this approach links well with self-determination theory (Ryan & Deci, 2000). Self-controlled feedback provides autonomy; individual feedback and goal-setting instils competence; while individual time with staff builds relatedness. Therefore, these contrasting approaches to athlete engagement warrant further investigation, especially from athlete perspectives.

Delivery particulars

Other delivery particulars were essential in creating the right feedback environment. Duration of analysis feedback was a concern, with some feedback sessions lasting 45-60 minutes or more. It is believed that important messages were diluted due to the volume

of information communicated (Williams & Hodges, 2005), and by excessive repetition.

However, coaches acknowledged the issue and amended their practice:

“At the start, coaches wanted to show everything ... it was so long ... it was an hour with 17 year olds ... I was getting bored, and it was my work.”

“Players seemed a lot more interested because it was (now) only half an hour long ... at the end (of the season) the players said they actually enjoyed it (match analysis feedback).”

In contrast, other coaches kept match analysis feedback to 20-30 minutes, and the consensus was that this length of session was ideal. The timing of analysis feedback throughout the week was also well-judged, with all coaches providing feedback early in the week. This allowed this feedback to be implemented in training. Particularly, holding feedback sessions 1-2 days after performance was viewed positively:

“I think that time to digest is important ... to give them time to deal with it (players and coaches)”.

This delay, preferred by players (Wright et al., 2016), was deemed important for emotional control (Chan & Mallett, 2011), allowing a focused and productive review (McArdle et al., 2010). Yet, some analysts believed greater regularity of analysis feedback, held immediately before associated training, may be more useful. This would reduce the volume of information given at once, and enable it to be immediately

applied. Therefore, problems with information processing and memory could be reduced (Laird & Waters, 2008).

Athletes having restricted access to footage and distance from analysis processes, although common (Bampouras et al., 2012), was considered a limitation. In contrast, players individually analysed were given their own clips, but not the entire match. Therefore, some analysts suggested that increased access via widely available file-sharing technology, would increase acceptance of, and commitment to the analysis process. However, coaches were reportedly resistant, perhaps due to autocratic preferences or because of their unfamiliarity with such technology:

“The match is on the computer ... ‘I’m terrible with computers me, I don’t know what you’re talking about’ (the coach responded).”

Reluctance to utilise technology in coaching (Butryn, 2013), and more broadly within education has been reported (Howard, 2013). Therefore, coach familiarity with technology is a consideration when establishing match analysis.

Establishing effect

In establishing effect, three sub-themes were established: ‘data tracking’, ‘player influence’, and ‘coach influence’.

Data tracking

Both enhancing performance and evidencing the impact of analysis are complex matters. Team success is ultimately judged by score-lines. However, ascertaining team, sub-unit and individual contributions towards success is difficult. Performance data can fluctuate greatly as it is impacted by multiple interacting variables such as form, team

selection, and opposition quality (Taylor et al., 2008). Another issue is when simplistic analysis is undertaken:

“The stats did lie because it said they had 60% pass completion but it was all passing amongst the back four, it wasn’t in the final third.”

Moreover, time restrictions limit analysis volume, therefore coach preferences are critical. Coaches preferred subjective information (video over statistics), loose analysis variables, and short-term utilisation of analysis (only reflecting match to match). This constrains the medium- to long-term tracking of performance (Wright et al., 2012), and unsurprisingly the data tracked showed few improvements. Indeed, the statistical effects of match analysis remain unclear, warranting further investigation.

Player influence

Despite frustration around the lack of statistical influence, analysts agreed other evidence of impact was apparent, like enhanced coach-athlete relationships (Mageau & Vallerand, 2003):

“The coach felt he had an improved relationship with the players ... and the players said this was because they were speaking with their coaches a lot more.”

Furthermore, it was believed to strengthen role clarity and team cohesion (Bray & Brawley, 2002; Pain & Harwood, 2009); for example, a player reportedly commented *“the good thing is when we are playing we can keep each other right”*, so the analyst suggested *“vicarious learning had occurred”*. In satisfied coach-athlete relationships,

shared knowledge and understanding is important (Jowett & Cockerill, 2003). Therefore, analysis processes may have formalised coach perceptions of performance for the athlete; and vice versa when athletes were given a voice during feedback sessions. Additionally, analysis may have facilitated greater informal communication between athlete and coach, with informal communication important in successful teams (Reade et al., 2008). Yet perhaps the ultimate player influence, was the perceived impact of the individual analysis:

“None of the players were in first team consideration ... seeing them get in the team was a real success ... coaches felt the individual analysis had developed them ... (players) wanted it to carry on because it helped.”

Coach Influence

As coaches facilitate the learning environment, any impact on the coach would be crucial. Notably, there was substantial engagement from younger coaches, proactive in seeking support:

“I want to go into (full-time) management after my career, and I would definitely have this!’ ... he properly took it on board.”

“The other coaches (not getting analysis support) would say ‘can you do my team this weekend?’ ... they all wanted a bit of it.”

Analysis also created extra training time, with pitch time limited due to athlete recovery. However, the integration of analysis into coaching took time, and there was certainly a learning curve to negotiate:

“From where we started ... we were really bad (at using the analysis) ... to where we left it was completely different.”

Whilst player interaction was not developed, perhaps due to power relationships in football (Cushion & Jones, 2006), other elements of delivery were fostered. For example, the balance of analysis feedback improved, possibly due to emotional intelligence (Chan & Mallett, 2011). Whilst coaches used analysis politically to conduct targeted training, *“the coaches changed training ... using tactics to get them on the ball”*; this was not at the expense of developing other players. The analysis also impacted other elements of coach decision-making, such as team tactics and training design:

“Something came up in the video and the coach would tell the players, ‘see that, that’s what we’re going to work on tonight’ ... before the video was based on the training, but now the training was going to be based on the video.”

Now, despite these successes, some analysts were left frustrated that the use of analysis had not gone far enough, *“it’s not being fully utilised ... the potential’s there”*. However, it is acknowledged that coaching is complex and problematic (Cushion, 2007). Consequently, any decision to extend the use of match analysis is far from simplistic. Therefore, the thought processes of coaches warrant further investigation.

Conclusion

This paper aimed to add another authentic account to the emerging literature on the application of performance analysis. Hopefully, it provides an insight for new practitioners and better prepares them for the occupational culture by providing a model of neophyte analyst experiences; from building initial relationships, through to establishing the effect of analysis (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: A Model of Neophyte Analyst Experiences

This model, and the associated discussion, should give experienced coaches, analysts and educators cause for reflection on their pedagogical application and training approaches. It should also encourage other researchers to share accounts of professional practice.

It is acknowledged that the transition into a new season would have been of particular interest; but this study was limited to the perceptions of a small group of neophyte analysts on one-year internships. Therefore, alternative perspectives would be valuable, particularly in-depth accounts from other relevant stakeholders such as coaches and athletes. Furthermore, this study looked at a group of practitioners from similar backgrounds and one sport. So, given the contextual specificity of coaching (Lemyre et al., 2007), emic accounts are required from different countries, sports, and practitioners. This would allow a greater understanding of performance analysis applications and its occupational culture.

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Appendix 2: Ethics Approval – Chapter 4

On 12 May 2016, at 15:46, Gary Boyd <Gary.Boyd@uws.ac.uk> wrote:

Dear Mark,

Further to your application to the school ethics committee for the study entitled; "Neophyte Experiences of Football Match Analysis: A Multiple Case Study Approach", I have received the reviewer's response and the committee is now able to **approve** your study **subject to required changes and with suggested changes**. The changes can be found in the attached review form. Your approval number is **9-5-16-001**. As with the previous study it is a condition of approval that you supply the committee with a report on the conduct of the study either at its conclusion or twelve months after approval (whichever is sooner).

Good luck with your work.

regards,

Gary

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PARTICIPANT INFORMATION

Investigators

Mark McKenna – Lecturer; School of Science and Sport

Reason for the study

Performance analysis is regularly utilised within football but we know relatively little about how to best utilise this coaching tool. Therefore we are looking for performance analysis interns at professional football youth academies to tell us about their experiences of working in the area to further inform the use of performance analysis.

What is involved in the study?

You have been approached as a performance analysis intern with a minimum of 6 months experience at a professional football club, and an Honours degree in Sport Coaching. We would require you to take part in two interviews at UWS lasting approximately one hour each. In these interviews you would be asked to discuss your experiences of using performance analysis, your experiences of working with players and coaches, and your understanding and beliefs around performance analysis as a coaching tool. Additionally you would be asked to share examples of your analysis work to help the investigator to understand your analysis process.

Confidentiality

All data will be dealt with in the strictest of confidence and will only be shared between the investigator and a small supervisory team. Data will be stored securely in accordance with University guidelines. Direct quotes from your interview may be used throughout the research paper, however this will be done anonymously through the use of pseudonyms. At no time will your identity, or the identity of your club be shared with the reader. On completion of the research study all data stored about you will be destroyed.

Risks

There are no risks involved in taking part in this study.

Right to withdraw

If you choose to participate as a participant in this study you have the right to withdraw at anytime and do not have to give any reason for doing so. Any decisions you make about volunteering or withdrawing from the study will have no positive or negative consequences as a recently finished final year student.

What you will get from the study?

You will hopefully develop a better understanding of what you think about performance analysis. In addition it is believed that this may help to develop the future use of performance analysis within your football club.

Further information

If you have any queries or require further information, do not hesitate to contact myself:

Mark McKenna

Email: mark.mckenna@uws.ac.uk

PARTICIPANT INFORMED CONSENT FORM

PARTICIPANT'S NAME:

STUDY TITLE:

I have received a copy of the project's participant information sheet and the investigator has explained to my satisfaction the purpose of the project. I understand my participation is voluntary and that I may withdraw from the project at any time. I am also aware that I am under no obligation to give reasons for withdrawal.

I also understand that my participation in, or withdrawal from the study, would have no positive or negative consequences as a recently finished final year student.

I hereby consent to participate in the research project (named above). I understand my role within the project, and my right to withdraw from the project.

Signature of volunteer: _____

Date: _____

Signature of Investigator: _____

Date: _____

Title of Activity:	Interviews
Location(s) of Work:	UWS
Brief Description of Work:	Interviews

Hazard Identification: Identify all the hazards; evaluate the risks (low / medium / high); describe all existing control measures and identify any further measures required. Specific hazards should be assessed on a separate risk assessment form and cross-referenced with this document.

Hazard(s)	Present Risk Evaluation L/M/H	Control Measures (i.e., alternative work methods / mechanical aids / engineering controls, etc.)	Risk Evaluation after control L/M/H
Lone Working: Health and safety of both participant and researcher.	Low	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Staff within the venue will be informed of when and where the interview is taking place. • Researcher will always inform someone of their whereabouts. • All interviews will be held in a safe environment for both participant and researcher. • If at any time participants feel uncomfortable we will move on from the question/topic 	Low
Interviews: participant and researcher safety.	Low		Low

Academic staff	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Technical staff	<input type="checkbox"/>	P'Grad students	<input type="checkbox"/>	U'Grad students	<input type="checkbox"/>
Maintenance staff	<input type="checkbox"/>	Office staff	<input type="checkbox"/>	Cleaning staff	<input type="checkbox"/>	Emergency personnel	<input type="checkbox"/>
Contractors	<input type="checkbox"/>	Visitors	<input type="checkbox"/>	Others	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>

Researchers to be aware of fire exits at the venues they visit.

Assessment carried out by:

Name:	Mark McKenna	Date:	04/11/2015
Signature:	Mark McKenna	Review Date:	04/11/2016

Interview Questions – Interns – Multiple Case Study

- Coaching and analysis background
 - Tell me about your experiences as a coach: your start, current/latest coaching, qualifications
 - Tell me about your experience of analysis as a player/coach/analyst
 - Tell me about your coaching philosophy (in relation to performance football)
 - When did you first become aware of it? Initial thoughts about analysis?
- Understanding of analysis and coaching
 - What do you now think about analysis within coaching? What has informed that opinion?
 - How has your opinion changed over time?
 - Tell me about how prepared you were for working at the club? What were/weren't you prepared for?
 - What helped prepare you for your time at the club? What extra preparations would have been useful?
- Working with players and coaching staff
 - Can you explain your current/previous role at your club; and the importance of relations
 - Can you describe how you worked with players and coaches? Describe a typical week
 - What worked, what didn't and what would you do differently
- Utilisation of analysis (e.g. analysis, feedback, training)
 - Describe a typical week with the club and how they trained and used analysis
 - Describe in detail feedback methods (e.g. timing, duration, set up etc)
 - What are your thoughts on the processes used
- Impact of analysis (e.g. social, relational, individual)
 - What impact did your analysis work have? Performance, training, CAR, learning environments, JDM
 - How do you know it had these effects. Can you give me an example
- Successes, failures, and barriers with analysis
 - What were your major successes/failures during your time at the club – why was this the case
 - What were the major barrier to your work and the use of analysis at the club
 - What were the major contributors to your work and the use of analysis at the club
- Future directions of analysis
 - What do you see as the future directions for analysis at the club (practical)
 - What do you see as the future directions for analysis research (research)
 - What do you see as the future directions for analysis education and training

Appendix 3: Ethics Approval – Chapter 5

From: Gary Boyd
Sent: 16 May 2016 09:20
To: Mark Mckenna <mark.mckenna@uws.ac.uk>
Subject: Ethics application

Dear Mark,

Further to your application to the school ethics committee for the study entitled; “Applying Pre and Post Match Analysis, and Motivational Video in International Women’s Youth Football: A Longitudinal Case Study”, I have received the reviewer’s comments and the committee is now able to **approve** your study **subject to required changes**. The changes can found in the attached review form. Your approval number is **11-5-16-001**. As with your previous applications this approval is conditional on the committee receiving a report at the conclusion of the study or twelve months after approval (whichever is sooner). Good luck with your work.

Regards,

Gary

Dr Gary Boyd

	Applying Pre and Post Match Analysis, and Motivational Video in International Women's
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international women's U19s football.

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PARTICIPANT INFORMATION: COACH

International Women's

Investigators

Mark McKenna – Lecturer; School of Science and Sport

Reason for the study

Performance analysis is regularly utilised within football but we know relatively little about how to best utilise this coaching tool. Therefore we are looking for international youth football coaches to tell us about their experiences of working in this area to further inform the use of performance analysis.

What is involved in the study?

You have been approached as an international youth football coach with a minimum of 12 months experience of coaching an international football squad. We would require you to take part in two interviews at your place of work lasting approximately 1 hour each. In these interviews you would be asked to discuss your experiences of and preferences around performance analysis, your coaching style and background, and your approaches towards the training of players. Additionally you (head coach only) will give permission for observations, field notes, player interviews, and squad archives to be used as part of the study.

Confidentiality

All data will be dealt with in the strictest of confidence and will only be shared between the investigator and a small supervisory team. Data will be stored securely in accordance with University guidelines. Direct quotes from your interview may be used throughout the research paper, however this will be done anonymously through the use of pseudonyms. At no time will your identity be shared with the reader. On completion of the research study all data stored about you and the squad will be destroyed.

Risks

There are no risks involved in taking part in this study.

Right to withdraw

If you choose to participate as a participant in this study you have the right to withdraw at anytime and do not have to give any reason for doing so. Any decision you make about volunteering or withdrawing from the study will have no positive or negative consequences regarding the analysis support currently received.

What you will get from the study?

You will hopefully develop a better understanding of what you think about performance analysis. In addition it is believed that this may help to develop the future use of performance analysis with your squad.

Further information

If you have any queries or require further information, do not hesitate to contact myself:

Mark McKenna

Email:

Personal details withheld.

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION: PLAYER

International Women's

Investigators

Mark McKenna – Lecturer; School of Science and Sport

Reason for the study

Performance analysis is regularly utilised within football but we know relatively little about how to best utilise this coaching tool. Therefore we are looking for international youth football players to tell us about their experiences performance analysis to further inform its application.

What is involved in the study?

You have been approached as an international youth football player with a minimum of 12 months experience of being part of an international football squad. We would require you to take part in an interview at your place of work, study, or training lasting approximately 1 hour. In these interviews you would be asked to discuss your experiences of using performance analysis, your experiences of working with coaching staff, and your understanding and beliefs around performance analysis as a coaching tool.

Confidentiality

All data will be dealt with in the strictest of confidence and will only be shared between the investigator and a small supervisory team. Data will be stored securely in accordance with University guidelines. Direct quotes from your interview may be used throughout the research paper, however this will be done anonymously through the use of pseudonyms. At no time will your identity be shared with the reader. On completion of the research study all data stored about you will be destroyed.

Risks

There are no risks involved in taking part in this study.

Right to withdraw

If you choose to participate as a participant in this study you have the right to withdraw at anytime and do not have to give any reason for doing so. Any decision you make about volunteering or withdrawing from the study will have no positive or negative consequences as an international football player.

What you will get from the study?

You will hopefully develop a better understanding of what you think about performance analysis.

Further information

If you have any queries or require further information, do not hesitate to contact myself:

Mark McKenna

Email:

Personal details withheld.

PARTICIPANT INFORMED CONSENT FORM

PARTICIPANT'S NAME:

STUDY TITLE:

Video in International Women's

I have received a copy of the project's participant information sheet and the investigator has explained to my satisfaction the purpose of the project. I understand my participation is voluntary and that I may withdraw from the project at any time. I am also aware that I am under no obligation to give reasons for withdrawal.

I also understand that my participation in or withdrawal from the study would have no positive or negative consequences.

I hereby consent to participate in the research project (named above). I understand my role within the project, and my right to withdraw from the project.

Signature of volunteer: _____

Date: _____

Signature of Investigator: _____

Date: _____

Title of Activity:	Case study, action research and notation in sport organisations.
Location(s) of Work:	Various local sport training facilities
Brief Description of Work:	Case study, action research and notation in sport organisations: Observations, interviews, video recording, computer work on site.

Hazard Identification: Identify all the hazards; evaluate the risks (low / medium / high); describe all existing control measures and identify any further measures required. Specific hazards should be assessed on a separate risk assessment form and cross-referenced with this document.

Hazard(s)	Present Risk Evaluation L/M/H	Control Measures (i.e., alternative work methods / mechanical aids / engineering controls, etc.)	Risk Evaluation after control L/M/H
Lone Working: Health and safety of both participant and researcher.	Low	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Staff within the venue will be informed of when and where the interview is taking place. Researcher will always inform someone of their whereabouts. 	Low
Interviews: participant and researcher safety.	Low	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All interviews will be held in a safe environment for both participant and researcher. If at any time participants feel uncomfortable we will move on from the question/topic 	Low
Video recording, observation and extensive computer work	Low	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Filming and observation to take place from a safe location. Weather appropriate protective clothing to be worn. Regular breaks to be taken from camera or computer 	Low

Academic staff	X	Technical staff		P'Grad students		U'Grad students	
Maintenance staff		Office staff		Cleaning staff		Emergency personnel	
Contractors		Visitors		Others	X		

Additional Information: Identify any additional information relevant to the activity, including supervision, training requirements, special emergency procedures, requirement for health surveillance etc.

All inexperienced researchers are to be trained in the aforementioned technique prior to implementing them with participants. Researchers to be aware of fire exits at the venues they visit.

Assessment carried out by:

Name:	Mark McKenna	Date:	04/11/2015
Signature:	Mark McKenna	Review Date:	04/11/2016

Appendix 4: Ethics Approval – Chapter 6

03/08/2022

Dear Mr Mark Mckenna,

Your application 18187: A professional football coach's journey with match analysis: a case study., submission reference 15447, has been approved, with conditions, by the Health and Life Sciences SEC. **You may proceed with your study provided you meet the conditions outlined below:**

Title	Comment
Please upload a copy of the Participant Information Sheet(s)	PIS refers to the school of Science and Sport, this should be changed to HLS.

If you wish to make any significant changes to your study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Personal details withheld.

Dr Gary Boyd

Filter Questions

- I confirm I have read the UWS and my School Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship.
(please tick to continue)

Pre-screening Questions

Does your work involve any of the following. (please tick all that apply)

- Human Participants
 Personal Data
 Animals
 Risk to the Investigator
- None of the above

Based on your answers to the above questions you should complete the remainder of this form and submit it to your school ethics committee for approval **PRIOR** to commencing any work on your project. Please click Next to proceed.

Applicant Details

Position of Principal Investigator

Staff

Principal Investigator

Title	First Name	Surname
<input type="text" value="Mr"/>	<input type="text" value="Mark"/>	<input type="text" value="Mckenna"/>
Email <input type="text" value="mark.mckenna@uws.ac.uk"/>		

School

Health and Life Sciences

Are there any co-applicants

- Yes
- No

Project Information

Title of Study

A professional football coach's journey with match analysis: a case study.

Primary purpose of the study

Postgraduate Dissertation

Where will the proposed research take place?

Online

How will the costs of the study be met?

No costs

Previous Approvals

Has the proposed study been considered by any other ethics committee?

- Yes
- No

Purpose, justification, design and methodology

Please give a full summary of the purpose, justification, design and methodology of the planned study: (word limit 1000 words)

Match analysis is widely applied in high-performance team sport settings (Prim and van Rooyen, 2013, Home, 2014, Lomax, 2018, Carling et al., 2016) and has three key stakeholders. Athletes are the end-users of match analysis (Bampouras et al., 2012), analysts are critical to the production of meaningful output (Wright et al., 2013), and coaches orchestrate the process (Nicholls et al., 2018). Therefore, understanding match analysis from the coach's perspective is essential. High-performance coaches have reported that match analysis is critical in assessing team performance (Martin et al., 2018, Wright et al., 2012) and can significantly impact their coaching practice (Nicholls et al., 2018). Specifically, coaches report that match analysis informs their planning and decision-making (Jenkins, 2017, Wright et al., 2013), such as guiding team tactics and problem-solving (Brümmer, 2019, Groom et al., 2011, Groom et al., 2012, Nelson and Groom, 2012). Beyond these perceived benefits, several surveys have superficially described patterns of match analysis utilisation (Wright et al., 2013, Wright et al., 2012, Nicholls et al., 2019, Nicholls et al., 2018). However, these studies fail to illuminate the how and why of match analysis application, which is vital in understanding coaching practice given its context-specific nature (Martindale and Collins, 2010).

Contrastingly, Groom et al. (2011) developed a grounded theory of match analysis application across the English F.A.'s international youth football coaches. Amongst the study findings was the consideration of athletes in the design and implementation of match analysis; however, given the nature of this research, the study failed to detail what these pedagogical accommodations involved. Yet, both positive and negative athlete experiences support the argument for athlete-centred match analysis. For example, docility was reported in athletes with limited power who faced relentless surveillance in a match analysis setting (Williams and Manley, 2014). Meanwhile, athletes identified value in discursive video feedback and the personal reflections this approach can facilitate (Francis and Jones, 2014, Middlemas and Harwood, 2017, Wright et al., 2016). However, despite the outcome of match analysis being largely dependent on the coach's intentions and actions, little more has been reported on this matter. Subsequently, further investigation of coach experiences of match analysis is needed. Moreover, given that the road towards expertise in coaching is prolonged and uncertain (Côté and Gilbert, 2009, Nash and Collins, 2006), investigating coach development in match analysis application is also required to enhance our understanding of best practice (Côté and Gilbert, 2009). Consequently, this study will explore one professional coach's longitudinal journey with match analysis and how they have developed their application match analysis over time.

Given that the application of match analysis is complex, a qualitative and interpretative paradigm will be followed (Armour & Griffiths, 2012). Specifically, a single case study design is selected to investigate a coach's developmental journey with match analysis (Eisenhardt & Graebner, 2007; Willig, 2013). A single case study can be impactful, particularly when sharing the understanding of highly experienced coaches (e.g. Mallett and Coulter, 2016, Taylor et al., 2014). As little has been reported on the phenomena under investigation, an exploratory approach will be adopted (Yin, 2003). In this study, one high-performance football coach will be purposefully selected to ensure the selection of an information-rich case (Russell et al., 2005) using the following inclusion criteria. The participant must have at least ten years of applied experience in leading the delivery and development of match analysis feedback. The participant must also hold a UEFA A license. These criteria ensure the participant has a well-developed coaching philosophy and extensive football and match analysis knowledge and understanding. The case will be pragmatically selected from the researcher's professional network.

Interviews will be the primary data source as they capture participants' thoughts, opinions, and attitudes (Sparkes & Smith, 2014). Semi-structured interviews will help focus data collection whilst offering flexibility to explore new and context-specific lines of enquiry (Purdy, 2014). Interviewing will move beyond the 'what', the 'how' and the 'why' of practice (Martindale & Collins, 2010). The participant coach will be interviewed approximately six times, lasting about 1 hour each, and the interviews will be audio-recorded to facilitate active listening (Louw et al., 2011). An interview guide will be developed through pilot interviewing (Sampson, 2004), which may include: participant background, coaching philosophy, analysis practices, critical incidents and lessons, constraints, and future analysis directions. Each interview will also focus on open-ended questions, probing for elaboration, being silent to coax, and checking for understanding (Braun & Clarke, 2013). Multiple weeks will be left between interviews to allow initial data analysis to inform the following interview and enable reflexive thinking (Holt et al., 2012).

Case study research typically involves multi-methods (Willig, 2013), so the participant will be asked to provide examples of match analysis output from across their career. This data will be used to facilitate participant remembering and to support the thick description of the case. The researcher will collect this data from the participant via a shared OneDrive folder (or equivalent). Only the participant and researcher will have access. The researcher may share examples of the match analysis output onscreen during interviews to stimulate the recall of the research participant (Raya-Castellano et al., 2020, Stodter and Cushion, 2019, Hall et al., 2021). Additionally, insight from approximately six significant others (e.g. players, coaches, analysts) will be captured to augment the coach's narrative (Mallett and Coulter, 2016, Taylor et al., 2014). These participants will be identified throughout the interview process by the coach. Each significant other will be asked to partake in one interview, lasting about 1 hour. In this interview, they will be asked about their experiences of match analysis during their time with the participant coach.

The interview data will be analysed thematically (Braun & Clarke, 2013), which involves familiarisation with recorded interviews, generating initial codes, searching for and sorting themes, reviewing and refining data descriptions and hierarchy, and writing the report. In considering quality assurance, the notion of trustworthiness and its criteria will be used (Shenton, 2004). The credibility of study results is enhanced through multiple quality assurance methods, including triangulation, iterative questioning, data saturation, and critical friends. Confirmability is established by checking for fair representation with research participants before dissemination, whilst thick description will be used to provide context-specific details and enhance the likelihood of transferability. Dependability is considered by using well-established methods and rationale for the decisions taken.

How has the scientific quality of the proposed research project been assessed?

- Independent external review
- Review within a company
- Review within a multi-centre research group
- Review within the principal investigator's institution
- Review within the research team
- Review by supervisor/director of studies
- Other

Sample Size

Please explain/justify your intended sample size:

A small sample of participants will be recruited in line with the case study research design adopted.

Analysis and Presentation

Please explain how you will analyse, present/disseminate the data you intend to collect:

Data will be analysed using reflexive thematic analysis. The aim is to disseminate the study data in a peer-reviewed publication.

Interviews/Questionnaires

Does the proposed research involve the use of individual/group interviews or questionnaires?

- Yes
- No

Please upload a copy of the Questionnaire or Interview Schedule

Documents					
Type	Document Name	File Name	Version Date	Version	Size
Default	Interview Questions – Football Coach's Journey with PA	Interview Questions – Football Coach's Journey with PA.docx	28/06/2022	1.0	15.5 KB
Default	Interview Questions – Football Coach's Journey with PA - Significant Others	Interview Questions – Football Coach's Journey with PA - Significant Others.docx	28/06/2022	1.0	15.4 KB

Will proposed interviews or questionnaires discuss topics that might be sensitive, embarrassing or upsetting for participants or is it possible that criminal or other disclosures requiring action could occur during the study?

- Yes
 No

Impact on Participants

Please provide details of how you will recruit participants to your study:

Identify:

The prospective participant coach will be identified through the researcher's professional network. The significant others in the coach's journey will be identified by the participant coach during data collection.

Approach:

The participant coach is known by the researcher so will be approached either in person or over the phone. The significant others known by the researcher will also be approached over the phone or in person. The significant others the researcher does not know will be approached via email, with the participant coach providing contact email addresses.

Recruit:

Each potential participant will be provided with a participant information sheet, will have the opportunity to ask questions, and will be given 7-days to decide whether to participate in the study. Participants will then be recruited via signed informed consent.

Will participants be from any of the following groups? (Please tick all that apply)

- Children under 16
 Adults with learning disabilities
 Adults with a terminal illness
 Adults in emergency situations
 Adults with mental illness (particularly if detained under the mental health act)
 Adults with dementia
 Adults in Scotland who are unable to consent for themselves
 Those who could be considered to have a particularly dependent relationship with the investigator
 Other
None of the above

Are there any special pressures which would make it difficult for potential participants to refuse to take part in your study? (e.g., relationship to the investigator?)

The prospective participant coach has previously worked with the researcher. However, that was over a decade ago and no power relationships remain. However, it will be made clear in the participant information sheet that they are under no obligation to participate in this study. The significant others identified will have worked with the participant coach and have been identified as being significant in their developing application of match analysis (e.g. players, coaches, performance analysts). However, it will be made clear in the participant information sheet that they are under no obligation to participate in this study.

Will study participants be paid to take part?

- Yes
 No

What is the expected duration of participation in the study for each participant?

Participant coach - 6 interviews, each lasting approximately 1 hour.
Significant others - 1 interview, lasting approximately 1 hour.

Will informed consent be obtained from study participants?

Yes

No

Please provide details of how you will obtain this consent and the information you will provide to potential participants to allow them to make an informed choice about whether or not to participate in your research.

Each potential participant will be provided with a participant information sheet, will have the opportunity to ask questions, and will be given 7-days to decide whether to participate in the study. Participants will then be recruited via signed informed consent.

Please upload a copy of the Participant Information Sheet(s)

Documents					
Type	Document Name	File Name	Version Date	Version	Size
Default	Participant Information Sheet - Coach Journey with PA - Coach	Participant Information Sheet - Coach Journey with PA - Coach.docx	28/06/2022	1.0	78.5 KB
Default	Participant Information Sheet - Coach Journey with PA - Significant Others	Participant Information Sheet - Coach Journey with PA - Significant Others.docx	28/06/2022	1.0	78.1 KB

Please upload a copy of your Consent Form(s)

Documents					
Type	Document Name	File Name	Version Date	Version	Size
Default	Informed Consent Form - Coach's Journey with PA	Informed Consent Form - Coach's Journey with PA.docx	28/06/2022	1.0	73.8 KB

Is the study likely to cause any discomfort or distress, either physical or psychological (see UWS Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship)?

Yes

No

Does the proposed research involve any physically invasive procedures?

Yes

No

Other ethical considerations

Does the proposed research involve deception regarding aims, objectives or the identity of the investigator?

- Yes
- No

Will research participants be debriefed after their participation?

- Yes
- No

Are there any other Ethical Considerations you wish to bring to the attention of the committee?

- Yes
- No

Personal Data

What measures will you put in place to ensure the confidentiality of personal data gathered during your study?

To provide the participant coach and significant others with anonymity, no individual, group or organisation will be named in the research output generated from this research. Instead, pseudonyms will be used. However, given the specific nature of this case study, there is a small risk of readers close to the case identifying the participant coach and perhaps significant others too. Therefore, this will be highlighted to potential participants as a risk in both the participant information sheet and informed consent form. The significant others will know of the participant coach's involvement in the study.

Who will have access to the data collected during the study and how will you keep it confidential?

Only the lead researcher will have access to the raw data generated in this study. The study collaborators will have access to the work product from the reflexive thematic analysis. Data will be stored securely on password-protected computers.

Supporting Documents

Please upload any additional supporting documents you are submitting with this application

Documents

Type	Document Name	File Name	Version Date	Version	Size
Default	Risk Assessment Form INTERVIEWS - Coach's Journey with PA	Risk Assessment Form INTERVIEWS - Coach's Journey with PA.docx	28/06/2022	1.0	77.3 KB
Default	Recruitment Email - Significant Others	Recruitment Email - Significant Others.docx	28/06/2022	1.0	15.6 KB

Signatures

Principal Investigator

The information supplied above is, to the best of my knowledge and belief, accurate. I have read the university ethics guidelines and clearly understand my obligations and the rights of study participants, particularly in relation to obtaining valid consent.

Signed: This form was signed by Mr Mark Mckenna (mark.mckenna@uws.ac.uk) on 28/06/2022 12:19

Interview Guide: Coach Interviews

This specific content of this interview guide will be developed through interview piloting after ethical approval is granted.

- Football experience
 - Can you tell me about your experiences in football (e.g. where you have worked)?
 - Can you tell me about your experience of match analysis?
- General perceptions of match analysis
 - Can you remember when you first became aware of match analysis and what you thought about it?
 - What do you think about it now? What has led you to that opinion?
 - Has your opinion changed over time, and if so, why?
 - How would you describe your coaching philosophy/style?
 - Has this changed over time, and if so, how?
- Describe match analysis and feedback approaches at each phase of career (e.g. analysis, feedback, training)
 - Can you describe a typical week with club (A, B, C etc) and how match analysis was used?
 - Can you describe the feedback methods used in the delivery of match analysis feedback?
 - Can you generally describe the typical content of feedback in match analysis?
 - Can you compare how match analysis feedback compares to feedback in coaching sessions (in both delivery and content)?
- Perceptions of match analysis (explore the structure explained above)
 - Why is match analysis delivered in these ways?
 - What do you like about this/these approaches to match analysis?
 - What do you not like about this/these approaches to match analysis?
 - What have been the major successes/failures in the use of match analysis? (iterative questioning)
- Impact and constraints
 - What impact does the match analysis have on the coaching environment, training, performance?
 - Can you provide me with examples?
 - What factors help to promote the successful use of match analysis? (task, people, environment)
 - Where is this evident across your career?
 - What factors help to restrict the successful use of match analysis? (task, people, environment)
 - Where is this evident across your career?

Interview Guide: Significant Others

This specific content of this interview guide will be developed through interview piloting after ethical approval is granted.

- Football experience
 - Can you tell me about your experiences in football (e.g. where you have worked/played)?
 - Can you tell me about your experience of match analysis?

- General perceptions of match analysis
 - What are your thoughts on match analysis?
 - What has led you to that opinion?

- Describe the match analysis and feedback approaches experienced when working with THE COACH
 - Can you describe a typical week with THE COACH, what was involved?
 - Can you describe how match analysis was used?
 - Duration, location, attendance, content, delivery style?
 - Can you describe the coaching style adopted by THE COACH?
 - How did this differ if at all between analysis and pitch?

- Perceptions of match analysis (explore the structure explained above)
 - What did you like about this/these approaches to match analysis/coaching?
 - What did you not like about this/these approaches to match analysis/coaching?
 - What would you have changed if you could about the use of match analysis with THE COACH?
 - What impact did the match analysis have on the coaching environment, training, performance?
 - Probes:
 - Can you provide me with examples?
 - How did that make you feel?

Risk Assessment Form – Online interviews

Department: Health & Life Sciences			Risk Assessment No:			
Assessed by: Mark McKenna			Location: Online			
Audited by: N/A			Dates of work: July 2022 – Jan 2023			
Description of work activity to be assessed:						
Online Interviews						
What are the individual hazards?	Who might be harmed and what is the RISK?	What are you already doing?	Do you need to do anything else to manage this risk?	Action by whom?	Action by when?	Done
<u>Work factors:</u> Interviews	RISK: LOW Researcher/ Participants	Researcher to be trained in techniques to be used. Interviews held securely on MS Teams.	Researcher to complete training. Lone worker to carry mobile phone for emergencies.	MMcK	Jun 2022	Yes
<u>Travel:</u>	RISK: LOW Researcher	No travel required	No	N/A	N/A	N/A
<u>Location:</u>	RISK: LOW Researcher/ Participants	Placements in the UK with no significant local risks.	No	N/A	N/A	N/A
<u>Environment:</u>	RISK: LOW Researcher/ Participants	No environmental health risks.	No	N/A	N/A	N/A
<u>Individual student factors:</u>	RISK: LOW Researcher	No long-term medical conditions or disability. Student has relevant knowledge and skills.	Researcher to update university of any change to circumstances.	Researcher	Ongoing	Ongoing
<u>Insurance Limitations:</u>	RISK: LOW Researcher/ Participants	Virtual environment only	No	N/A	N/A	N/A
Additional Information:						
None.						

Assessment carried out by:

Assessed by:	Mark McKenna	Date:	Jun 2022
Signature:	Mark McKenna	Review Date:	n/a
Audited by:	N/A	Date:	n/a
Signature:	N/A	Review Date:	n/a

Dear {potential research participant},

My name is Mark McKenna, and I am a sport lecturer at the University of the West of Scotland. As part of my research, I am investigating a coach's journey with match analysis; the coach is {name the coach}.

During our interviews, you have been identified as a significant other who has shared in {name the coach}'s journey during your time together at {name the setting(s)}. Given this, I am writing to ask if you would be willing to be interviewed about your experiences of match analysis during this time.

To allow you to make an informed decision, I have attached an information sheet with further details about the study. If you could let me know whether you would be prepared to participate, that would be greatly appreciated.

Thanks for your consideration,

Mark

{INSERT EMAIL SIGNATURE}

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION: COACH

A professional football coach's journey with match analysis: a case study.

Investigator

Mark McKenna – Lecturer; School of Science and Sport

Reason for the study

Performance analysis is used frequently in football, and its application is decided mainly by the head coach. Despite this, relatively little is known about how coaches perceive and apply match analysis; and nothing is known about how coaches develop their use of match analysis over time. Therefore, we are looking for a professional football coach to share their journey with match analysis.

What is involved in the study?

You have been approached as a professional football coach with a minimum of 10 years of experience using match analysis in high-performance settings and a UEFA A licence. The study involves a series of approximately six interviews, each lasting about 1 hour. In these interviews, you will be asked about your experiences of using performance analysis across each phase of your career. These interviews will be held online on MS Teams (or equivalent) and audio-recorded (not video-recorded). You will also be asked to share examples of your match analysis with the researcher to help them understand your approach(es). Lastly, you will be asked to identify significant others that have shared parts of your journey with match analysis (e.g. players, coaches, analysts). We will look to recruit and interview approximately six significant others who will be asked to share their experiences of match analysis when working with you.

Confidentiality

Data will be dealt with in the strictest of confidence and will only be shared between the investigator and a small research team. Data will be stored securely following University guidelines. Direct quotes from your interview may be used throughout the research paper. However, this will be done anonymously using pseudonyms. At no time will your identity be shared with the reader. Upon publication of the research report, we will destroy the audio files collected.

Risks

There is a minimal risk that someone could deduce your participation in this study. The significant others approached to participate in this study will know about your involvement in this research. There are no other risks involved in taking part in this study.

Right to withdraw

If you choose to participate in this study, you have the right to withdraw at any time and do not have to give any reason. Any decision you make about volunteering or withdrawing from the study will have no positive/negative consequences on your relationship with the researcher.

What will you get from the study?

You will hopefully benefit from reflecting on your career and your use of match analysis.

Further information

If you have any queries or require further information, do not hesitate to contact me:

Mark McKenna

Email:

Personal details withheld.

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION: SIGNIFICANT OTHERS

A professional football coach's journey with match analysis: a case study.

Investigator

Mark McKenna – Lecturer; School of Science and Sport

Reason for the study

Performance analysis is used frequently in football, and its application is decided mainly by the head coach. Despite this, relatively little is known about how coaches perceive and apply match analysis; and nothing is known about how coaches develop their use of match analysis over time. Therefore, we are looking for a professional football coach, to share their journey with match analysis.

What is involved in the study?

You have been identified by the main participant (the coach) in this study as a significant other that has shared part of their journey with match analysis (e.g. as a player, coach, or analyst). Therefore, I would like to interview you once for approximately 1 hour. At this interview you will be asked about your experiences of match analysis whilst working the coach. The interview will be held online on MS Teams (or equivalent) and audio-recorded (not video-recorded).

Confidentiality

Data will be dealt with in the strictest of confidence and will only be shared between the investigator and a small research team. Data will be stored securely following University guidelines. Direct quotes from your interview may be used throughout the research paper. However, this will be done anonymously using pseudonyms. At no time will your identity be shared with the reader. Upon publication of the research report, we will destroy the audio files collected.

Risks

There is a minimal risk that someone could deduce your participation in this study. The coach will know you've been identified as a potential participant in this study. There are no other risks involved in taking part in this study.

Right to withdraw

If you choose to participate in this study, you have the right to withdraw at any time and do not have to give any reason. Any decision you make about volunteering or withdrawing from the study will have no positive/negative consequences on your relationship with the coach.

Further information

If you have any queries or require further information, do not hesitate to contact me:

Mark McKenna

Email:

Personal details withheld.

Informed Consent Form

Title of Project: A professional football coach's journey with match analysis: a case study.

Name of Researcher: Mark McKenna

Please initial box

- 1 I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet dated _____ for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions.

- 2 I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason.

- 3 I understand that my interview(s) with the researcher will be audio-recorded.

- 4 I agree to take part in the above study.

Name of Participant:

Signature:

Date:

Name of researcher:

Signature:

Date:

1 copy for participant and 1 for researcher